

**How can the Value Chain and Supply Chain of SMEs and Micro-Businesses
Facilitate the Development of the Economy of Pakistan?**

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**The thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement of the University of
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Declaration

I declare that I have not been registered for any other research awards while I am listed as a candidate for the aforementioned degree. The primary data, findings, results, and conclusions presented in this thesis are the product of the listed candidate and have not been submitted for consideration for any other comparable academic award.

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Abstract

The study is focused on the need to investigate value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro-businesses facilitating the economic development of Pakistan. Literature shows that SMEs are the core contributors to Pakistan's employment level. However, a significant gap was explored in previous studies regarding the SMEs of Pakistan and their value chain processes. Though various studies uncover the different aspects of value chain, these are not explicitly related to Pakistani Automobile and Petrochemical firms. Thus, the research aims to explore these sectors' value chain attributes to eradicate existing research gap. Further, research objectives are designed to explore the contribution of these sectors to Pakistan's economic development. The sustainable practices of SMEs, profit-sharing mechanisms, and the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs are other prominent attributes that surround the objectives of this research.

Qualitative data collection methods were utilised in the study to accumulate in-depth findings. Interviews were used as the most appropriate strategic tool to accumulate data from participants of selected SMEs in Automobile and Petrochemical industries. Thematic analysis is deployed in a data analysis process, and responses are coded using a Vivo coding scheme. The findings of this study indicate the constructive and significant role of SMEs and Microbusinesses in cultivating a supply chain and value chain of the selected Automobile and Petrochemical Industries of Pakistan. Results are revealing limitations of SMEs such as the lack of appropriate use of technology, lack of resources, and financial support, besides a few other key areas. Results of qualitative thematic analysis results also revealed that despite these disadvantages, the collaborations of large firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses had facilitated their organisational performance through effective use of expertise, cost advantage, knowledge sharing, and skills development. The overall research findings concludes the impact of SMEs and microbusinesses on Pakistan's economic state is also analysed with the help of participants' viewpoints. These viewpoints show that SMEs and MSMEs can contribute to economic stability in Pakistan by influencing GDP level, employment growth, and bringing more dollar remittances to the country.

Moreover, the research recommends further in-depth exploration of this area, and investigators have numerous future research options. It is necessary for prospect investigators to conduct studies on a similar topic by eliminating the methodological limitations of this research. In this way, a better picture of Pakistani SMEs and their value chain operations can be portrayed in the literature. The research recommends strategic contributions from policymakers. They should initiate favourable policies for SMEs which can include easing regulatory burdens, business registration process, and access of micro finance. The government can contribute with their strategic initiatives of PPPs, where SMEs' collaboration can be mandated for Public sector large-scale firms. SMEs can use these large-scale business collaborations for the improvisation of their value chain operations. The research recommends that SMEs, microbusinesses and large enterprises enter value chain operations to improvise cost reduction, quality, procurement needs, product differentiation, and other factors. Automobile SMEs or MSMEs are recommended to shift from electric to hybrid-style vehicles for catering reductions in waste and CO2 emissions. Petrochemical SMEs or MSMEs are recommended to gain assistance from large-scale firms to design a proper material recycling process for sustainability needs. The implications of the study portray a positive social change in this area. This can be grounded in improvements in the value chain of SMEs in terms of employment levels, poverty, and other positive changes in the economic development of Pakistan.

Keywords: Value Chain, SMES, Microbusiness, Collaboration, Supply Chain, Economy of Pakistan, Knowledge Transfer, Knowledge Sharing, Automobile Industry, Petrochemical Industry.

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List of Acronyms

SMEs: Small and Medium Enterprises

MSMEs: Micro-Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

PVC: Polymerization of Vinyl Chloride

PPPs: Public Private Partnerships

CSR: Corporate Social Responsibility

GDP: Gross Domestic Product

SECP: Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan

VCA: Value Chain Analysis.

GVC: Global Value Chains

CAGR: Compound Annual Growth Rate.

SCC: Supply Chain Collaboration.

RBT: Resource-Based Theory.

SAP: Systems, Applications & Products

ERPs: Enterprise Resource Planning

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1 Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter aims to highlight areas creating a need to conduct this study. The chapter introduces key concepts and reasons behind selecting a targeted research topic. The research background provides a brief discussion of key concepts. One of the key concepts of value chain deliberated in the background shows that it denotes the whole life cycle of a product or process, starting from raw material sourcing, semi-finished or finished material, production, and consumption to disposal/recycling processes of a firm. The background shows that this chain of value-adding activities is influential in affecting firms' economic prosperity and survival.

The automotive industry is one of the selected sector in this research which involves the designing, development, manufacturing, marketing, and distribution of motor vehicles. The firms selected from this sector are involved in the manufacturing of spare parts and OEM. The second sector of Petrochemicals industry produces polymers which possess similar properties like plastics and a PVC firm selected in this research is involved in the production of garment hangers. The research problem shows that SMEs are core contributors to the country's employment growth and GDP.

However, the chapter indicates that Pakistani SMEs have not performed significantly to make a good contribution to the GDP. For instance, only 4% of the GDP was contributed by the Automobile sector. Therefore, the research intends to explore the supply chain processes of petrochemical and automobile industries in Pakistan for the eradication of this problem. The reason for selecting these sectors is that they exhibit more potential for international market penetration. Another reason was identified in the research gap as most of the previous studies on value chain operations do not target these sectors of Pakistan. Thus, the research intends to explore different value chain disciplines which are knowledge management, technology transfer, sustainable supply chain practices, and the creation of global value chains. These disciplines were primarily focused on evaluating Pakistani SMEs and their value chains so that their contributions in the economic development of Pakistan could be assessed.

The chapter provides brief insight into the research aim, objectives, question, and problem identified in the study. Rationale of the research shows that different Automobile and Petrochemical SMEs are selected to get a broader view of the role

and importance of SMEs. The study's implications show that microbusinesses and SMEs can benefit from this research by improving their global value chains which can ultimately affect the economic development of Pakistan. Research settings discuss the use of in-depth interviews with the organisation's managerial and executive level staff of SMEs. Moreover, a layout of the study is offered at the end of this chapter. The layout shows that introduction, literature review, research methodology, data analysis, discussion, and conclusion chapters are added to the study.

1.1 Background of the study

The significant role of SMEs and other micro-businesses in the value and supply chain of automobile and petrochemical industries is one of the key elements in the development of Pakistan's economy. The EU has classified the SMEs based on headcount and the company's turnover or a balance sheet total.

Table 1: Categorisation of the enterprise (EU recommendation 2003/361) (Source: EUR-Lex, 2023)

Company category	Staff headcount	Turnover	or	Balance sheet total
Medium-sized	< 250	≤ € 50 m		≤ € 43 m
Small	< 50	≤ € 10 m		≤ € 10 m
Micro	< 10	≤ € 2 m		≤ € 2 m

Consequentially, the working definition of micro-businesses is that firms with up to 10 in numbers of employees are classified as micro-businesses (Ayyagari, Demirgüç-Kunt and Beck, 2003). The SMEs working in a specific industry are considered an important part of its value chain that is an integral part of strategic planning that assists organisational and national gains. According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) (2011), a value chain denotes the full life cycle of a product or process, including sourcing raw, semi-finished or finished material, production, consumption and disposal/recycling processes. The idea of sustainability is to ensure the effective utilisation of natural resources in a manner that does not threaten the ability of future generations to use those resources. Moreover, a sustainable value chain approach permits both industry and society to better

comprehend and address the environmental challenges linked with the life cycle of products, processes and services. Furthermore, in this study, the supply chain is an explicit part of a value chain that encompasses mandatory processes. The model of the global value chain identifies that the design, production and marketing of several products includes a chain of activities divided between organisations situated in different areas. The value chain describes the activities required to bring a valuable product from its conception to the final consumer (CISL, 2023).

Figure 1: Chain of value-adding activities (Source: McCormick and Schmitz, 2001)

1.1.1 Economic background of Pakistan

There are three types of economic systems: Free Economy, Command Economy and Mixed Economy. Pakistan's economic system is a mixed economic system. In this type of economic system, both private businesses, as well as government control exist. Nowadays, all the present economies are mixed/dual economies in which characteristics of both economies are blended to survive new economic and social problems (Britannica, 2020).

These days, free market economies incorporate instructions from the government in rectifying economic problems, modifying financial and fiscal policies, and making price decisions.

Pakistan's mixed economy includes three important sectors: agriculture, industry, and services. The contribution of these three industries towards the economy is 21% of GDP, 20.9% of GDP, and a notable 57.7% of GDP, respectively. The trade report shows that the trading account has been in a shortfall for many years, and the situation has not changed much now because of too much reliance on imported goods. This has led to the disturbance of Pakistan's foreign exchange investments; not only that, these economic crises have led to the continuous depreciation of the Pakistani rupee (Anwar, Ashfaq, and Abbas, 2017).

It is quite clear from the aforementioned facts that Pakistan's economy is undergoing a lot of problems, and to encounter these issues, a thorough and robust framework is required which must be an amalgam of social, political, and economic strategies (Paracha, 2003).

Through historical events, it has been deduced that Pakistan's economy has been declining since the 1980s, but there was a little bit of improvement in the 2000s. Having said that, Pakistan has its fair share of strengths which include exceptional geographical location, a hard-working population, plenty of natural resources and human capital. These strengths can help Pakistan create value and improve the economy. On the other hand, low literacy levels, lack of capital and finance, absence of law and order, corruption, interference of tribal sardars, feudal lords, and religious mentors are drawbacks of Pakistan's economic system (Anwar, Ashfaq and Abbas, 2017).

1.1.2 Background to the Industries

1.1.2.1 Automobile Industry in Pakistan:

The automobile industry is one of the biggest and most prevalent industries in the global world economy. It is one of the largest sectors in the world's trade business which has grown to a substantial level of over US\$ 600 billion (Mirza and Manarvi, 2011). Altering the car models from time to time, enhancing fuel consumption, maximising consumer comfort level without altering quality, and cost-cutting are a few most important and inevitable challenges of the auto industry in today's fast-growing world. There is a need for continuous exploration of new ideas, collaborations, new designs, low costs and improved quality. Hence, the requirement for knowledge transfer and information exchange is imperative for the sustainability and survival of the auto industry (Khan, 2011).

In developing countries, like Pakistan, there is an absence of local growth and development, basic skill set, industrial setup, and institutional reforms. Due to the unavailability of these key factors, it is impossible to back up the attained technology (Nag, 2017).

The automotive industry contributes 4% towards Pakistan's GDP. As far as greater economies are concerned, like India, the contribution is 7.5%. In China and Germany, it is 5% (Naz and Siddiqui, 2020). It won't be fair to compare either the automotive sectors or the economies of these countries. The input from the automobile industry is extremely crucial for Pakistan due to the state of the economy.

Pakistan's Automobile Industry is one of the rapidly growing trade sectors nationally. Huge investments have been made by international automobile manufacturers in order to establish assembling plants in Pakistan. One such example is Pak Suzuki Motors (Rose and Ito, 2008). The Government of Pakistan has introduced programs like "The Auto Industry Development Programs" which promotes the trade of auto parts between global automobile manufacturers and local vendors (Mirza and Manarvi, 2011). The objective is to realise and comprehend the gains and benefits acquired by Pakistani automobile car retailers and assemblers through collaboration and technology attainment from international automobile manufacturers. Local vendors are making high revenues by manufacturing auto spare parts locally under foreign technical assistance which are cost-effective compared to the imported parts (Doner et al, 2013).

1.1.2.2 Petrochemical Industry in Pakistan:

The consumption of petroleum products in Pakistan has risen to 17.5% from 2000 to 2013. Due to industrialisation, the use of petroleum products is continuously increasing, after analysing the current situation, it can be predicted that the usage will keep on increasing in the near future (Kausar and Khan, 2018).

The present petroleum resources in Pakistan are not sufficient to meet the demand therefore Pakistan imported 136×10^6 barrels in the year 2013. In July 2016, approximately 35.57 Million barrels of Crude Oil were imported and a 3.5% growth was recorded. The country paid the US \$3.59 billion for the imported oil (Bibi, Ahmad and Rashid, 2014).

Engro Polymer and Chemicals Limited was previously known as Engro Asahi Polymer and Chemical Limited. It is one of the subsidiaries of Engro Corporation which is the leading Pakistani business conglomerate which deals in fertilizer, food,

petrochemicals, power generation, automation and terminal storage industries (Ahmad, Akram and Amin, 2017).

EPCL went public in June 2008 by offering 50 million shares and received the amount of Rs. 2.8 billion against the offered amount of Rs. 900 million. After the initial public offer, Engro's share in EPCL remained at 56% (Hussain and Safdar, 2018).

EPCL started as the only PVC manufacturer in Pakistan having a capacity of 100,000 tons per annum. Its operations are located at Port Qasim in Karachi. The plant was authorised in November 1999. In 2009, EPCL made vertical and horizontal expansion in the plant, they installed 50,000 more PVC resin facilities, along with that, facilities to manufacture Ethylene di Chloride (EDC) and Vinyl Chloride Monomer (VCM) were also installed, these two basic raw materials in PVC resin manufacturing (Ahmad, Akram and Amin, 2017). To reduce its dependency only on PVC and for the sake of diversity, EPCL also installed a Caustic Soda plant with a capacity of 105,000 tons. Currently, EPCL has the capacity to produce 150,000 tons of PVC, 240,000 tons of EDC, 216,000 tons of VCM and 105,000 tons of Caustic Soda annually (Rashid et al., 2020).

EPCL sells Caustic Soda to textile mills, leather mills, and soap and detergent manufacturers. The company is expanding its warehousing network to increase its storage capacity in order to readily cater for the demand across Pakistan. Warehouses are available in Karachi, Lahore, Multan, Faisalabad, Islamabad and Quetta (Khurshid and Chaudhry, 2010).

The international customer base is located in Sri Lanka, UAE, Bangladesh and Bahrain. Being the sole PVC manufacturer in Pakistan, the company produces high-quality PVC and also has the benefit of a good geographical location hence it has a comparative advantage (Ahmad, Akram and Amin, 2017).

1.2 Research aim and objectives

1.2.1 Research aim

The aim of this study is to investigate the significance and contribution of SMEs and microbusinesses in the value and supply chain of the Automobile and Petrochemical industry of Pakistan.

1.2.2 Research objectives

The objectives designed to be achieved by this study are focused on the processes, performance, profitability, sustainability and contribution of SMEs working in the selected industries of Pakistan.

The specific objectives designed for this study are given below:

1. To assess the supply chain levels at which SMEs enter into the value chain
2. To evaluate the sustainability of the SMEs and microbusinesses as supply chain partners
3. To identify and evaluate the profit-sharing mechanisms in the value chain
4. To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses

1.3 Research question

The research questions of the study are as follows

1. At which level could SMEs/Microbusinesses enter the value chain?
2. How sustainable are the microbusinesses' and SMEs' roles in the value chain?
3. What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?
4. Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?

1.4 Research problem

1.5 The rationale of the research

Micro and small businesses are widely recognised as driving factors for the economic growth and development of the state (Eniola and Entebang, 2015). SMEs are the source of a large number of employment in the country, thus MSMEs play a crucial

role in reducing poverty. They emphasise innovation, creating international opportunities and enhancing adaptability to ensure sustainability. The MSMEs are considered to encourage rural industrialisation thus maintaining a regional equilibrium. It also helps in the distribution of opportunities and equal chances of growth for individuals by ensuring the rightful distribution of livelihood and income throughout the state (Keizer, Dijkstra and Halman, 2002; Madrid-Guijarro, Garcia and Van Auken, 2009). Despite the role of these firms, literature on the value chain operations of Pakistani SMEs and MSMEs is almost unavailable. Nag (2017); Mirza, and Manarvi (2011); Doner et al., (2013); Khan (2011) have produced studies on Pakistani Automobile and petrochemicals industries. However, these studies do not contribute any findings related to both sectors' value and supply chains. This creates a major research gap which is the main problem targeted for evaluation in this study. Another rationale is that the automotive industry is only contributing 4% towards Pakistan's GDP which needs an improvisation (Naz and Siddiqui, 2020).

This study is intended to comprehend the supply chain processes of sectors that exhibit potential for international market penetration and their contribution towards the development of Pakistan's economy. For this purpose, two sectors have been short-listed: Pakistan's automobile industry and the petrochemical industry. Data on the website of the Karachi Stock Exchange (KSE) of Pakistan and the Export Promotion Bureau of Pakistan shows that the short-listed industries have a strong global value chain and high market penetration in international markets hence making them viable for the research. One company from the Automobile Industry and one company from the Petrochemical industry will be chosen besides SMEs to get a broader view of the role and importance of SMEs in selected sectors and their contribution towards the GDP of the country. The choice of companies from each sector depends on the percentage of their export nationally and internationally. Pak Suzuki and Engro Polymer and Chemical Limited are well-acknowledged companies in Pakistan. While analysing the data of the short-listed companies, the supply chain structure of these companies will be studied at local, national, regional and international supply chain levels.

1.6 Potential implications of the study

The micro-businesses, SMEs, and businesses with international portfolios related to the above-mentioned companies will be studied and scrutinised to determine how they affect the global value chain.

The effect on the global value chain is directly related to the outcome of the contribution towards the development of Pakistan's economy. This study will focus on value creation activities in association with selected disciplines, including knowledge management and transfer processes, technology transfer, value chain, the role of SMEs in the global value chain, and recognition of sustainability practices in the value chain of the selected industries of Pakistan. Moreover, the findings of this study are anticipated to help policymakers, industries, SMEs, and higher authorities improve existing strategies and formulate new, effective ones. The study can help in the smooth integration of value-adding activities and processes to have an active role in the global value chain.

1.7 Research setting

The researcher will get contact details including e-mail addresses from Pakistan Companies Database which is an online portal that provides information about the registered companies and businesses in Pakistan. With the help of an archival search, the Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) and the Ministry of Commerce are the two government organisations that can assist in providing information and contact details about several companies in different cities of Pakistan. Export Promotion Bureau of Pakistan and Pakistan Stock Exchange will determine the percentage of exports each company is doing and, in turn, how much percentage it is contributing towards the GDP of Pakistan.

The research will be conducted through in-depth interviews with key members of the company, such as people working at the organisation's managerial and executive levels. The researcher examines the interviewee so that he can get rich and detailed information about the topic (Qu and Domay, 2011). In-depth interviews are a useful tool for data collection which is used in qualitative studies. This data collection method is used for issue identification and strategic planning. This method allows the interviewer to study the respondent's feelings in depth and understand the

respondent's viewpoint on a certain subject. In-depth interviews are quite effective as the outcome is rich background information that can help narrow down specific information and facts for the subject (Guion et al., 2011).

1.8 Layout of the Study

The remaining four chapters of this study include the Literature Review, Research Methodology, Findings and Discussion, and the Conclusions.

Chapter 2 focuses on the review of the literature related to the topic of inquiry. This chapter is divided into a few sections, including a brief account of the global value chain, followed by Porter's value chain to enhance the theoretical and practical understanding of the processes involved in value creation processes. The literature is reviewed extensively to identify and comprehend the resources/capabilities aspects of the value chain such as a) organizational learning, b) knowledge management; c) technology transfer; d) Environmental Sustainability; and e) SCM collaboration for participating in the global value chain. The literature review entails the importance of each element in value-adding activities. The later section includes the identified gaps in existing literature, followed by the summary of the chapter.

Chapter 3 entails the methodology chosen to carry out the research. The methodology chapter briefs and rationalises the methodological choices for this study. The chapter entails the data collection and analysis techniques, approaches, and strategies. The brief introduction to the sample population, data collection tools, and ethical considerations are discussed in the last sections of Chapter 3.

Chapter 4 is designated for primary data analysis which includes a thematic analysis of the 10 interviews conducted with managers working in selected industries. The collected qualitative data was analysed repeatedly to identify patterns and themes to make micro and macro themes. The themes and subthemes are identified and presented through thematic analysis of the participants' responses. All findings are presented in the findings section and later discussed in the discussion section with support of existing literature.

Chapter 5 is designed to discuss research findings in the light of previous studies. A critical review and comparative analysis of findings were offered in the discussion. Thus, this discussion chapter identifies previous studies supporting or contradicting the findings achieved in this research.

Chapter 6 is designated for conclusions and recommendations. In the first section, the research questions and objectives are addressed. Followed by some recommendations for policymakers and implications for the industry or relevant stakeholders.

2 Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter of the thesis is devised to provide scholarly evidence based on an extensive review of the literature related to the role of SMEs and Microbusinesses, their role in value chain operations and activities, and how these organisations aid the development of the economy of Pakistan. This literature review also encompasses the theories and frameworks that help in understanding the value chain processes. The economic situation of the selected country Pakistan is also discussed briefly to familiarise readers and facilitate the comprehension of crucial aspects related to the topic of inquiry.

This chapter is divided into four main sections. The first section entails a brief introduction of the concepts related to the research questions. The section discussed the concepts of value chain and supply chain, processes, and activities involved in creating value. The section also focuses on the significance of the supply chain as a function of the value chain in economic development. Lastly, this section concludes with a brief account of Pakistan's economic conditions.

The second section of this chapter is based on the Theoretical Framework related to research questions. The underpinning theories are discussed, including Michael Porter's Value Chain Analysis (VCA), Porter's Generic Strategy, Global Value Chains (GVCs), knowledge management and transfer, theory of technology transfer and sustainability, the generalised analytical discussion on the value chain, predominantly focused on the value chain including global value chain analysis in the automobile and petrochemical industries. This section is crucially devised to identify the fundamental elements involved in the value chain, such as resources, capabilities, and processes. This value chain of both selected sectors is discussed separately to produce a well-informed context of the topic of inquiry. It includes the literature review related to the overall value creation process, including the key stakeholders or value chain partners. Considering the extensive nature of value creation activities, the function of supply chain activities is majorly assessed to narrow the focus of this research.

The third section entailed the rationale for Meta Theoretical Triangulation. Among supporting theories VCA, knowledge transfer, and technology transfer are considered

predominantly most helpful in analysing the supply chain activities that can play a significant role in value creation. Moreover, this section also comprehends the rationale for deploying multiple theories to examine the phenomenon.

The fourth section of the literature review encompasses the critical analysis and synthesis. This section will critically analyse the existing literature in association with the research questions and highlight the gap in the existing literature. The chapter ends with a summarisation of the literature review and identification of potential areas and methodologies for future research.

2.2 Value chain and underpinning concepts

A value chain encompasses the cascade of activities that happen within an organisation to deliver valuable goods or services to the market. The value is added to the service or product throughout the value chain. The value chain works as an efficient tool that gives a detailed visualisation of the performance of the firm by identifying all activities involved in the processes (Ryan et al., 2020). The conceptual attributes of the value chain denote the operational activities of an organisation that adds value to its customer's experiences. The organisations integrated value chain to create and capture the value through value chain activities. Moreover, the created value through value chain should always be more than the sum of the value created by individual activity (de Moura and Saroli, 2021).

The value chain analysis helps organisation to focus on delivering maximum value to its customers with the lowest possible cost by enhancing its production efficacy. The value chain is comprised of a diversified number of functions and processes, and supply chain is one of the most crucial aspects that is shared between the firm and suppliers to make and deliver products to the consumer (Dubey et al., 2020). It involves steps from the initial state of a product or service to the final product that is received by the consumer. It incorporates all the stakeholders, including other businesses and entities that are involved in creating the final product from raw material procurement to finished items for consumption (Cho et al., 2012).

Supply chain activities typically include refining, designing a product or service, assembly, manufacturing, packaging, and transportation. It begins with the phase of raw material delivery to the production facility and finishes at the point of delivery to

the consumer. Supply chain management is a crucial function of an organisation that covers the initial to final stage of the product (Khor and Varvarezos, 2017).

The value chain activities are segmented into five major functions, including inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales activities and service (Dubey et al., 2020). As Dubey et al. (2020) signified maximising the performance of any one step facilitates the company in attaining a competitive advantage in the industry. A lucrative value chain is a balance between the demand of the customer and the product of the organisation. Analytical and technical processes such as product testing, innovation, research and development, and marketing are focused as opportunities to add value to the products produced by organisations. The five major segments of value chain activities are as follows:

Table 2: 5 Major segments of value chain (Source: Dubey et al., 2020).

Activities	Processes
Inbound logistics	Receiving (raw material, machinery, semi-finished products), warehousing and inventory control
Operations	Value creation activities that convert inputs (raw material, designing, and production etc.) into final products.
Outbound Logistics	activities required to get a finished product to a customer
Marketing and Sales	activities linked with promotion, building customer relationships, and making a perception of buyers related to purchase of a product
Service	activities through which value can be sustained or enhanced, for instance, customer care

2.2.1 Role of supply chain and value chain in economic development of Pakistan

Existing business dynamics are becoming more complex, and there is an urge to bring adequate approaches and tactical strategies into practice. Besides countless opportunities, the globalisation of corporate environment, diminishing trade boundaries, and integration of global networking raises several threats and risks for large enterprises and SMEs. SMEs have lower power of bargaining and several other limitations that influence the success factors of SMEs and Microbusinesses.

However, the SMEs and microbusinesses are integral parts of Pakistan's economy. According to the State Bank of Pakistan (2022), SMEs are responsible for 40% of the GDP of Pakistan and 25% of manufacturing exports. Following the Agriculture sector, small and medium enterprises are known for generating employment for the highest percentage of the working population in the country. Moreover, the 78% of employment in non-agriculture sectors is generated by SMEs and MBs. In the presence of structural barriers, SME funding began to heighten in 2013 and reached PKR 524 billion in December 2021 in contrast to PKR 284 billion in December 2013 (SBP, 2022). Naveed et al. (2022) highlighted that there are over 5.2 million SMEs and Microbusinesses reported in the year 2021, making up almost 90% of the exclusive private organisations. These enterprises may contain but are not limited to manufacturing units, services, and start-ups functioning at various levels of value chain.

2.2.1.1.1 Cost Leadership

In cost leadership, the organisation focuses on lowering costs and considers the broader scope of market. However, the sources of cost advantages depend in the structure of industry and may vary. These may conclude the pursuit of economies of scale, patented technology, access to raw materials, and other factors. A low-cost producer must bargain and utilise all means of cost advantage. Once cost leadership is achieved, the producer gains an advantage over other players in the market and may command the prices considering the market average (Wanyonyi et al., 2021).

2.2.1.2 Difference between value chain and supply chain

There is often a misconception leading to the interchangeable use of both terms but it is important to understand that both concepts have fair differences. The supply chain is a vital function or subset of a complete value chain. The supply chain model was later followed by the value chain (Holweg and Helo, 2014). The activities involved in procuring raw materials and ensuring smooth and economical manufacturing operations. The value chain has a larger scope, and it focuses on various aspects that can enhance the performance of the organisation and experience of the consumer. The value chain is more concerned with processes that ultimately create and add value at various steps. The value chain involves every stakeholder adding value to the product from beginning to the last stage, eventually adding value to the end product and enhancing consumer experiences, including the disposal of the packaging after consumption of a product. However, the supply chain is merely an organised transfer of a product from one stakeholder to another (Mishra et al., 2018).

2.2.2 Role of SMEs in the Global Economy

The SMEs are well-recognised for their vitality and contribution in areas including the generation of employment opportunities, innovation, and exports. The smaller firms are known to be employment producers as they tend to be more intensive in employing labour in comparison to larger firms and also in terms of the in-house growth of SMEs. The generation of employment opportunities is in response to the start-up ventures initialising at a level of small businesses (Singh, Garg, and Deshmukh, 2010).

2.3 Theoretical framework

2.3.1 Value creation and value chain analysis

The value chain framework was proposed by Michael Porter in the year 1985. The competition to grasp the limited market necessitates the supply chain partners to focus on adding value to supply chain by value creation. The analytical framework was initially designed as a template for manufacturers which was later extended to overall operations, including the supply chain (Ilyas et al., 2007). Generally, a value chain defines the process of formation of a product and its transformation from the initial raw material stage to the last disposal of the product's packaging. It includes a variety of activities that are divided into sets of primary and supporting activities. The

predominant activities are primary activities that include inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing, sales, and services (Porter, 2001). The secondary activities consist of supporting activities, including infrastructure of the organisation, human capital management, technological infrastructure, and other activities that help achieve a desired final product or service. Every function of the enterprise should be well-structured and connected seamlessly to ensure value addition at each stage. The value added to the product or service will add value to the business and enhance its financial performance (Ricciotti, 2020).

Michael Porter defines value as the maximum amount a consumer is willing to pay to purchase a product or avoid any unfavourable concerns from a provider. Porter's Value Chain Analysis is a strategic tool that is intended to better comprehend the competitive advantage, to identify the areas to enhance value for the customer and decrease cost for an organisation, besides understanding the organisational position and relationship with the stakeholders such as suppliers (upstream), customers (downstream), and other enterprises in the industry. VCA is considered to be a frontier in building sustainable value for an organisation. Porter's model focuses on enhancing the profit margins and building a competitive advantage for the organisation regardless of the size and nature of the organisation (Strakova et al., 2021).

Figure 2: Value Chain Analysis (Source: Harvard Business School, 2023)

2.3.2 Other related models and frameworks

2.3.2.1 Porter's generic strategies

The generic strategy framework is related to value chain analysis. The Value chain analysis focuses on cost and differentiation as the two dominating aspects which are also a major part of the generic strategy model (Islami et al., 2020). Similar to VCA, Porter's generic strategy also focuses on strategies that can help enterprises gain their competitive advantage and profitability over the other players in the industry. As discussed, the generic strategies are intended to gain a sustainable competitive advantage in the target industry. An organisation should possess two competitive advantages, low cost, and differentiation, to enhance profitability and maintain it to above average. These two, combined with the scope of activities, form three generic strategies to improve and maintain performance in an industry. These three generic strategies are cost leadership, differentiation, and focus. Moreover, the focus is further categorised into two dimensions, including cost focus and differentiation focus (Li, 2023).

Figure 3: Generic competitive strategy (Source: Porter, 1985)

This model elaborated on the generic strategies to gain a competitive advantage and secure sustainable financial performance of an organisation or an industry (Wanyonyi et al., 2021).

2.3.2.1.1 Differentiation

This strategy is driven by identifying and developing a unique position in the industry. Through this strategy, a producer efficiently blends the attributes of the product

perceived as important by the consumer and positions it distinctively with the other attributes of the product. This uniqueness usually gains a reward of a premium price for the designed product (Ali and Anwar, 2021).

2.3.2.2 Global value chain

The SMEs in developing countries have increased trade opportunities in turn of recent developments in Internet communication technology (ICT) and the international fragmentation of the production of goods. The inclusive accessibility to the internet and advancements in ICT have decreased the cost and expense of communication and sharing of information. The later development has allowed SMEs to narrow their operations and excel in their performance at distinctive points throughout the production process (Epede and Wang, 2022). Digital connectivity, such as websites, IT infrastructure, and other related technological advancements, have facilitated manufacturing SMEs operating in developing countries to become a part of the global value chain (GVC). Moreover, GVCs provide SMEs with an essential opportunity for learning, especially those in developing economies. Connecting to global value chains is a bundle of opportunities for SMEs and their national economies (Epede and Wang, 2022; Pietrobelli and Rabellotti, 2011).

The global value chains are increasingly restructuring the international trade and the global economy. GVCs have a tremendous impact on the employment and the gross domestic product (GDP) of developing countries (Antras, and Chor, 2022). GVCs are changing the dynamics of current organisational structures and functions while enhancing their operations in several countries. GVC participation necessitates the organisations working with a set of interrelated activities to create evident competitive advantages. This enables SMEs to add evident value to the product offered to their customers around the globe. GVC partnership can be shaped through forward or backward linkages. Predominantly, global value chain participation depends on the strategic preferences of the organisations and economies. However, the expected outcomes of participation in GVCs differ depending on various factors (Epede and Wang, 2022). Moreover, GVC governance theory can offer important contributions in interpreting the particulars of how and why inclusion and exclusion of organisations occur at the industry level, and what are the expected outcomes. According to Ponte

and Sturgeon (2017), the GCV governance theory of linkages was proposed by Gereffi et al. (2005). Five generic ways that firms set up and govern linkages in value chains were identified in this theory: (1) simple market linkages which is usually governed by price; (2) modular linkages, the transaction-related complex information is codified, and before passing to a supplier or other stakeholder as per standards (3) relational linkages, exchange of tactical information takes place between buyers and suppliers with distinctive capabilities, governed by trust and repute; (4) captive linkages, less proficient suppliers are offered detailed guidelines by dominant buyers, governed by purchaser power; and (5) linkages within the same organisation, governed by management hierarchy. Gereffi et al. (2005) suggested that these mentioned five linkage types would be related to foreseeable combinations of three variables: the complexity of information exchanged concerning value chain tasks, the capacity of codification of that information, and the capabilities existing in the supply base proportional to the requirements of the operation (Ponte and Sturgeon, 2017).

2.3.3 Value chain development

As discussed before, the value chain development is subjected to the creation of a customer-oriented chain in order to enhance business-specific productivity and functionality. It is an integral part of the success of a company (Kaplinsky, 2004). It is significantly important to look at the different sectors with the perspective of including the potential value chain within the private sector and the public sector organisations operating within the country incorporation with the international and recognised companies in the different areas, specifically within the technological and automobile sectors (Irshad, 2015). The value chain development is subjected to the creation of a customer-oriented chain in order to enhance business-specific productivity and functionality. The different multinationals existing are involved in some of the prominent industrial and service sectors belonging to automobiles and telecommunications to enhance the value chain development (Hitt, Li, and Xu, 2016).

One of the potential challenges associated with the development of one of the substantial value chain development and technology transfer mechanisms with regards to the availability of the organisational clean the different multinational companies, as well as international, will be the availability of adequate trained

resources with a high level of competency as well as the collaborative features (Felin, Foss and Ployhart, 2015).

Certain elements contribute to the value chain like entry, systematic efficiency and governance. In the value chain, barriers to entry and rent is considered important, too as Ricardo in his theory of rent, stated that scarce resources must be utilised in the best possible manner. Another element that enables the building of the value chain is the activities that are performed by the company which is termed governance (Gereffi and Kaplinsky, 2001). The concept of governance is very broad and helps to distinguish between the different types of chains. The third element is systematic efficiency which is important because it turns the focus from point to system efficiency. Tesco, Europe's major retailer, portrays a great example of systematic efficiency when they did the strategic restructuring to gain market share and profitability only by the ability to slim down their inventory and ensure the processes were just in time.

Value Chain has become an integral part of the economy in many ways. Even the producers from low-income countries find this concept very interesting as it's about increasing the efficiency of an individual while being part of a chain. Some of the significant companies and international business entities which are significantly involved in the business development and sustainability processes of over 9 billion USD within Pakistan.

2.3.4 Value chain in the automotive industry.

Schmid and Grosche (2008) evaluated the automotive industry value chain. The value chain defines all the activities included in the business model which is utilised for the creation of products and services. The business model of automobile firms needs to be concentrated at a higher level so that they can gain efficiency in their operations. The challenge they face is that the resources they need cannot be easily available in every market. The automobile manufacturers have now eliminated their focus on exporting vehicles to foreign companies. With globalisation the World has become a small village and now firms are carrying out their activities in foreign countries to avoid the need of export.

Though the changes in the model have positively affected revenue streams, intercultural challenges have increased. There are some important factors which has

led companies to move towards International value creation (Cavusgil, Ghauri, and Akcal, 2012). Some of them are growing in emerging markets such as BRIC countries, macro-economic factors of emerging markets, and competition level. Among these countries, China and India have gained popularity due to low-cost labour availability in the market. Further, China has also gained popularity with the aid of its technological innovation and advancement. Macroeconomic factors of availability come up with parts, oil prices, sales prices and exchange rates are the main contributors. Macroeconomic factors can be political, environmental, social, technological, legal, and economic (Gouveia and Ros, 2000). These factors can adverse in the home country. This leads the firm to initiate operations internationally. Technological challenges are heavily faced by automotive industry participants which leads companies to internationalise their value chain in countries having technological advancement.

Furthermore, industry-wide needs are influential to come up with international value chains. Industry-specific requirement creates a need for companies to produce low-cost cars. This is the main reason that companies are creating internationalisation in their value chain. They search countries where procurement, RandD, production and sales can be done at lower costs in contrast with their home countries and other foreign countries. One of the needs of the automotive industry is innovation and switching towards the production of environmentally-friendly products (Alfaro et al., 2012).

The influence of the exchange rate on the internal value creation process can be evidenced by the changes in the euro and dollar exchange rate from 2006 to the mid of 2008 (Ma and McCauley, 2011). The strength of the euro led many non-American companies to start value creation in the US. The reason was that in their US vehicle export, a higher exchange rate affected their sales and a situation of loss occurred. In this instance, Volkswagen subsidiary Audi has initiated its production site in the US (Pavlínek, 2008). On the other hand, BMW has maximised their procurement with suppliers who can finalise their prices or deals at dollar prices so that currency fluctuations would not hurt negatively (Schmid and Grosche, 2008).an another decision was made by Daimler and the company initiated its subsidiary in hungry. This decision was made in an attempt to enable the production of A and B class vehicles. The strategy was mainly adopted by the companies as paying for the materials to

suppliers in Euros was affecting their profitability in a negative manner. Further, production units in Europe lead them to pay salaries in euros which can be costly as well. To avoid this cost a strategy was adopted by the company.

Several other market entry strategies were utilised. For instance, different operations of R&D production and sales are internationalised with the acquisition of a subsidiary. Some of the other types of market entry strategies are joint ventures, mergers, licensing, contract production, strategic alliance and others (Taylor, Zou and Osland, 2000). Foreign subsidiaries are used by automobile companies for the purpose of developing manufacturing and selling units. Foreign distribution companies have gained great attention as they have well-developed distribution networks. One example is Tata Motors which acquired Jaguar and Land Rover companies in 2008 (Kumar, 2008). The acquisition was made to initiate operations outside the Indian market. However, these acquisitions cannot be successful at times as several factors can affect their success, such as the level of integration between home and foreign country operations. One of the cases can be evidenced by BMW's acquisition of Rover, where the company experienced issues in quality management. Further, the integration between both companies was a huge problem. For almost 6 years, both companies have tried to resolve issues and coordinate with each other. However, issues remain persistent (Schmid and Grosche, 2008).

2.3.5 Globalisation in the automotive industry

Sturgeon et al. (2009) produced a study uncovering the effects of Globalisation on the automotive industry. The author showed that some common factors that can influence different industries, including automotive, are cross-border trading and FDI. The acceleration of these growth-related factors was initiated in the 1980s. Low-cost labour availability in different countries, such as China, has attracted firms to transfer FDI to these countries (Liu and Dicken, 2006). These FDI flows have maximised supply in local markets as well as products were exported to developed nations. These FDI patterns and changes in business agreements were initiated with the agreements of the World Trade Organisation. This has created a change in global sourcing patterns and investment liberalisation which has also encouraged trading throughout the globe.

Global value chains include different types of firms, including lead firms and suppliers (Cattaneo, Gereffi, and Staritz, 2010). Product strategy is usually devised by lead firms, where they design products and prepare a road map to the final product in terms of planning. They initiate orders and generate finance for the generation of the final product. Lead firms are involved in the designing and production of transmissions, engines, and vehicle assembly in their facilities (Pavlínek and Ženka, 2011). These firms are considered innovation generators, and they employ on a large scale. Furthermore, higher buying power and coordination make them a distinctive position. The trend prevailing in the automotive industry supports producers to have a prime position. However, the trend changed in 1990s when global suppliers added to the supply chain and their role became more extensive as they started taking a key role in designing, production, and other operations (Sturgeon, Van Biesebroeck and Gereffi, 2008). This evolution results from the outsourcing operations of these firms. Thus, the power of leading automobile producers was taken partially by 30 suppliers in the market. In other words, the global value chain has caused a shift in power as suppliers are now equally important.

The competition in the industry intensified, and this has led automobile producers to come up with an order strategy (Pil and Holweg, 2004). This strategy can support customer satisfaction as they can determine their desired characteristics before the time of vehicle production. The previously build-to-forecast approach was utilised in the market where demand is forecasted on the previous sales volume and as per demand highlighted by dealers. However, auto body style and options are now showing a rise (Meyr, 2009). These changes in customer choices and preferences show that built to order strategy can be more essential to cater to customer needs in contrast with traditional strategies. This can be evidenced by the fact that 62% of vehicles are sold in Germany on built-to-order (Holweg and Pil, 2005). This comprises the highest share across the whole market. Vehicle specifications have faced compromise due to the lead time and superficial choices of customers.

Globalisation has resulted in a change in supply chain management, and suppliers are now comprised of global and local suppliers. Previously, parts were exported by lead firms for assembly in plants (Holweg, 2008). Another method was to gain parts on the location of production operations. From these globalisation changes, the emergence

of global suppliers has benefited the large suppliers in the industry. Some of the suppliers are now adopting strategies of the lead firm to maintain strong linkages. With the increase in production and rise of customers' demands suppliers are getting winning contracts (Govindan, Kannan and Haq, 2010). With these contracts, suppliers are required to work on one or a few parts of the vehicle. These can be shifted to the nearest plant for assembling subsystems. After assembling subsystems these can be delivered to the location of the final assembly plant.

Giant firms operating in the industry place barriers to the new entry of small firms (Dean, Brown and Stango, 2000). Further, their position inhibits small firms to show upgraded performance. Moreover, they face issues in the development of new products. This aspect of the competition is more concentrated in the automotive industry. The reasoning is that new product development takes billions of dollars of investment. Furthermore, the time required will be almost 3 to 5 years, and up to 30000 engineering hours will be needed (Sturgeon et al., 2009). These concentrated requirements keep small companies lagging in the race of competition. This concentration not only affects suppliers yet also influences lead firm and their decision-making processes. The reasoning is that firms are required to be customer-specific in designing their vehicles, determining specifications and standards as well as feasible transaction costs (Lin, Chen and Nguyen, 2011). These strategies of lead firms affect the capacity of smaller firms to come up with new or unique products, and neither can they improve.

2.3.6 Globalisation in the polymer industry

Malík and Kröhnke (2006) researched the existing situation of the polymer industry and explain some of the trends which can be seen in the future. The polymer industry is facing numerous macroeconomic challenges. However, some of the factors have positively affected industrial growth. These are globalisation and the increasing demand of consumers. Furthermore, the demand for polymers increased as their properties were similar to plastic to an extent (Tingle et al., 2007). Gathering the materials required in the production of polymers is challenging, and some of these materials are stabilisers and additives. For firms to prosper in the industry, it is important to compare performance improvement targets critically. This can enable firms to revisit their performance measurement and management system.

Furthermore, existing know-how should also be upgraded (Kumar et al., 2009). Know-how can be considered as knowledge possessed by the firm which can be in terms of the technology they utilise. In this instance, knowledge can be gained for future development by investigating or studying Polymer stabilisation and degradation. Analysing the existing situation of the plastic industry can be significant in assessing upcoming trends in the polymer industry for stabilisation and activation.

With the rise in ecological awareness, regulations in different countries have changed (Olajire, 2014). These regulatory frameworks create a need for companies to work as per safety, health, and environmental concerns of society so that companies will not face legal penalties. Furthermore, changes in the additive market have the potential to create a strong influence on the growth of polymer stabilisation. The reasoning is that commoditisation has created economic pressure on companies. Innovation in the stabilisation system is also influential in driving development within the firm (Pfaendner, 2010). These can be used in terms of inflammable plastics, filled and pigmented plastics. Some of the factors that can be concentrated by polymer industry firms can be evidenced in the below figure. The figure shows that with the aid of commoditization by marketing polymer products. This is important to reduce economic pressures as a need to increase the profitability of a firm. Ecological awareness on the other hand, is important, these polymer companies should invest in environmental sustainability, and the regulatory framework prevailing in the country should be governed. These regulatory frameworks should be a part of polymer companies so that legal threats will not arise. Furthermore, the complexity level in the system should be minimised to reduce transaction costs. These can play an important role in companywide development in the near future.

Optimising Stabilisation systems and their systematic usage will affect performance. Furthermore, processing should be done as per standard procedures with the aid of statistical techniques. Some of these methods can be utilised to determine melting point, and polymer density as well as determining volume fractions (Meziani et al., 2004). For example, an analysis of polymer chain defects can be considered as an additional study to provide insights to the company regarding the areas that are having issues. Degradation principles should also be assessed by polymer producers.

2.3.7 Value chain in petrochemical industry in Pakistan

Petrochemical products, including crude oil and other chemicals, have the highest share in Pakistan's exports. As reported by Hafeez (2024), domestic oil exploration caters to approximately 20% of petroleum needs by production, whereas imported crude oil is used to produce other 35% locally. The local refineries generate 55% of the requirement which is 11 million tons, against the total demand of 20 million tons. The remaining 9 million tons of petroleum required is imported. Moreover, the refining process is considered as the beginning of producing a wide range of products and raw materials. The derivatives of crude oil are used in several other industries, such as construction, plastics, textiles, and others. The demand for petroleum is rising at a Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5% each year. The limitations in the value chain, including production and logistics, have restricted the ratio of domestic and imported petroleum generation to 55:45 (Hafeez, 2024; Ministry of Energy, 2023).

Moreover, the processing of by-products of crude oil to obtain advanced by-products is very challenging in Pakistan. The generation of derivatives of crude oil, such as naphtha and other thermoplastics and thermosetting resins, is also part of the value chain of the petrochemical industry. The bulk consumption of Polyethylene (PE) and Polypropylene (PP) are categorised as thermoplastics. The petrochemical industry processes raw materials of crude oil into high-value products used as input materials for other industries. Currently, the petrochemical industry of Pakistan is bound to the generation of Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), Polystyrene (PS), Synthetic Fibers (i.e., polyester), and Purified Terephthalic Acid (PTA), and Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) resins. However, Pakistan lacks the facilities and investments to produce basic petrochemical derivatives such as ethylene, propylene, etc. in the country (Ministry of Energy, 2023).

As stated in the report by Ministry of Energy (2023), the rising demand of petrochemicals is increasing with economic development. According to the study conducted by local refineries in collaboration with an international consultant, by the year 2035, there would be a need for two large-scale petrochemical refineries to fulfil the PP and PE demands, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 4: Forecasted Demand of Petrochemicals in Pakistan (Source: Ministry of Energy, 2023)

2.3.8 Resource-Based Theory:

The resource-based view is one of the most dominant and quoted theories. This is an organisational framework that highlights the internal resources of a firm which can help the firm achieve sustained competitive advantage. The main theme of this theory is that if a firm wants to achieve sustained competitive advantage, then it must attain and manage valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources and also should have an organisation that can understand and captivate those resources (Barney et al., 2001).

According to RBV, the firms have a goal of gaining maximum profit. These firms are operated by logical and practical managers who are functioning in a distinguished market which is predictable yet heading towards achieving stability (Bromiley and Papenhausen, 2003). RBV also explains that if a firm's managers are successful in predicting the future value of a firm's resources better than its competitors, then the firm gets a chance to secure sources of sustained competitive advantage in advance (Kraaijenbrink et al., 2009).

This theory delivers an exceptional way of evaluating the phenomenon of supply chain and studying the events that are taking place within the supply chain both individually and collectively (Williams et al., 2002). Every activity taking place in the supply chain needs specific resources and supplies to finish the task at hand, hence moving

towards creating a competitive advantage. The more challenging segment is to incorporate the existing resources within the supply chain and control them in a way which leads to creating a competitive advantage. To achieve this, supply chain partners play an important role and help organisations achieve considerable cost reductions and improved profits. Organising existing resources within the supply chain, along with controlling and projecting the combined resources, leads to stronger and more effective results. It also creates uncertainty of cause and effect. This uncertainty is difficult to copy and eventually produces greater value for the customer (Hitt et al., 2016).

Kozlenkova et al. (2013) emphasised that through the synthesis of existing literature based on marketing, the use of resource-based theory has been evaluated on the basis of multidimensional analysis. Each aspect was evaluated, and dimensions for future research were also provided to facilitate the progression of RBT in marketing. The utilisation of RBT across the various domains of marketing was considered. Generally, the resource-based theory has been predominantly applied in three dominions. These include marketing strategy, transnational marketing, and innovative marketing (Chiao et al., 2010). The theoretical and empirical insights in relatedness with several market-based resources on performance through various marketing contexts are found in the existing literature. The utilisation of resource-based theory in marketing is based on primary motivations related to its captivating framework. The framework bids for the integration of various resources that comprehend synergistic, distinction effects on performance and associated eventualities (Kozlenkova et al., 2013; Barney, Ketchen and Wright, 2011; Foss, 2011)

The attributes and utilisation of market-based resources such as relationships, brand building, and information vary from those studied in non-marketing contexts. The perspective of market-based resources emphasised that the focal point of marketing research is on resources that are intangible and complimentary. It is considered that the effects of intangible resources on the sustained competitive advantage and performance of an organisation are much greater than those of tangible resources. It is believed that seventy percent of the market value of a firm is the result of its intangible resources. The performance of an organisation is also considered highly related to its intangible resources, as in the case of custom relationships and equity of

the brand. Present studies also emphasised that the complimentary benefits are more when external market-based resources are combined with internal resources (Kozlenkova et al., 2013). Day (1994) also signified that exploiting outside-in capabilities requires a match with the inside-out capabilities. Moreover, researchers also verify the underlying resource requisition of resources as the main predictor of the performance of resource-based theory (Jaakkola et al., 2010). More precisely, the sustained competitive advantage is only produced when the means are valuable, rare, and imperfectly imitable and the VRIO of an organisation facilitates the exploitation of the potential of means. A comprehensive argument on VRIO is significant for facilitating the implication of Resource-based theory to market-based resources. In addition to this, the criteria for the organisation need a few modifications to cater to the different skills, processes, and policies. These will facilitate the exploitation of resources for exchange at the firm-level analysis. The framework of VRI is designed for the evaluation of exchange-level resources depicting the rationale behind the resources at the firm level (Alexy et al., 2018; Kozlenkova et al., 2013).

Another significant perspective highlighted by Kozlenkova et al. (2013) is the evaluation of the connectivity of resource-based theory with related theories. For instance, theories related to resource advantage, agency, and transaction cost economics. These tend to give an exclusive understanding of the reasons leading to the failure of firms and managers to exploit the true potential of market-based resources. These theories also significantly reflect the elements of VRIO's organisation. Moreover, the investigators in both domains of marketing and management debate that resource-based theory gives a consolidating model that combines assorted literature with varying perspectives. Inclined with this rationale, a resource-based theory may collate other theories in a specific framework. As emphasised by Peteraf (1993), the RBT is a unifying model that demonstrates to be an exemplar capable of expounding and assimilating research in all capacities of stratagem (Palmatier, Dant, and Grewal, 2007).

On the other hand, few researchers suggested that RBT cannot integrate or conjugate other related theories into a single framework. This is due to ground differences in the assumptions and logic of different theories. However, it is suggested that RBT can integrate various and diversified resources into an individual framework for the

evaluation of complementary or combined effects of the resources based on the market performance (Kozlenkova et al., 2013).

2.3.8.1 Resources and capabilities of the firm

The capabilities and resources are the cardinal constructs discussed in resource-based theory. Therefore, it is crucial to comprehend the conceptual variation among the constructs and differentiate them from the dynamic capacities that are considered predominantly in recent studies. Resources are referred to as tangible and intangible assets that are used by firms to design and implement strategies. Moreover, the resources refer to something an organisation can draw on to attain its objectives and goals. There are four predominant categories of resources; physical, monetary, manpower, and organisational (Ravichandran et al., 2005; Kozlenkova et al., 2013; Hesterly and Barney, 2008).

In addition to this, capabilities are detachments of firms' resources; capabilities refer to a non-transferable resource that is rooted organisationally and is specific to the firm. Capabilities are intended to enhance the productivity of an organisation's other resources. These are, in general, grounded on information and tangible or impalpable processes that empower a firm to arrange its various other resources in an effective array and augment the higher productivity of existing resources. As a consequence, capabilities are set of a special form of resources that are purposefully utilised to enhance the productivity of existing resources in possession of an organisation (Eddleston et al., 2008; Kozlenkova et al., 2013).

The concept of dynamic capabilities was introduced by Teece et al. (1997). It represents continuous production, extension, upgrade, protection, and maintained relevance of the firm's inimitable asset base in varying surroundings. They are considered a relevant element in "high-velocity" or tempestuous markets. Correspondingly to capabilities, the dynamic ones are those resources that are capable of leading the modification of other resources and helping value creation. Routines of product development, transfer processes, resource provision, and coalition along with capabilities to acquire and processes related to creating knowledge, can be considered exemplars of dynamic capabilities (Wirtz et al., 2007; Schilke, Hu and Helfat, 2018). Few investigators have argued that dynamic capabilities

necessitate their peculiar stand-alone theory. However, others have considered them as a way to extend the resource-based theory to vigorous surroundings. The view that dynamic capabilities are predominantly different is based on the notion that SCAs acquired from the utilisation of typical resources are only infrequent in dynamic markets. The prompt change superseded several resources with the fast and constant change in configurations, profits and disposal of resources of the firm. It is significant to meet the hassles of the shifting marketplaces (Teece, 2007; Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000). Essentially, the resource-based theory is capable of dealing with resources that are more valuable in a particular environment due to their short-term benefits and competencies. Such resources are more effective in high-velocity markets and are comprehensive to elaborate their influence on SCA. The dynamic capabilities are debated to be exclusively consistent with the RBT and to be considered part of it. Therefore, the dynamic is considered another form of resource that could be evaluated within the RBT framework (Teece et al., 1997; Peteraf and Barney, 2003; Kozlenkova et al., 2013).

2.3.9 Critical evaluation of resource-based theory

The prevalent static and tautological nature of the theory is subject to criticism as many other theories. However, definitions and refinements of theories are predominantly addressing the concerns (Hitt et al., 2016). Few of the critiques complain the static nature of theory is subject to its failure to either address its impact on the actions of the organisation on effective utilisation of resources over a period of time. It also discusses the effect of these resources on SCA in a dynamic market. In further response, the overview of the VRIO contrasted with VRIN framework resources has recognised that resources are subject to be effectively rendered by the firm, against only claimed by an organisation (Makadok, 2001; Peteraf and Barney, 2003). Moreover, Day (2011) signified many theorisations have enlightened that dynamic capabilities help to alleviate apprehensions related to the abilities of RBT in order to elaborate the effects of resources in turbulent environments. In the domain of marketing, it is also proposed that adaptive capabilities of marketing are known to permit organisations to anticipate market trends and events prior to their known actualisation and they later proceed with effective adaptation (Day, 2011; Mudambi and Tallman, 2010; Teece et al., 1997).

Additional reproach to RBT is its tautological or self-verifying nature of the theory. These issues make it default for empirical testing. Barney (2001) has accredited that in a case where resources are identified for sustainable strategic advantage recognised in their abilities for satisfactory production of strategic advantage (Kozlenkova et al., 2013). There are predominantly three dimensions in which researchers have addressed the reproach to RBT. Firstly, it is considered that the outcome variables should be used to solely define the resources, for instance, performance or SCA. Precious, exceptional, and defectively imitable resources could be elaborated in terms of variables that are exogenous. These are significantly discrete from the dependent variable of interest (Peteraf and Barney, 2003; Bromiley and Rau, 2016). Another way is researchers are dissociating the direct link between the resources related to VRI and consequences by defining the processes of an organisation as the source of resource exploitation (Peteraf and Barney; 2003; Barney and Clark, 2007). However, VRI resources are significant but not ample for the acquisition of SCA. The last and third ways encompass the viewpoint of the researcher related to dependent and independent variables. It is said that studies with longitudinal separation of these pose an enhanced level of confidence in the spontaneous collation of the effects. Consequently, Resource-based theory is intrinsically not redundant. However, existing research often uses resource-based theory in a manner that solidifies it empirically untestable (Kozlenkova et al., 2013).

2.3.10 Value creation through organisational learning

2.3.10.1 Knowledge Management

The limited studies regarding knowledge management in SMEs are alarming despite the significant role of SMEs in a country's economy. The earlier studies have significantly highlighted the lack of systematic management of knowledge in small and medium-sized enterprises. However, if any of the SMEs tend to implement measures in terms of knowledge management, they are not as cultured and effective as in larger enterprises. On the other hand, this does not reflect that the approaches suitable for the management of issues related to knowledge are not crucial for the success of SMEs. Preferably, the importance of effective knowledge management needs to be

emphasised as an integral factor for the sustainability of the organisation (Egbu, Hari and Renukappa, 2005; Durst and Edvardsson, 2012).

The firms operating at smaller scales are vulnerable to several constraints related to resources. Moreover, the inadequate and inconsiderate use of the existing resources has proven to raise severely adverse consequences as compared to issues raised with ineffective resource management at the larger business. For an instance, small enterprises are generally having flat structures with an adequate hierarchy to follow a free-floating style of management that rather supports entrepreneurship and novelty. These firms are under the supervision and control of the firm's owner and formal policies. Furthermore, in many small firms, the central positions are served by the owner-managers. This business environment restricts the power and authority of decision-making and planning to only the sole person. However, it is significant for those key persons to recognise the vitality of the management of knowledge in support of their operational requirements. In addition to this, the SME's routine operations for business also require vigilance and effective attention while time restraints are evident in terms of strategic planning and issues. In certain situations in combination with limited financial resources and expertise, these issues consequently result in immobility or sharing of knowledge as a result of which the knowledge remains limited to the owners and few key persons. However, the sharing of knowledge is observed only in corridors or at any informal event (Halme and Korpela, 2014; Varis and Littunen, 2010).

As emphasised by Durst and Edvardsson (2012), small and medium-sized enterprises have to go through several unparalleled challenges in terms of knowledge management in contrast to those faced by larger businesses. The review of existing literature hints that the researchers have intended to adopt approaches that were devised for larger enterprises instead of for SMEs. This act tends to disrupt the characteristics and capabilities of the smaller firms posing a greater risk to their existence. The literature highlighted the difference in approaches for knowledge management in small and larger enterprises. The smaller firms lack the precision in policies targeting strategic knowledge management while they are inclined to handle knowledge management on the level of operations, systems or devices. SMEs are seemingly required to be more inclined towards the management of implied knowledge

as compared to larger businesses. The gateway for communication in smaller firms is usually between the firms instead of serving as an intra-organisational facility. The sector pertaining to SMEs is less progressive in relatedness to the construction of knowledge while having an automatic approach to the concept of knowledge management. SMEs are known to rely lesser on societal collaborations. Correspondingly, SMEs are fragile as compared to larger enterprises in terms of the prescribed and efficient discussion to share implicit knowledge. On the other hand, larger enterprises have well-designed formal strategies to effectively manage the knowledge within and outside the organisation. Most SMEs embrace unstructured and informal ways towards organisational learning that are also for a short period. The strategic members in smaller enterprises are inclined to limit the knowledge within organisational boundaries thus freezing the mechanism of knowledge sharing (Tunc Bozbura, 2007; Hutchinson and Quintas, 2008; Durst and Edvardsson, 2012).

It is evident that activities related to knowledge management are time-consuming and may require a particular level of trust and effort (Maier and Hadrich, 2011). However, the slow rate of staff turnover is evident in SMEs and is anticipated to have a positive influence on efforts related to knowledge management and sharing. The process of identification of knowledge is based on events that facilitate to recognise of the useful set of knowledge for the organisation along with the relevant sources for the acquisition of knowledge. The process also included the identification of pre-existing knowledge. Moreover, knowledge creation is meant to concentrate on the generation of new knowledge. This process is supported in organisations by providing team members with adequate time to experiment. Despite the internal generation of knowledge, external sources are required for constructing knowledge. Considering the intrinsic limitations of SMEs, they are usually pressurised to gain benefits from external sources. The storage and retention of knowledge require processes comprised of documentation, classification and coding of knowledge in order to construct an internal knowledge base of an organisation. Effective storage or retention of knowledge will also help to reduce the loss of significant information in case of retirement, departure or any other circumstance resulting in a change in members of the organisation. This process of knowledge management sets strenuous challenges for a smaller firm as it is evident that in SMEs most of the knowledge is restricted to the minds of the founder

and some chief employees of the organisation. They tend to neglect the significance and practice of storing knowledge in a physical form or sharing it through substitution means (Sankowska, 2013; Kianto, Vanhala and Heilmann, 2016; Haesli, and Boxall, 2005). While reviewing the existing literature it is also significant to note that three areas of knowledge management are relatively well investigated in terms of SMEs, these include; knowledge management implementation, knowledge management perception and transfer (Durst and Edvardsson, 2012).

2.3.10.2 Knowledge Management in SMEs

Knowledge is recognised as one of the most crucial factors while strategising corporate operations. The knowledge has proven to enhance the competitive advantage of the companies over their counterparts. Consequently, institutions seek to adopt effective measures to manage their knowledge and skills. However, the smaller firms find it hard to cope with the needs for knowledge management predominantly due to the limited resources and accessibility. Moreover, the researchers have significantly focused on the domain of knowledge management. Nevertheless, larger corporations have been discussed predominantly in studies while small enterprises are disregarded in terms of knowledge management (Durst and Edvardsson, 2012).

2.3.11 Knowledge Transfer:

Knowledge Transfer is defined as a process by which skills, abilities, information and experiences are transformed from the knowledge hub for example, a university or a college or a research centre to those organisations or people who require it, for example, a company or a social enterprise. Therefore, the whole concept of knowledge transfer shares boundaries between universities and businesses and involves the commercialisation of abilities and experiences acquired by higher education. The intention of Knowledge Transfer is to assist innovation. Examples of KT are; university-industry contracts, open innovation and the generation of new ideas and knowledge exchange process (Koman and Kundrikova, 2016). Liyanage et al. (2009) emphasised that the transfer of knowledge is considered one of the primary components of knowledge management. The knowledge transfer can purposefully serve as a strong catalyst for striving and managing the competitive advantage while

managing the effective use of in-hand resources. Moreover, successful and optimal transfer of knowledge can also lead to the accumulation or integration of new knowledge. Knowledge transfer encompasses either active communication among people in terms of what information they have or active consultation with individuals to learn from their set of information and experiences. Hence, knowledge transfer can be used as an instrument to acquire knowledge (Van Wijk, Jansen and Lyles, 2008). Their models for knowledge transfer differ in context but are similar in terms of collaboration, sharing of information and learning through knowledge transfer (Liyanage et al., 2009). The effective transfer of knowledge has crucial factors concerning the acquisition and absorption of transferred knowledge in order to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of an organisation (Jane Zhoa and Anand, 2009).

2.3.11.1 Knowledge transfer in SMEs

Knowledge transfer is an essential component for the success of SMEs. The transfer of knowledge is not limited to the research and development department or the business terms. The knowledge transfer should be integrated throughout the management processes inclusive of personnel training and development, international experiences, global networking and innovation. It is also signified that SMEs founded by entrepreneurs with international exposure have higher levels of knowledge transfer and absorptive capabilities. They are more likely to have distant customers along with advanced innovative ideology sustainable with technological changes. Their episodic exposure will allow them to understand and apply the emerging effective management strategies to their SMEs (Filatotchev et al., 2009).

2.3.12 Technology Transfer

Technology Transfer is defined as a procedure for comprehending and envisioning a new application for a prevailing technology. The term technology has been defined by many researchers with different perspectives and many definitions have been given to this term. Thus, the word technology, according to Kumar et al (1999) includes two parts, the first part is a physical component which contains objects like commodities, tools, apparatus, supplies, blueprints, methods, and processes and the second constituent is based on information which contains information on different aspects of marketing, quality control, management, production, labour. Technology Transfer is

utilised in transforming research into economic development. Examples of Technology Transfer are; the reduction of an idea to practice in a model, and the authorisation of intellectual property to a producer for the manufacture of a product (Lane, 2010). In this concept, the word "technology" simply means ideas, conceptions, details, practices, components and products. The studies in recent times of hard and soft technology concerning technology transfer have created a direct link between technology with knowledge and more attention is being given to the field of research and development (Dunning, 1994). If we talk about technology then it means we are striving to get a specific result, trying to find a solution to a problem and accomplishing some particular tasks with the help of a skill set, knowledge and utilising assets (Lan and Young, 1996). Technology is also associated with the procedures and policies it uses to create a product. It is assumed as an organisation's intangible asset or firm-specific which creates a stepping stone for the firm's competitive advantage. The technical assets such as equipment's are considered as 'Hard Technology' while the intellectual assets such as skilled personals are referred as 'Soft Technology'. Soft technology is comprised of human resource areas such as decision making, strategic management, development planning and others (Cohen, 2004).

International technology transfer is a multi-dimensional process which involves the transfer of information and technical data. It combines several scientific and technical fields, organisations, institutions and businesses (Lema and Lema, 2012).

According to Bell, there are several ways through which technology can be transferred between suppliers and recipients:

Flow 1: investment goods, supplies and other products. This flow includes tangible assets; those which have a physical form and a potential monetary value. Tangible assets include; equipment, proposals, policies, schemes etc.

Flow 2: Capabilities and expertise for maintenance and set-up. This flow consists of intangible assets which are also termed immaterial knowledge. The capabilities and skill-set to function and manage technical systems are assumed as human and knowledge capital.

Flow 3: Technological change. This flow includes imperceptible human investments but in comparison to the second flow it includes resources of the firm, it can be called people's personified technology.

The first and second courses are helpful in supplying increased manufacturing capacity to different firms and countries but when implied alone, they add very little value towards innovation (Bell, 1990).

2.4 The Rationale for Meta Theoretical Triangulation

Triangulation is helpful in maximising the credibility and validity of research findings. Multiple theories are used in the analysis of the research aim. One of the reasons is that a single theory cannot deliver insights on the whole picture of the research goal. Different theories targeted in this research support the evaluation of research objectives designed in this research. Many of these theories are even related to each other which creates a triangulation of these concepts. Prominent theories that support the assessment of research objectives are Michael Porter's value chain, Resource-based view, Porter's generic grid, theory of technology transfer, knowledge transfer, and Global value chains theory.

Michael Porter's value chain is based on support and primary activities. The theory benefits the research by examination of elements which can create value for buyers. Both of these theories create triangulation to define the elements which can be used to create value for the achievement of different competitive strategies defined in Porter's generic grid. Thus, the findings of these theories are evident to help the evaluation of 3rd objective. Another theory supporting the assessment of this objective is Porter's generic grid strategies deliver theory regarding differentiation, cost leadership, cost focus, and other elements. The theory is selected as it entails a microscopic view of firms' strategic targets which push firms to evolve their value chains. The theory is helpful in the critical evaluation of 1st research objective targeting supply chain levels at which SMEs enter into the value chain. The theory limits the guidance regarding the direction which can be supportive in value chain creation. This is the main reason that knowledge sharing, technology transfer, and Porter's value chain model were also utilised to create meta-theoretical triangulation.

Other theories of knowledge transfer and technology transfer are also supporting this research objective. One of the theory of technology transfer produced by David Ricardo entails the difference between comparative costs of production between countries which maximise international trade among countries. With this technology and knowledge transfer, firms can improve their value chain production processes. This also plays a supportive role in enhancing sustainability in production processes. However, these technology transfer and knowledge-sharing theories provide limited insights. This is the main reason to triangulate these concepts with Global value chain theory.

Meanwhile, global value chains theory (GVCs) covers a major evaluation for objective 4 of this study. The theory refers to international production sharing as a phenomenon to break down production into different activities and tasks carried (The World Bank, 2020). The theory has surfaced concepts of cross-border production which ultimately triangulates other knowledge and technology transfer theories. This builds up some major facts about why large-scale firms collaborate with SMEs and microbusinesses. One of the limitations of this theory is that it specifically targets the globalised value chain which delimits the implication of its concepts on SMEs. However, the limitation was positively utilised in the study to address areas requiring inquiry of large-scale collaboration with SMEs.

Nevertheless, the theory cannot be utilised as a standalone option which is the main reason to target RBV theory. This is significant for creating meta-theoretical triangulation to observe the resource management of SMEs. Resource-based view theory entails that the resources of a firm are helpful in the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage. Once the firm attains and manages valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources, a unique competitive edge can be easily attained by the firm (Barney et al., 2001). The rationale behind the inclusion of this theory is that it provides insights regarding resources which practically triggers firms to enter the global value chain. Further, the concept of sustainable competitive advantage of this theory supports the evaluation of objective 2 elements targeting the sustainability of SMEs.

One of the limitations of this theory is that it entails a focus on all the types of resources like labour, capital, and others. However, this research specifically targets knowledge

sharing and technology sharing as core resources. For this reason, knowledge transfer and technology transfer theories are added in combination with RBV to create meta-theoretical triangulation.

2.4.1 Theories of Technology Transfer

2.4.1.1 International trade theory

Adam Smith (1776) stated that a country can get benefits by practising free trade policy. For example, if one country has an advantage in one particular production over some other country and vice versa then in this situation both countries gain through trading. However, he did not succeed in generating a robust theory of international trade. It has been established that the classical theory of international trade was created by David Ricardo. Several theories about comparative advantage and benefits from trade are linked to him but still many solid concepts regarding trade were in place before he stated his thoughts and concepts (Zhang, 2008).

In this theory, the fundamental factor is a technology which helps in understanding the configurations of international trade. The theory highlights that the difference between comparative costs of production between countries is the key feature for international trade to take place but this difference also highlights the different types of techniques utilised in production. In a more practical view, this theory states that the different levels of technologies implemented in countries regulate the international division of labour and its consumption and trade patterns. Hence, the theory holds that trade is advantageous to all the countries that are involved (Leamer and Levinsohn, 1995).

The Ricardian theory was unable to describe the intricacies of trade, although it can be utilised to define boundaries in which details of the trade lie. It was accepted previously that if details and terms of trade are to be determined, it is vital to construct a trade theory which focuses both on the products as well as the demand side (Sen, 2010).

The Ricardian model and Heckscher-Ohlin model are the two essential models which prove to be the pillars of international trade theory. The Heckscher-Ohlin model is a prominent model which discusses comparative advantage in economics. This theory

states that countries trade in those products which they can produce efficiently and in bulk. It highlights the fact that the trade of items or products needs those production factors that a country has in large quantities (Feenstra, 2015).

The general equilibrium theory has been extensively implied in trade theory. However, the key distinguishing feature between the two is the realisation that not every commodity and element is mobile in the same way. The difference in mobility can be considered in various forms. The assumption based on classical mobility was often considered in terms of trade theory; it states that all finished products are tradeable between the countries, unlike the intermittent products. However, intermittent products are tradeable among the various sectors of the local economy (Acemoglu, 2010; Jones and Neary, 1984; Balistreri and Rutherford, 2013; Eltis, 2000). Nevertheless, a large number of studies examined the consequential effects of departures based on these assumptions. In addition to this, Jones and Neary (1984) emphasised that an auxiliary element characterising the international trade theory is an emphasis on applied questions. This element makes it more realisable and real while analysing small-scale enterprises. This is not intended to label the trade theory to any specific sector. For instance, in the 1960s in spite of its supremacy, the Heckscher-Ohlin model never superseded the Ricardian model. Relatively, positive trade theory utilises a set of models in which each model is suited for analysis through a discrete range of questions. Despite the fact that this diverse approach is criticised, it is actualised that any model when implemented to derive any proposition is not certainly robust. This is in response to the relaxations related to the assumptions of models. However, it is a more favourable means of acquiring beneficial insights along with hypotheses suggested on the basis of empirical testing as compared to seeking to derive any generalised model that also includes all models in a special domain (Helpman and Razin, 2014; Zhu and Trefler, 2005).

2.4.1.2 Technology Transfer in SMEs

It is noticeable that the SMEs operating at the international level are capable to gain more revenue and have larger capital as compared to national firms. In such circumstances, SMEs are a better economic position with more productivity, profitability and a higher proportion of exports. The SMEs also have resilient

inclinations for the non-equity type of technology transfer for instance licensing. Moreover, SMEs originating from developed and advanced countries have a higher capacity for investments as compared to those operating in less developed countries. Moreover, the local firms in less developed countries have more of their investments clustered in a specific region or within the proximity of the country of origin in contrast to larger firms operating at a multinational level. The factors such as limitations with horizons, risk aversion and the influence of psychic distance may have a significant impression on the operational and functional capacities of the SMEs (Javalgi and Todd, 2011; Buckley, 1997).

2.4.2 CSR in SMEs

Corporate social responsibility is conventionally related to large organisations. However, the growth in recognition and importance of SMEs has correspondingly signified the contribution of SMEs towards society and their environment. Jenkins (2009) signified that the size of the organisation is the major concern for an SME, while their internal and external attributes represent their abilities and behavioural individualities. SMEs are anticipated to have a personalised management style that lacks formal structures for managerial and operational tasks. Such informal attributes and perspectives vary significantly among the SMEs while it also has a significant impact on the firm's attitude towards CSR. In SMEs control lies in the hands of the owner-manager which has its consequences. The SMEs are difficult to be regulated due to a low level of trust in bureaucracy, less responsiveness for institutions including, legal bodies, government policies and competitor benchmarking and other public interest bodies. Regardless of all such pressures, SMEs are adaptive and flexible to rapidly evolve to integrate their part in CSR through their products and services.

Small and medium enterprise contributes a significant part of investments to mitigate social issues and environmental hazards. Their CSR activities are often in response to their moral convictions rather than in the domain of any of their business activities. However, recent growth has been noticed in CSR-related activities by SMEs. CSR activities are also realised as crucial means of establishing a dominant scope for competitive advantage to SMEs. However, three elementary issues are considered to be addressed as the responsibility of SMEs in terms of CSR. These include encouraging diversity in the workplace, establishing a good vocational environment

and protecting the environment (Jenkins, 2009; Torugsa, O'Donohue and Hecker, 2012).

2.4.2.1.1 Focus strategy

It tends to target a narrow segment of the market. This strategy helps to cater to a narrow segment to serve products tailored according to the needs of the market.

The focuser selects a segment or group of segments in the industry and tailors its strategy to serve them to the exclusion of others. This strategy has two forms: cost focus and differentiation focus. First, it may lead organisation to achieve a cost advantage in its target segment, while the differentiation focus helps seek distinction in its target segment. The company is deploying a cost-focused strategy focused on low cost as compared to the market to its niche segment with enhanced customer targeting advantage. Whereas, the organisation following the differentiation focus should focus on a narrow segment of the market and position the unique product catering needs of that segment with exclusiveness (Tanwar, 2013).

2.5 Critical Analysis and Substantiation

Critical analysis of the literature reveals that theoretical frameworks available on value chain and supply chain management are supportive for firms to improve their competitive edge (Hitt, Li, and Xu, 2016; Felin, Foss, and Ployhart, 2015). These theories are Michael Porter's value chain framework based on primary and support activities. Other important related frameworks are GVCs, Porter's Generic strategies of competitive edge, and others. All these can specifically influence the operations of SMEs and microbusinesses.

On the other hand, the theory of technology transfer, knowledge transfer, resource-based view, and CSR somewhat directly influence the operations of SMEs. However, the critical evaluation of previous studies shows a lack of knowledge of the Pakistani Automobile and Petrochemical industry. Nag (2017) identified the fact that developing countries, like Pakistan, face the absence of local growth, development, and a lack of technology. On the contrary, Hafeez (2024); Ministry of Energy (2023) identified limitations in value chain within the petrochemical industry. The production and logistics were affected by the ratio of domestic and imported petroleum generation.

Moreover, Naz and Siddiqui (2020) identified the fact that the automotive industry contributes 4% in the GDP of Pakistan. Despite this low proportion, the input from the automobile industry is extremely crucial for any country as the positive contribution of automobile sector always improves the economic state of the country. In contrast, the Ministry of Energy (2023) showed that Pakistan lacks the facilities and investments that are needed in the production of basic petrochemical derivatives like ethylene, propylene, etc. This aspect ultimately defines the rationale to evaluate the selected research aim.

2.6 Identifying Research Gap

The literature gap is identifying unexplored terrain which reveals areas that fall short in the previous. These gaps will be filled in with the aid of this research using analysis done on the basis of different objectives. Thus, with the evaluation of these gaps, the investigator can reach better conclusions regarding the significance and contribution of SMEs and micro businesses in the value and supply chain of Pakistan's automobile and petrochemical industries. One of the reasons is that previous studies on the Automobile and Petrochemical industry of Pakistan are quite limited or almost non-existent.

Different studies from the automobile sector in Pakistan were contributed by Nag (2017); Mirza, and Manarvi (2011). Here, Mirza and Manarvi (2011) offer an exploration of technological advancements in the Pakistani automobile sector. These findings support the exploration of research objectives surrounding knowledge and technology transfer. However, it fails to deliver findings regarding the whole picture of the value and supply chain of the Pakistani Automobile sector. Moreover, different studies produced by Nag (2017); Doner et al., (2013); Khan (2011) have uncovered various facts related to the automobile sector. The majority of the literature delivered in previous automobile sector studies only covers technology transfer, knowledge, and trading practices. Therefore, all these studies fail to deliver a complete picture of the value and supply chain of the Pakistani Automobile sector.

Khurshid and Chaudary (2010); Ahmad, Akram and Amin (2017) have produced facts affecting the production in petrochemicals industry of Pakistan. The study was produced on Engro Chemicals and does not create any strong insights regarding value

chain of these petrochemical firms. This literature gap is the main reason to target the evaluation of value chain of the petrochemical industry. Some other studies that have contributed similar literature gaps are Ahmad, Akram, and Amin (2017); Hussain and Safdar (2018); Ahmad, Akram, and Amin (2017). On the other hand, Zafar and Mustafa (2017) have produced findings regarding the contribution of SMEs and their role in Pakistan's economic development. In contrast, some other studies have only touched on this topic somewhere in the literature. Therefore, the literature gap identified in previous studies will be covered in the analysis of this research. The critical evaluation of this literature gap will enrich the existing current literature on the significance and contribution of SMEs and micro businesses in Pakistan.

2.7 Chapter Summary

The literature provides insight into value chain underpinnings and concepts. Here, the role of supply chain and value chain were discussed to shed light on the differences of these concepts. Meanwhile, the theoretical framework reveals different value chain theories of GVCs, Michael Porter's value chain framework, Porter's generic strategies of competitive edge, theory of technology transfer, knowledge transfer, resource-based view, and CSR. Here, a critical review of these theories was done to explore the limitations and benefits of each of these theories. The literature digs into the role of these theories in the value chain management of these sectors. All these theories are significant in shedding light on the value chain operations of the automobile and petrochemical sectors. The rationale defined for the selection of multiple theories shows that none of the single theories can define the whole picture of the research aim selected in this study. A critical analysis of the whole literature is performed in the chapter, along with the identification of the literature gap which needs to be filled in using the analysis of this research.

3 Chapter 3: Introduction to methodology

The chapter provides a brief insight into the methodology of this research. The chapter showcases methods portrayed in previous studies, and justifications for the selected research methodology were provided. Research paradigms and available philosophies are discussed along with the justification portrayed for using the philosophy of realism. In the light of previous studies, inductive and deductive approaches were critically evaluated, along with justifications for the selection of these approaches. One of the sections also uncovers available research strategies, and interviews were selected for the evaluation of this research aim. The chapter shows that the qualitative data collection method is selected against the quantitative method, and the justifications were offered to produce an in-depth evaluation of research aim. Discussion of sampling technique shows the justification for selecting the convenience sampling method. Sample size, research instrument, and data analysis methods were also critically evaluated in the chapter to offer justifications for the selected method.

The methodology is planned to comprehensively elaborate the processes utilised by the researcher to construct the sequent and well-structured steps to be followed across the study. These steps were considered significant to find the precise results and findings of the research in a systematic, understandable, and justified manner (Basias and Pollalis, 2018). The methodology is defined by leveraging the well-recognised approach Saunders "Research Onion." This approach is beneficial to describe and justify the choices and decisions made by the researcher regarding the philosophy, choice of methodology, strategy, collection of data, and analysis. These steps are crucial in terms of designing a strong and robust study design (Mayer, 2015).

Figure 5: Saunders Research onion (Saunders et al., 2019).

3.1 Research Paradigm and Philosophy

The paradigm of the research is the initialisation phase of planning research. It initiates the research pathway and helps make choices for other elements involved in the research process. Paradigm is classified into two predominant areas: ontology and epistemology (Katina, 2022). The former form of paradigm, ontology, deals with the assumptions made by the researcher regarding the quality of reality. The later form of paradigm, epistemology; deals with the assumptions of “*what*” should be deliberated as satisfactory knowledge in various fields of study and “*how*” it can be achieved (Slevitch, 2011).

The research philosophy is signified as the guiding point of the process of the study, and it is denoted by the outermost layer of the research onion (Håkansson, 2013). As Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019) highlighted, the research philosophy “*relates to the development of knowledge and the nature of that knowledge.*” It helps the researcher to build the foundation of choices for research. It provides rational support to the process of decision-making for the selection of a particular method for the study (Kenny and Fourie, 2015). There are various forms of philosophical stances, including positivism, realism, interpretivism, and pragmatism (Goldkuhl, 2012).

3.1.1 Selected philosophy

For this study, realism is deployed as the most suitable philosophical stance for conducting qualitative research. This philosophy follows an epistemological stance and emphasises that objects occur independently of our understanding of their reality (Killam, 2013). Realism philosophy anticipates considering the identity or existence of the phenomenon. It does not allow any theory to influence the nature of the existence or reality of the subject. In addition to this, the realist philosophy is considered to go well with the qualitative research method, and it is considered a “*position of choice*” by various researchers. It also suggests that organisations are objective entities. (Holden and Lynch, 2004).

3.1.2 Justification for using realism philosophy

The realist philosophy was used by the investigator to explore the significant realities associated with the operational and functional roles of value chain addition. Moreover, the philosophy is helpful in exploring its implication in SMEs for adding value to the economic structure of Pakistan. This philosophical stance has helped the qualitative exploration of the subject by examining the structures and functions of the supply chain of SMEs. It has helped the researcher to realise the means by which SMEs/Microbusinesses can enter the value chain, the sustainability of the role of the microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain, and the sharing of financial profits by the value chain participants. It will help explore the existing performance of SMEs and micro-businesses at different stages of supply chain management. Moreover, the objectives behind the collaboration of large corporations with SMEs will also be analysed inductively to generate a generalised theoretical understanding of the subject of study. Similarly, Adamides, Papachristos, and Pomonis (2012) have deployed a form of realism to gain an understanding of the dynamics of the supply chain of seasonal goods.

Interpretivism philosophy following the epistemological paradigm is not considered appropriate for this study. Interpretivism philosophy emphasises researchers implement a “*semantic approach*”. It works with a notion to ascertain a concept's intrinsic, obligatory, and crucial aspects (Goertz and Mahoney, 2012). This philosophy helps interpret the collected data and comprehend the logical aspects while

considering the human factor associated with it (Thorne, Stephens, and Truant, 2016). Furthermore, it is argued that the findings of the study following the interpretivism philosophy are more inclined towards the human perspective. Whereas, in this study, the researcher urges to explore the reality underlying the operational and functional aspects of supply chain management. Moreover, value chain processes are explored which facilitates the sustainability of SMEs, their financial and non-financial performances, besides the intentions of large corporates to merge to decrease their expenses and maintain their quality standards.

The positivism philosophy is not considered for this study as it is considered more appropriate for quantitative research. Positivism focuses on the independence of the existence of the subject regardless of the investigator's assumptions. It requires hypothesis building and adopts scientific testing besides the deductive approach (Park, Konge, and Artino, 2020). Pragmatism philosophy is also not considered a well-suited research philosophy as it allows the investigator to freely select any one or more philosophies while collecting and analysing the data. This philosophy is appropriate for mixed-method research (Subedi, 2016). Therefore, considering the aspects mentioned above of all philosophies, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism were not regarded as relevant to the current study. The realism philosophy is regarded as the best-suited form of philosophical stance considering the objectives of the research (Benoist, 2021). Realism has helped the researcher to determine the objective reality and its existence. Realism was used to generate more concrete information related to the value chain management of the selected manufacturing industries while avoiding any subjective influence and assumptions during the process (Ormston et al., 2014).

3.2 Research Approaches

The approach used for building the research methodology depends on the aims of the study, adoptions, restrictions, and personal views. Saunders' Research Onion denotes two types of research approaches: inductive and deductive. The deductive approach uses theories to form an understanding of the subject of the study (Pandey, 2019). Hall et al. (2023) also showed that the deductive approach means reasoning from particular to general ones. The deductive approach is significant to different relationships to obtain more on general circumstances. The inductive approach is considered to work as opposed to the deductive approach. The inductive research

utilises the grounded theory based on literature and pieces of evidence to gather data for the topic in alignment with the problem of research, purpose, and questions. The collected primary data is later analytically comprehended to support or modify the theoretical background related to the topic of inquiry (Saunders et al., 2018). Moreover, it is said that the inductive approach is a process based on logic that mostly begins with a set of specific observations and leads to general conclusions related to the research problem.

3.2.1 Selection and justification of selected approaches

In this study, deductive and inductive reasoning were used following the collection and analysis of the qualitative data. Firstly, deductive reasoning is deployed for building evidence-based literature and the theoretical background of the research. The theoretical background is extensively used to devise the interview questionnaire with the support of published secondary data. The research intends to follow a deductive approach to forming a foundation for specific observations through analysing and reviewing the secondary data (Mayring, 2014; Rahi, 2017). Documentation analysis of previous studies was conducted to identify if findings obtained from interview responses support previous studies' findings. It facilitated the effective development of the instrument used for data collection. Through the deductive approach, the objectives and questions of the study were designed to focus on the evidence-based literature of previous studies related to value addition in the supply chain management of SMEs. The interview questions were formulated to cover the required areas related to the research question and the study's objectives. The data collected was analysed and assessed in the discussion section concerning concepts and theories signified in the existing literature related to the topic of inquiry. Furthermore, theories and evidence-based knowledge were also used during the interview process. The questions were elaborated with the support of existing literature to ensure better comprehension of the research interview questions. This has helped the investigator attain as much relevant and useful information as possible from the respondents.

More meaningfully, the inductive approach is considered to analyse and collect the primary data. The inductive approach helped gather the required data set through an open-ended questionnaire and analyse the text-based, non-numeric data. The data collected is analysed thematically to form more comprehensive knowledge and

support or improve the theoretical context related to the research topic (Schlagwein and Hu, 2017). The combined approach of using deductive and inductive reasoning in the same research has facilitated gaining sound and logical insights related to the level SMEs/Microbusinesses can enter the value chain, sustainability of role of the microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain, sharing of financial profits by the value chains participant. It has helped to analyse and assess the performance of SMEs and micro-businesses at different stages of supply chain management. The willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses will also be analysed inductively to generate a generalised theoretical understanding of the subject of study.

3.3 Research strategy

Saunders' research onion has a strategy as its third layer. It denotes the strategic view of a researcher for collecting data for the research. It is argued that the development of theory and the realisation of occurrences can be attained by utilising different types of research strategies (Johannesson et al., 2021). These are focus groups, interviews, case studies, observations, and others. These are broadly used strategies in social sciences (Johnston, 2014). Interviews are used in this study to evaluate research aim regarding supply chain of SMEs and micro-businesses.

3.3.1 Selection of research strategy

For this study, the researcher deployed an interview-questionnaire strategy with a combined deductive and inductive reasoning approach (Weller et al., 2018). This is one of the qualitative research methods utilised in the collection of primary data. Interviews help researchers get in-depth discussions with one or more people to critically evaluate their opinions, perspectives, and experiences regarding the subject matter (Osborne and Grant-Smith, 2021). Different types of interviews include structured, unstructured, and semi-structured ones (Karatsareas, 2022). Structured interviews were utilised in this study as a questionnaire was designed beforehand as per targeted research objectives and questions. Semi-structured and unstructured interviews often deviate researchers from their research objectives or aims (Chauhan, 2022). With the use of structured interview questionnaire, the researcher can effectively compare and contrast different opinions of respondents to answer research objectives and questions in a detailed and individualised manner. This research

strategy is reliable to explore a wide range of research disciplines in the social sciences. The research approach of documentation analysis of secondary research was applied to critically compare and contrast the findings of interviews with previous studies (Jain, 2021). This interview research strategy investigates different questions like who, what, when, where, why, and how things are related to a particular phenomenon (Saunders et al., 2019; Crowe et al., 2011). Thus, the research strategy of an interview questionnaire is combined with documentation analysis.

Moreover, Kunkel et al. (2022) produced a study on Industry 4.0 in sustainable supply chain collaboration, and interviews were conducted with international buying firms and suppliers in the electronics industry. This qualitative technique helped the in-depth examination of digitalisation in the electronics supply chain and how it affects sustainability in supply chain collaboration (SCC). The author showed that opportunities, risks, and obstacles associated with SCC were examined using this strategy which was impossible using any other strategy (Kunkel et al., 2022).

3.3.2 Justification for using Interviews

The study's objectives focused on developing an understanding of the particular processes and aspects of the selected industries. Interviews have helped to perform an in-depth examination of the structures and seek thorough information related to the functions of the supply chain of SMEs. Interviews have answered all the questions related to SMEs. It can be helpful to explore how things go in SMEs. This has enabled the identification of factors which SMEs/Microbusinesses can enter the electronics industry. The questionnaire can be used to evaluate how they can achieve sustainability through the value chain and the processes involved in the value chain participants' sharing of financial profits. Exploring how large corporations work with SMEs and microbusinesses to raise quality standards and decrease costs is helpful.

Other strategies that were not considered suitable for this study include survey, experiment, action research, grounded theory, ethnography, case study and archival research (Saha, 2022). The experiment strategy usually involves a theoretical hypothesis and the selection of samples of individuals from known populations. It requires the examination of causal links among the study's variables (Saunders et al., 2019). The survey strategy can be incorporated into the quantitative case study and

is more helpful in collecting data from a larger population (Grassini and Laumann, 2020). The ethnographic research strategy deploys the inductive approach and aims to describe the societal characteristics of the subjects. Moreover, action research cannot be embraced as it necessitates continuous engagement and immediate actions to resolve problems (Elg et al., 2020). Narrative inquiry is not found appropriate for this study as it is a form of story-telling during which participant briefs about their events and experiences chronologically.

Moreover, Mangla, Kumar and Barua (2015) conducted a case study for analysing the risk associated with the green supply chain using a particular approach, fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (fuzzy AHP). It is a qualitative and quantitative analysis technique that is used to analyse the recognised risks helps in defining their priority of concern. The Fuzzy AHP approach is correspondingly beneficial in dealing with the subjectivity and ambiguity related to individuals called for the analysing the risk (Mangla, Kumar and Barua (2015). However, time limitations is a main concern to avoid the selection of this strategy.

3.4 Research Method

Several types of research have conformed to the qualitative research method (Qu and Dumay, 2011; Morgan and Drury, 2003). McCusker and Gunaydin (2015) signified that the qualitative study method is described in terms of the aims of the study. It is related to the comprehension of a few aspects of social sciences. Its data analysis is based on words and themes rather than numbers, as in the quantitative method.

3.4.1 Selection of qualitative method and justification

Qualitative data was collected to observe the role implementation and role of the theories and practices in SMEs. It is projected to provide a deep understanding of the research question and aims to facilitate the integration of human factors in terms of their feelings, perspectives, behaviour, and attitudes. The qualitative method was anticipated to help examine the structures and functions of the value chain of the target industry. It comprehends how SMEs/Microbusinesses enter the value chain, achieve sustainability, and share financial profits with the value chain participants. Qualitative data collection and analysis are anticipated to help understand the existing

performance of SMEs and micro-businesses at different stages of supply chain management.

The quantitative method was not considered suitable for this study, as it advocates the development of hypothesis and statistical testing of collected numeric data. Quantitative data is a raw form of numeric data analysed in various mathematical and statistical manners (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). The analysis ranges from producing simple tables or diagrams denoting the occurrence frequency to using simple statistics, for example, indices, to enable comparisons (Bettany-Saltikov and Whittaker, 2014). It can be an analysis that identifies and concludes the findings through complex statistical modeling. However, the numeric data lacks the factors and comprehensiveness in terms of perceptions, human behaviours, and insights related to the topic of inquiry (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015).

On the contrary, the qualitative is considered most suitable for this study as it is known to facilitate gaining insight and in-depth information related to theoretical and human perspectives related to the phenomenon. The qualitative study method is preferred when the objectives of the study demand a larger scope in time, the flexibility of research, and better exploration of the topic of inquiry (Queirós, Faria, and Almeida, 2017). Richey et al. (2016) have highlighted the significance of qualitative interviews while deploying the method in their research to explore the utilisation and limitation of big data in supply chain management. Moreover, the qualitative method was also used by Glas and Kleemann (2016) deployed a qualitative method of study to analyse the effect of Industry 4.0 on procurement along with supply management.

3.5 Data Collection and analysis

3.5.1 Sampling technique

The sampling techniques are deployed to obtain the data that imitates the characteristics of a larger population. Sampling techniques facilitate acquiring higher overall accuracy and manageable data for the study. There are majorly two major forms of sampling techniques: probability and non-probability sampling. The case study strategy is frequently coupled with non-probability sampling (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019). The convenience sampling method of non-probability sampling is used in this research.

3.5.1.1 Justification for selecting the Convenience sampling method

One of the justification is that previous studies conducted on similar topics were guided by this sampling method. The study is designed to explore the current LE practices of the automotive and petrochemical industry in Pakistan (Jeong et al., 2019). For sampling the target population, it was difficult to identify the relevant candidates for the study. The target population for the sample was comparatively smaller because the study focused on employees working at the organisation's managerial level. Considering these limitations and little difference in the selected population, convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, has been considered the most appropriate for this study (Jeong et al., 2019; Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

Convenience sampling uses respondents who are "convenient" to the researcher (Andrade, 2021). No specific pattern is used to acquire respondents. You can easily recruit them from a public building, from a workplace, and others. This convenience helps the researcher to enable timely completion of the research. Thus, the advantage of using this sampling method is that it is cheap, efficient, and simple to implement (Emerson, 2021).

On the other hand, the Probability sampling method is all about selecting a sample from a population (Berndt, 2020). This selection can be based on the principle of randomization or random selection. This makes it more complex, costly, and time-consuming than non-probability sampling. However, the disadvantage of this sampling method is that the sample lacks clear generalizability (Emerson, 2021; Andrade, 2021). This forms up a limitation of this research which can be covered in future research studies.

3.5.2 Sample size and participants

As signified by Sim et al. (2018), the rule of thumb for selecting the sample size in qualitative research. It is grounded on methodological concerns and past understanding with comparable research. Bernard (2013) recommended that 10 to 20 well-informed individuals are sufficient to reveal and comprehend the essential categories in any precise social domain. Therefore, for the interest of this investigation, the sample size considered for selecting the target population is a total number of 20.

All 20 participants were contacted through email intended to invite them for research participation. These participants were affiliated with the automotive and petrochemical industries in Pakistan. The scheme for sample and participation in this study was finalised based on access to the sample, geographical proximity, willingness to participate, and availability of candidates at a certain time (Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim, 2016).

3.5.2.1 Justification for the selected sample size and participants

The sample of this study is comprised of a total of 10 participants for an in-depth interview. Another reason behind the selection of this sample size is that a larger sample size can affect the timely delivery of research, and handling of data can be challenging. The research scope is quite deep, and data collection from a larger sample might create challenges in the coding and thematic analysis of the research. Thus, a larger sample would have caused numerous obstacles in processing and analyzing data. White, Blok, and Calhoun (2022) have also supported these facts and showed that numerous obstacles can arise when dealing with large sample data.

The study included two managers from Pak Suzuki Pvt. Ltd. and two managers from Engro Petrochemical Ltd as participants. Moreover, further 6 interviewees were managers affiliated with MSMEs in Pakistan from both industries, i.e., petrochemical and automotive. Participants from different companies were added to gather varying responses. This diverse sample will play a vital role in producing evidence regarding variations in the value chain operations of different types of firms or industries targeted in the study (Renert, Russell-Mayhew, and Arthur, 2013). Diverse participants or groups always improve data analysis quality with more logical and sound research findings (Khubchandani et al., 2016). These groups of participants uncover more understanding related to research objectives and aim.

3.5.3 Research Instrument

The study uses qualitative analysis, and the interview guide is designed to gather primary data from research participants. Open-ended questions were designed to gather in-depth responses from participants (Weller et al., 2018). Close-ended questionnaires can be less productive to deliver depth in participant's responses which can create issues in evaluating research objectives and aims (Roulston, 2011). These

questionnaires are designed with close-ended response scale i.e., Likert 5-point, and other type of scales are used in these questionnaire which can limit depth in responses (Roulston, 2011). This is the reason to target open-ended questions in the interview questionnaire of this study. The structured questionnaire collects data from respondents with some standardised questions (Phellas, Bloch, and Seale, 2011). These were asked in a specific way in an organised sequence. These interview questionnaires can be evidenced by Appendix 2 with all the participants' responses. An interview guide is also provided in Appendix 1.

3.5.3.1 Interview guide

The interview guide is designed to help conduct in-depth interviews with the participants of this research. The interview questionnaire is divided into sections to gather the respondents' demographical and research-related qualitative data. The open-ended questions were asked to allow participants to provide supplementary data, including their feelings, experiences, attitudes, and understanding (DeJonckheere and Vaughn, 2019). Compared to other qualitative techniques, open-ended questions are found to be more effective (Roberts et al., 2014). Holland and Christian (2009) affirmed their ability to produce robust textual material to assist qualitative analysis.

The inductive interview guide was comprised of four sections. The first section revolves around the demographics and background of the interviewee. This section focuses on gaining information related to the professional and academic portfolio. The research tool is attached as Appendix 1. Questions encompass aspects like gender, education, job position, current organisation, skillsets, the experience of the interviewee in the current organisation, functions of the concerned department, and products (See Appendix 1). Section two of the interview guide was devised to cater to the research questions related to the level they think SMEs/Micro businesses can enter the value chain and the sustainability of their roles in the value chain. This section encompasses the questions about SMEs/Micro businesses' transit into a value chain, triggering factors involved in the recognition and globalisation of the value chain, needs of business, changes in the value chain, and its impact on the performance of an organisation. This section tends to evaluate the existing perceptions of individuals

related to the level or stage when they think SMEs/Micro businesses can or should enter the value chain. It further inquires about triggering and globalisation factors, needs of SMEs/Micro businesses to add value to their operations, integration of value chain, required changes, and impact on the performance of the firm. This section also focused on sustainability and inquired about practices, their positive and negative impact. The section also portrays the potential for the survival of SMEs/micro businesses in the existing market and the role of sustainability.

The third section of the interview guide was grounded on research questions pertaining to processes involved in profit sharing with the participants of the value chain and gaining insights into the utilisation and benefits of the value chain at various levels of a supply chain in SMEs/Micro businesses operating in Pakistan. The interview questions focused on the benefits to participants of contributing to the value chain, knowledge sharing and technological advancements, their implementation of technology to monitor performance and the advantages of software integration. Moreover, this section also asked interviewees about the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses and how they differ from those in large enterprises. Respondents were also asked about the benefits of the supply chain, means of knowledge transfer, and documentation. The fourth and last section of the interview concentrated on gaining in-depth knowledge related to the readiness of large organisations to team up with SMEs to increase quality standards and cost-effectiveness. The respondents were asked about their perspectives related to collaborations with larger organisations and their impact on the quality and cost of the product. They were also asked if their organisation has teamed up with large firms and, if so, what were the reasons and impact of organisational performance. Moreover, the predetermined targets and their progress, barriers, initiatives taken by large companies to minimise those barriers, and effects of the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs on the economic development of Pakistan were the central points aimed in section four of the research instrument.

3.5.4 Data analysis method

The method of data analysis is grounded in the method of the research and its paradigm. The strategy and instrument also steer the selection of appropriate methods for the analysis of the research data. There are two major methods for analysing the

data, i.e., quantitative data analysis and qualitative data analysis (Rahi, 2017). This research has implemented a qualitative design that is grounded on the examination of open-ended questions. For this purpose, quantitative analytical techniques were excluded from considerable choices for the analysis of collected data. The data collected from the in-depth interviews were analysed through thematic analysis. It is a method for identification, analysis, and interpretation of “*patterns of meaning*” considered as themes contained by collected qualitative data (Clarke, Braun, and Hayfield, 2015). As elaborated by Lawless and Chen (2019), the thematic analysis was performed by analysing the responses and categorising them into themes based on common or similar words and phrases. The common phrases and expressions of participants were a group and identified as life experiences and perceptions of the employees. The summarisation of diversified content was also executed to gather the responses appropriately for analysis. Themes were grouped to form micro and macro themes (Köhler et al., 2019).

3.5.4.1 Data analysis process in research

For this research, the interview responses of 10 participants were qualitatively analysed using Microsoft Excel. The responses were coded based on inductive coding techniques. An open coding process of Vivo is used to add participants’ exact words or phrases. This plays a significant role in coding their exact experiences and perspectives obtained in interviews (Arije, Oyedun, and Omisile, 2021). This can be evidenced by the data analysis chapter which reveals exact phrases from participants. The justification behind the use of Vivo coding is to avoid any personal biases in the interpretation of responses. The second step was axial coding which involved identifying patterns to organise concepts and find relations among the codes, leading to micro and macro themes. Axial coding is utilised to break data into discrete parts so that connections between different codes can be identified (Gorra and Kornilaki, 2010). This has helped the development of patterns for themes formed in this research to identify a relationship between codes.

Figure 6: Data Analysis (Self-created)

This is due to the fact that the theoretical framework was used to arrange and determine the Vivo coding scheme for the analysis of the research data. Moreover, the type of research instrument used for the collection of primary data, measuring tools, and forms of analysis are also suggested by the inductive approach (Morse and Mitcham, 2002).

There are various techniques for analysing the qualitative data which are not considered appropriate for this study including analytic induction, grounded theory, discourse analysis, and narrative analysis. As signified by Floersch et al. (2010), grounded theory is similar to thematic analysis on the basis of the Vivo coding and process of constructing themes from the collected set of data. However, Grounded Theory supports the simultaneous collection and analysis of the research data (Charmaz and Thornberg, 2021). Moreover, the analytical induction starts with a notion or inarticulate explanation of the topic of inquiry that is later explored with the help of repeated investigation of carefully chosen circumstances (Katz, 2015). The last analytical technique is that of Narrative analysis which is determined to follow a storytelling format while referring to a group of methods for understanding texts or

visual data to form a story (Smith, 2016). Considering the above attributes of each qualitative analytical technique, thematic analysis is found most appropriate for drawing constructive and effective conclusions. The method is justified as interview responses were also deployed by Sodhi and Tang (2018) to discover and explore the social sustainability of corporate supply chains. Moreover, Chen et al. (2021) examined the processes, advantages, and challenges in the implementation of technological advancements in the supply chain of blockchain.

3.5.4.1.1 Formation of Themes

The responses to the interviews were transcribed to comprehensively analyse the collected data. The open coding process of Vivo Coding was deployed using an inductive coding technique the researcher intends to capture the exact words or phrases of the participants. The axial coding followed the open coding of the research data which refines the data by identification of patterns and the relationships among the various codes. The identified patterns and associations are gathered and analysed for micro and later, macro themes. Through Vivo coding the exact words or phrases of respondents are used in themes to interpret exact experiences and perspectives. Furthermore, theme formation can be seen in Appendix 3 which reveals all the 14 themes designed from the responses of participants. The first three themes of SMEs' entrance into the value chain, factors, and impact of changes in the value chain were contributed by the findings of four questions of section 2. A brief discussion of theme formation is offered in the analysis chapter.

3.5.5 Management of Biases in Data analysis

QDA (2023) showed that two types of researcher biases can negatively influence the interpretation of research findings and data analysis process. These are selection bias and reflexivity bias. Selection bias is eradicated by transparently documenting participants' selection and avoiding any personal preferences regarding religion, gender, or other elements in the selection of participants (Bell-Martin and Marston Jr, 2021). In this research, diversity is adopted in participant selection to avoid biases. This diversity was adopted in the selection of participants from different firms and industries. Reflexivity bias as personal beliefs, and conceptions can negatively affect analysis (Berger, 2015). The researcher has avoided continually self-reflecting their

impact on the study's outcomes. Though these are very hard to avoid, the researcher has avoided answering any research question that he/she thinks might be a correct answer. Furthermore, the Vivo coding analysis used in the study was also influential in avoiding any personal biases in data analysis.

3.5.6 Reliability and Validity

Evaluating the reliability of the qualitative study enables investigators to gauge the 'firmness' of the study relative to the use and relevance of the approaches adopted, along with the integrity of the results and findings (Noble and Smith, 2015). Validity refers to the veracity and precision in which the outcomes precisely mirror the collected information, while reliability refers to steadiness within the engaged methodical procedures. However, these terms are argued in the context of qualitative analysis (Bengtsson, 2016; Cypress, 2017). The credibility of a qualitative study is intended to assure the "trustworthiness" of the study. The validity is termed as a truth value, reliability of qualitative research is termed as consistency and neutrality. While, generalisation is the applicability of the finding to any other circumstances, groupings, and backgrounds (Sarma, 2015; Noble and Smith, 2015).

3.6 Ethical consideration

The predominant considerations for the ethical governance of the study play a crucial role in retaining the veracity, robustness, and applicability of the research. The major considerations encompass the values of honesty, anonymity, confidentiality, and autonomy of the individuals involved in the process of study. These were ensured by signed and filled consent forms from the participants (Connelly, 2014). The confidentiality and anonymity were sustained by regulating the privacy of details of participants used during correspondence and data collection. Integrity was essentially maintained throughout the process of investigation (Giordano et al., 2007). Acknowledgment of contributions from another researcher's work is another critical aspect of ethical considerations. It guarantees the originality of the research and facilitates due credit to the author's research work (Cunningham, Goh, and Koh, 2020). The numeric coded identifiers were used while analysing the context of each respondent appropriately to ensure the privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity of the participants. The data gathered from the in-depth interviews were strictly processed

for the purpose of research only. The storage and accessibility of data were kept limited to the researcher. The data was not stored for longer than the required period of time (Ross et al., 2018; Mathy et al., 2003).

3.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter entails the methodological procedures designed for the study. The research onion is peeled layer by layer to construct a systematic and organised sequential format for the study. The selected philosophy of study is Realism. The study followed both deductive and inductive approaches for gathering and analysing data through a qualitative data collection method. The method of research to explore the question of the research is qualitative. The cross-sectional study used in-depth interviews to collect qualitative data for the study. Convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, was advocated for participant sampling, and a rule of thumb for sample size was deployed. The open-ended structured interview questionnaire was devised to obtain resourceful data from the participants. The reliability and validity of the research were also discussed before the technique for data analysis. Thematic analysis was used to analyse and fetch the useful perspectives and experiences of participants related to the research question. The ethical considerations ensured for the study were necessarily discussed. The data shared by informants is protected, and the research originality, besides other ethical considerations were preserved throughout the research.

4 Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion

4.1 A brief introduction to the chapter and its sections

This chapter is comprised of 3 major sections. Section one represents the demographical characteristics of the participants including their qualifications, designation, job responsibilities, effective skills of participants, level of experience, role in an organisation, age group, function in organisation, and major product of the industry. The demographics are also represented in various tabulated and graphical forms such as pie charts, tables, and graphs.

Section two represents the qualitative data analysis and its findings. The themes and sub-themes are formulated by examination of collected data, identifying significant patterns prevailing in participant's responses. Based on the attitude or impact of the responses, each response is critically examined and graded as positive, neutral or negative. The responses of the participants were also tabulated (See Appendix 2) to help identify emerging and sub-emerging themes on the basis of identified patterns and also significantly represent the unpredicted responses. The unpredicted responses are those that either do not align well with the question of the interview or the response received is not considered a representative or anticipated response based on the theoretical and empirical knowledge of the topic of inquiry. Section two predominantly represents the findings and analysis of the data gathered during the interview process. This section will demonstrate the significant responses and their relatability with the theoretical and empirical background of the respective concerns. This section elaborates the responses based on identified themes and emerging themes through thematic analysis.

Section three is the last section of this chapter, conclusively discussing the themes, emerging themes, and their responses in light of evidence-based literature from scholarly journals and peer-reviewed articles. This section will focus predominantly on similarities, conflicts, and parallel issues present or signified in responses with the help of secondary data available concerning the relevant theme and its responses.

Sections one, two, and three combine to form chapter 4 of this dissertation by using the deductive approach. The excerpts of responses of research participants are included in Appendix 2.

4.2 Section 1: Participant’s demographics

4.2.1 Name of present employer or organisation

The employees working in managerial capacities in the automobile and petrochemical industries in Pakistan were recruited as interview participants for this study.

Figure 7: Name of present employer or organisation (Self-created).

Among 10 participants, 2 out of 10 were from Pak Suzuki Motor Company Limited. 2 out of 10 were from Engro Polymer & Chemicals Ltd. While 4 out of 10 participants were from SMEs, 3 from Loads Limited and 1 from Plastochem Corporation and 2 from microbusinesses, both from Sunplastic.

Table 3: Participants from different organisational scales (Self-created).

<u>Participants from different organisational scales</u>		
Participants from Large scale firms	4	2 from Engro Polymer & Chemicals Ltd. 2 from Pak Suzuki Motor Company Limited

Participants from SMEs	4	3 from Loads Limited. 1 from Plastochem Corporation
Participant from Microbusiness	2	2 from Sunplastic

4.2.2 Job designation

The selected individuals were working at diversified managerial levels in their respective organisations. Out of 10, 6 were in a manager position in their respective departments, including production, sales, operations, and project management, while 4 of the participants were serving as assistant managers in their organisation.

Table 4: Current designation of each participant (Self-created).

<u>Designation</u>	<u>No. of Participants</u>
Production Manager	2
Area Sales Manager	2
Manager Project Planning and Contracts	2
Assistant Manager - Procurement Supply Chain	2
Assistant Manager Production	1
Assistant Manager Operations	1

4.2.3 Highest level of education

8 out of 10 participants have acquired a postgraduate (Master) degree, while two out of ten participants have completed their graduation (bachelor's) in their relevant field.

Figure 8: Highest level of education of Participants (Self-created).

4.2.4 Job Responsibilities

The responsibilities of the job vary from designation to organisation. The job description of one of the participants (Participant 1) includes sales of PVC in Sindh and Baluchistan. They bid in the open market and negotiate with global traders to meet the annual sales target. Participant 2 notified that he has to ensure maintenance and adjustment of dyes/assembly lines according to product specifications or model changes. Participant 3 has responsibilities related to the production and management of inventory, fulfilling customer demands, ensuring delivery time, and ensuring smooth processes. Moreover, participant 4 established that his responsibilities encompass project planning. It also involves the utilisation of all sorts of project management tools. His job requires his services from the beginning of the validity phase, maintaining feasibility reports, execution and monitoring of bidding stage and contracts besides managing the company’s development projects such as expansion plans. Participant 5 has a diverse set of responsibilities in terms of his operational role. It includes designing and coordinating with the SAP consultation team, implementing SAP, dealing with procurement and cost management, and managing cost breakups effectively. However, participant 6 belongs to

an SME that also includes a varying set of responsibilities, including managing production and assembly lines, monitoring the supply of material, ensure reduction in downtime along with internal Audit and documentation. Participant 6 also manages a team of individuals, including labour staff. Participants 7 and 8 are responsible for meeting sales targets in their allocated areas, while Participant 9 assists his manager in dealing with procurement, labour and ensuring effective production activities. Participant 10 supervises and assists trading and supplier activities.

4.2.5 Effective skills of participants

The table below precisely represents the skills of each participant working in selected industries. These skills are perceived as helpful by participants in managing their responsibilities and performing better in their job roles.

Table 5: Skills of each participant (Self-created)

Participant	Skills
Participant 1	SPSS, SAP, MS office
Participant 2	Ms office and SAP
Participant 3	Managerial skills to manage a team. Maintaining supply and production during raw material scarcity such as COVID-19 supply chain disruptions
Participant 4	Project planning and software scheduling Firmware, it's understanding and expertise Engineering knowledge Creating proposal documents, analysing bids, handling stakeholders and Contractors. It also involves the capability to utilise all sorts of

	project management tools and an understanding of the validity phase.
Participant 5	Effective practices and skills involved to manage the costing and procurement of material expertise in MS. Excel
Participant 6	Technical and managerial skills
Participant 7	Creating proposal documents, analysing bids, handling stakeholders and Contractors
Participant 8	SPSS, meeting sales targets, finalising quotations, meeting with clients, establishing business relationships
Participant 9	Managerial skills to manage a team. Maintaining supply and production during raw material procurement and finalising quotations
Participant 10	Project management, supervising procurement, trading and operational activities

4.2.6 Level of experience

According to data collected during the interview, out of 10, there are 7 participants who are working in the current organisation for more than five years now, and 3 participants have an experience of more than one year but less than five years. The figure below represents the data analysis for participants with years of experience in their current organisation.

Figure 9: Experience in the current organisation (Self-created).

4.2.7 Role in organisation

The role of the participants shows the scope of activities and responsibilities in their current organisation. Among 10 participants, 6 candidates are working in an operational capacity, and 4 have blended roles comprised of strategic and operational activities. The figure below represents the no. of participants besides their role in the organisation.

4.2.8 Age group

The age group of the participants was defined as 25 years or less, 25-35 years, 35-40 years, and 40 years to more. Among 10 participants, 7 fall under the group of 25 to 35 years of age, and 3 out of 10 participants are between 35 and 40 years of age.

Table 6: Age Groups of Participants (Self-created)

Age group	No. of participants
25 years or less	-n/a
25-35 years	7

35-40 years	3
40 years to more	-n/a

4.2.9 Function in organisation

The predominant function in the organisation of most of the participants is found operations. Three participants are reported to work in the marketing domain, while 7 participants have a major function of operations while handling various other associated functions such as procurement, production, management, supply chain, and finance.

4.2.10 Major product of the industry

Out of 10 participants, 5 participants belong to the Petrochemical industry, 5 participants belong to the automobile industry. Among 5 of automobile industry, 3 were engaged with an organisation producing OEM and Spare parts. While 1 out of 5 from petrochemical industry are associated with distribution and wholesale of PVC and petrochemicals, and two produces garment hangers for the local and international industry. The pie chart below represents the major product of each selected organisation.

Figure 10: Major produce of selected organisations and division (Self-created).

4.3 Section 2: Finding and analysis

4.3.1 Formation of themes

Themes emerged from the responses of participants and questions designed in the questionnaire. The first question (1st objective) addresses what level SMEs/microbusinesses could enter the value chain. This question is addressed from themes 1, 2, and 3. These themes are responding to queries regarding SMEs' and Microbusiness entrance into the value chain, factor and needs of organisations leading to change in their value chain, as well as impact of changes in the value chain on organisational performance. All these themes emerged from responses to interviews from the first four questions of section two. Altogether, these themes are supportive to respond to the first research question.

The second question (2nd objective) aims to discover the role of sustainability of microbusinesses and SMEs' in the value chain. The response of the said research question forms themes 4, 5, and 6, where the 4th theme portrays sustainable practices in Microbusinesses and SMEs. 5th theme highlights the benefits of SMEs as value chain

partners, and 6th theme represents knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners. Thus, these themes dig into the value chain of SMEs along with the sustainability of micro-businesses. These themes emerged from the last 4 questions of section two and the first two questions of section 3. The formation of these themes can be evidenced in Appendix 3. An example table of theme formation is provided in the below section portraying initial 4 thematic analysis of 2 respondents.

The third question (3rd objective) explores the benefits offered to the supply chain partners, especially financial benefits. This research question's responses formed theme 7 to 10 in the study. These themes are specifically related to the supply chain. They are discovering the use of technology in value chain management, the role of ERP in supply chain management, levels of supply chain, and knowledge transfer among value chain partners. These themes include questions 3 to 8 of section three which are utilised to critically evaluate this research question.

The fourth and last question (4th objective) explores why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses. The response pertaining to the said research question leads to formation themes (11 to 14) of the study formed from all the questions of section 4. These themes create insights into collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and micro-businesses, as well as the benefits and barriers of these collaborations. Lastly, it addresses the role of SMEs and micro-businesses in the economy of Pakistan in theme 14.

Table 7: Example of Theme Formation (Self-created).

	<u>Theme 1</u>	<u>Theme 2</u>	<u>Theme 3</u>	<u>Theme 4</u>
Macro themes	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	Factor and needs of organisations leading to change in their value chain	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs
Respondent 1	"SMEs enter the value chain during the need	"They look for business and expansion providing organisations	"The demand for one of the leading products PVC was more than it	"There are no sustainable practices. microbusinesses and

	<p>for operational activities, maintenance and transportation of products. Occasionally for procurement of material. At Engro, SMEs and Microbusinesses come after dealers”.</p>	<p>with low-cost advantages and better service. Specialised services with a low-cost advantage Meeting each KPI and continuous monitoring is an important part of adding any partner to Engro outsource transportation. Factors include the Low cost of material Scarcity or no other supplier In Engro, SMEs are customers because SMEs work on credit”.</p>	<p>was produced initially. The import has its issues besides disruptions. The company hold command as the leading producer and supplier of PVC but to meet market demand effectively additional facility was established this led to a loss of command power but equilibrium was maintained Besides these, its value of Financial involvement Quality is preferred over cost Exchange of defective goods lead to loyal customers”</p>	<p>SMEs are only adding cost advantage to the value chain. They are not interested in sustainable practices as they require investment, they have issues with affordability and so few Practices are not aligned with the concept of sustainability. SMEs can challenge the existence of larger enterprises in the market if they start considering sustainable practices”.</p>
Respondent 2	<p>“SMEs enter the value chain at the production stage or planning/production of start a new model. All significant strategic steps and processes are approved or endorsed by</p>	<p>“Importing CKD and assembling Cost – US Dollars At the time option left is to reduce profit margins Price fluctuations To produce any part locally all standards should be conformed feasibility specifications material quality</p>	<p>“Value Chain Operations SAPs into the equation More vendors bring in more SMEs to facilitate you to do the job. Boost organisational performance besides install new machinery to facilitate the new model reliant on a few of the partners that we were working with who were</p>	<p>“Adaptability to change is important a shift towards electronic vehicles and hybrid style. Change and evolution bring out a positive impact and an ability to match up with the speed of the industry. If Pak Suzuki had a vendor who could have helped develop those parts in Pakistan,</p>

	<p>SMC Japan Suzuki Motor Company Japan Assembling of all parts Minimizing import of CKD”.</p>	<p>inspection department same standards quality gates are passed then we send that particular part to SMC Japan. If local lacks tools but have the expertise, the company help them identify the required tools come into the agreement with them to help them out, facilitate them to you know, actually it's like a win- win situation”.</p>	<p>outside Pakistan. good technological advancement already working with organisation performance cost the local company doing the same job at lesser costs in the same amount of time with no load, no logistic problems”.</p>	<p>we could have survived in the sedan sector with the automotive industry import everything raises the cost mid-sized sedan the parts localised keep the price of the car or the cost of the car”.</p>
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4.3.2 Thematic analysis

4.3.2.1 SMEs' entrance into the value chain

Small- and medium-sized enterprises are considered a vital part of the supply chain and value chain of the industry. SMEs play strategic, operational, and functional roles in the value chain, facilitating smooth processes and operations of the larger firms and industries. The respondents were asked to share their perspectives regarding the stage or need of SMEs to enter the value chain in their industry. Most of the responses signified the importance and pivotal role of SMEs in aiding their operational and functional activities. Participants 2, 7, 8, and 9 indicated the inclusion of SMEs in the planning and production stage. Respondent 2 is associated with the automobile industry and categorically mentioned the entrance of SMEs in the value chain of the automobile industry as,

“SMEs enter the value chain at the production stage or planning/production of start a new model.”

Participant 2 further signified that SMEs have played a prominent role in producing and manufacturing the parts of automobiles that minimised the import of CKD from the international market. The local manufacturing and production of parts and assembling of automobiles served as cost-effective alternatives without making any compromise on the quality of the product. Moreover, the parent company Suzuki Motor Company Japan takes all significant strategic steps and processes followed after approval and endorsement from SMC Japan. Participant 3 also highlighted the collaborative role of SMEs and micro businesses at the earlier stages of production and manufacturing in the garment industry. The SMEs help larger firms to gain cost advantage and ensure compliance with quality and time of delivery to the end customer.

As he mentioned, *“we can work collaboratively together to make sure that the end customer gets their product in time.”*

Participant 4 also added to the above premise that SMEs enter the value chain according to the needs of large firms. The firms may require various services or products including raw materials to finished products or transportation or marketing or any process to help them manage their functions and operations. The SMEs and micro businesses become part of the integral value chain either in terms of their services, material, supply chain services or their product. Similar to contributions of Participant 9, Participant 4 also implied that SMEs can be integrated with the value chain in form of small contractors for civil works or minor mechanical works.

Moreover, Participant 4 quoted,

“They enter the value chain when large organisations require services or materials or supply chain services, products or materials that they require for their projects or for the people they work.”

Participant 5 also endorsed the entrance of SMEs as an integral part of its value chain. It is mentioned by the respondent that the larger organisations do not have a large capacity and capability to produce a large number of parts, products and services such as raw materials, intermediate products and other processes including transportation and warehouse services. Participant 5 emphasised that

“Any multinational cannot produce such quantity itself, so we have to localise our parts to different vendors.”

Moreover, participant 5 also reasoned the need for SMEs for larger firms because of the limited capacity and cost advantages for the firms as a result of localised production of a larger number of parts with the same quality attributes. Respondent 6 highlighted that their SME was entered into the value chain when the larger firm requires product changes and locally produced parts such as radiators. When demand was placed the product was designed by engineers to add value to their product line while analysing the value stream of the automobile industry as an original equipment maker (OEM).

However, one of the respondents mentioned the limitation in the role of SMEs in the value chain of his industry. The entrance and role of the SME in his relevant industry were limited to transportation and operational activities. He further added,

“They are part of our indirect value chain, but not our direct value chain.”

Additionally, Participant 1, who works as a Sales Manager in a selected Petrochemical organisation considered SMEs as part of a value chain that comes after the dealers as secondary customers for their products. Participant 1, and Participant 8 mentioned that his organisation occasionally tends to procure material or products from SMEs. Factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations.

Participants 7 and 8 also highlighted the vital role played by SMEs during the distribution phases besides procurement and production. Participant 9 highlighted the potential role of SMEs in processes like raw material procurement (supplier), production, research, and development. Moreover, Participant 10 acknowledged,

“SMEs can be a part of the value chain at any stage from planning to customer”

4.3.2.1.1 Factor and needs of organisations leading to change in their value chain

The respondents were inquired to share their perspectives related to the factors and requirements of the larger firms to integrate changes in their value chain. Among all collected and analysed responses, low cost of material and cost-effectiveness are predominating factors for managing changes in the value chain. The conformity to international standards by locally produced parts or products has better cost advantages over internationally imported products and goods. International trade is subject to fluctuation in exchange rates and requires a considerable time for shipment and delivery to the organisation. By managing changes in their value chain the firms can save time and minimise the delivery terms. The payment methods and cost are more certain than those of imported products.

Almost all interviewees, including participants, had acknowledged cost-effectiveness as the predominant reason for collaboration between large firms and SMEs. Participant 1 highlighted the low cost of materials was one of the leading elements that motivated firms to adopt changes in their value chain mechanisms. Moreover, the availability of materials, products or services is also considered while making any significant changes in procurement or supply chain mechanisms. The required expertise and skills with cost benefits are also one of the factors driving change in the value chain of the larger firms. Respondent mentioned the issues of availability and the limited number of suppliers as major factors impacting the changes in the value chain. Moreover, participant 1 mentioned that the need for integration of SMEs and changes in the value chain usually originates after the supply of products to the dealers in his relevant industry and SMEs are considered secondary customers for their business products.

Participant 2 also shared the high cost of importing all parts from international markets. Despite parts being acquired from SMC located elsewhere, the accumulated cost of import is always higher than local production. Reliance on several SMEs and

microbusinesses for various services and products is better than depending on one source for all needs. He stated,

“When we (large organisation) improve or enhance our value chain, that means bringing in more vendors, bringing in more SMEs to facilitate us to do the job.”

Participant 3 also emphasised in cost and quality of products and services as a major factor that positioned them as SMEs in the value chain of the large garment industry. He mentioned,

“The things that we bring to the business is primarily the quality.”

Participant 4 significantly defined the needs of larger firms as the key to the entrance of SMEs, changes in the value chain, and making changes to the existing mechanism.

“SMEs enter the value chain when large organisations require services or materials or supply chain services, products or materials for their projects or for the people they work.”

Respondent also emphasised the need for an organisation to use services such as the requisite for storage facilities or warehouses, transportation, or direct procurement of material or products are also a few of the factors that crucially alter the value chain of the organisation. The respondent also stated that,

“We have small jobs that we need to do, and we hire small contractors for civil works and minor mechanical works for minor electrical works. I think that is the point that we start contacting local vendors.”

Similarly, participant 5 highlighted cost as a predominant factor for adapting to new value chain mechanisms or integration of SMEs as value partners. He further suggested that continuous increases in cost and prices have led the changes in the value chain. Other factors include technical knowledge, material, processes, inventory planning, process optimisation, and management layout design and processes along with inventory facilities. He further notified the factors that may lead to changes in the firm value chain as,

“Maybe a design process improvement and manpower management and five S activities.”

Participant 6 notified that being a part of an SME, cost-effectiveness, quality, and time of delivery are elements that keep them integrated with the value chain of larger firms. He further mentions that larger organisations gain a beneficial competitive advantage and sustainability in their value chain by creating an alliance with SMEs.

4.3.2.2 Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance

The larger firms plan and execute changes in their value chain with the intention of enhancing their current and prospective financial and non-financial organisational performances. The changes are executed and implemented with the help of effective monitoring systems to ensure the desired performance and optimisation of processes. Cumulatively, it is observed from qualitative data collected by participants that the stock availability of parts or products, accessibility, or localised manufactured products or parts are a few of several reasons that initiate large firms to take SMEs on board for managing their supply chain and associated processes effectively.

Participant 1 adhered that organisations gain advantages in cost, quality, and availability of their product by ensuring a positive impact on organisational performance. The customers admit the efficient services and products of Engro Petrochemical because it prefer quality more than cost advantage. They provide advantages to their client by ensuring the exchange of defective goods.

Participant 2 works in the automobile industry, having sound experience supporting the positive stance of changes deployed by large enterprises to help sustain their business. The respondent emphasised that the changes in the value chain have increased the production and capability of the organisation to meet the demands of the market effectively. The import of Complete Knock-Down (CKD) has decreased profit margins due to differences in exchange rates and changes in the international market, resulting in

fluctuation of rates. Consequentially, the changes integrated to facilitate local production of automobile parts with conformity to international standards have beneficially decreased the fluctuation in rates, increased the profit margin, and controlled delivery time. Conclusively, the changes in the value chain, including liaison with SMEs and insurance of sustainable practices, enhanced the financial and overall performance of the organisation.

Participant 4 profoundly expressed that changes in the value chain positively impact organisational performance. He expressed his opinion by stating,

“The organisation went in a way where everything was centralised to improve the efficiency of the overall value chain and for operations.”

Participant 7 highlighted the logistical capabilities of SMEs and the needs of large firms as major factors necessitating the entry of SMEs as value chain partners. Furthermore, the feasibility of time is also one of the crucial added advantages. Participant 7 substantiated the role of SMEs by saying,

“The collaboration with local SMEs helps in managing business in short time without compromising on cost.”

Participants 8 and 9 also voted for time efficiency and cost advantages by enlightening the significant difference in taxes, duties, regulatory issues, and conversion rates. The larger organisations are in a better controlling position when they deal with local organisations.

Participant 10 signified the role of SMEs as an effective part of the value chain and defined flexibility and spontaneous nature as predominant features of SMEs. As mentioned by participant 10,

“SMEs, despite all setbacks are more flexible and spontaneous as compared to larger organisations. The time efficiency and finances are few of the important factors.”

4.3.2.2.1 Sustainable Practices in Microbusiness and SMEs

The entry, requisition, and usefulness of microbusinesses and SMEs as a part of the value chain are reflected in responses elaborated on the entrance of SMEs into the value chain. The respondents were further enquired to share their views about the impact of changes made to ensure sustainable practices while taking SMEs on board for any process or localisation of any element required by the larger firms. All 10 interviewees signified environmental sustainability as predominant concern for their sustainable practices throughout the industry.

Participant 3 significantly highlighted in his response that sustainable practices and technological advancement have helped the organisation to reduce wastage and improved the quality of the material. He further reiterated that sustainable practices can help exporters gain international contracts. Despite problems with natural gas or diesel generation, the firm is managing to meet the needs of the market. The other options for power generation such as solar systems are costly and may not be sufficient to provide the required amount of power to meet the organisational needs effectively. There are further issues that are crucially highlighted by a respondent to adhere to global initiatives and policies for sustainable practices such as minimising carbon footprints, levels of CO₂ emission and significant minimisation of these levels. Moreover, he made a point that

“We have to invest in ways where we can reduce the cost by going sustainable.”

However, respondent 3 also shared that sustainable practices do challenge their performance when there is a demand from a client to avoid conventional power in such cases there is a challenge for the organisation as sustainable energy-generating options are not cost-effective or feasible in this country due to several reasons. He said,

“The survival is pretty much based on meeting those demands within the cost that they are willing to pay. It does have a big effect on how we operate, especially on orders.”

The attitude of response to the questions related to sustainable practices was considered negative for Participant 1. In his opinion, sustainable practices are beneficial but are not affordable or feasible for SMEs for various reasons. He further emphasised that SMEs have limitations and an attitude to gain benefits while minimising the cost. However, he

highlighted that SMEs can challenge the existence of larger enterprises in the market if they start considering sustainable practices.

Participant 2 considered sustainable practices as the most important area of concern to ensure positive financial and non-financial growth. The respondent stated,

“It is the most important because if you are running on the same old practices, you won’t be able to penetrate the path because the market is changing quite rapidly.”

Participant 4 notified that stability is important after the stabilisation of routine and operational activities, the performance of the organisation also starts improving. Various factors are challenging or supporting the sustainability of the firm, such as fluctuating and unexpectedly increasing freight charges, exchange rates, and other limitations. The contractors and workers as manpower are an essential part of the value chain as key role players in managing a broad variety of projects. Further, he added,

“I think if we were not able to sustain those businesses, and those businesses are unable to catch a break, the overall operations of all larger businesses will be affected.”

Participant 5 stated that COVID-19 has changed the supply chain mechanisms in various ways. However, the company has established contracts with SMEs to ensure proper production and availability of the product. With the help of outsourced warehouses, the organisation managed to store imported inventory for approximately two to three months. Moreover, PSMC also seeks collaboration with other companies to initiate air shipments to facilitate smooth production lines at every cost. The SMEs and micro businesses are part of the organisation's planning and launching projects. He stated that,

“The survival of a firm in the market, it may be a very small vendor or big vendor is very important in running the line efficiently.”

Participant 6 also contributed importance of sustainability and the role of SMEs in the value chain by mentioning a few advantages besides, he emphasised that the changes or issues in sustainability will eventually affect other firms working in the industry. He stated.

“We have our upstream suppliers as well. They do supply material we are depending on them as well.”

Participant 9 emphasised waste management as a major part of SMEs practices to ensure sustainability. Moreover, participant 10 signified that SMEs play an effective role despite limited scope and constraints. The respondent also mentioned,

“SMEs are inclined towards environmental wellbeing and take measures to safeguard environment and responsible consumption of resources.”

4.3.2.2.2 Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners

The SMEs are partnered as value chains with the larger organisations for the support and opportunities they provide to them. There are several benefits highlighted and discussed by the participants of the research. The responses collected are analysed to find that the benefits gained by a collaboration of SMEs or micro businesses into the value chain are mutual to some extent while having larger financial and operational benefits for larger firms. The majority of respondents acknowledged that as value chain partners, SMEs can gain visibility, and a successful partnership is considered a ground-breaking achievement if recognised by larger enterprises.

4.3.2.2.2.1 Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners

Participant 1 responded that Engro Petrochemicals has 3PL (third-party logistics) system. The company takes outsourced partners on board to provide them with transportation, warehouse facility, and labour. The organisation has ensured to provide SMEs with affiliations, technical assistance, and knowledge related to their needs, and the organisation itself gained the financial numbers from outsourcing tasks and operations. He stated that,

“The affiliated SMEs are provided with WPPF that is workers participation, profit fund or the pension fund or something similar. It is sort of a bonus if they meet all the KPIs. A small bonus is paid out to all the contracted labour of our warehouse contractors.”

Participant 2 highlighted the trickle-down effect on the finances and performance of an organisation in response to the addition of SMEs or micro-businesses in their value chains. Moreover, participant 3 shared his opinion that the time of delivery and quality are effectively managed by outsourcing SMEs' services and facilities. The collaboration helps minimise the risk and delays for large organisations while aiding the financial benefits for both parties, SMEs and larger organisations. He shared his opinion by stating,

“Apart from money, it's the streamlining of the process that works for everyone's benefit.”

Participant 4 shared that business is stable for longer periods of time. SMEs get blanket purchase orders that are set at particular prices or rates for specific services they are said to provide to larger organisations. The bidding details and contracts are signed for a duration of time, supporting a consistent business for the SMEs. The collaborations on a contractual basis provide a definite revenue for their specific service, thus minimising the odds of fluctuating market trends. Moreover, this improves service time and billing along with supply chain, operational and functional processes, customer compliance, and other key areas. He further emphasised that,

“The most important benefit for SMEs is they get stable business for longer periods.”

When Participant 5 inquired about benefits including profit sharing with SMEs, responses collected emphasised cost advantage and accessibility of parts or products as predominant benefits. Participant 5 signified,

“Making an SME or a value chain partner with that we have some long-term business relationship with the SME which is a benefit in the form that we are not going to do business with other vendors to design the part from scratch.”

He further stated that they ask small businesses to produce that part of their required specification at a high production level. Furthermore, these parts are compatible with the other models they produce. The procurement and processing of parts are fastened by adding a value chain partner or SME. However, there are areas of concern, such as SMEs

having inadequate or incompetent knowledge related to basic business and banking, periodic check and balance systems, and little information related to customs duties or SROs. Collaboration with SMEs provides them with information and knowledge that helps them to reduce cost duties on raw materials and plan effective procurement systems.

Participant 6 provided a beneficial outlook from the perspective of an SME. He mentioned several financial and non-financial benefits the larger firms can offer through partnering with SMEs as the value chain partner. These benefits include but are not limited to enhancement in production processes and techniques, product differentiation, and value addition to the SMEs' portfolio. The monetary benefits acquired by SMEs in return for affiliation are predominant among all benefits related to profit or knowledge sharing. The organisation has collaborated internationally with a company in Kenya which is considered a milestone for small businesses. The machinery was imported from Kenya, and technical support was provided with this collaboration, helping SMEs make cheaper and higher-quality radiators. He signified,

“We are getting a lot of benefits by collaborating with international organisations, such as cost saving.”

Participants 7 and 8 showed similar responses. They elaborated that knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners are limited. Participant 9 showed that collaborative events and training and development programs are knowledge-sharing and profit-sharing tactics that create numerous opportunities for SMEs. He stated,

“Collaborative events, training and development and opportunity for SMEs to surpass other local competitors in market.”

Participant 10 showed that the benefits of knowledge sharing for SMEs could be in terms of financial ones and experiential learning. He said,

“Microbusinesses- Financial benefits and experiential learning. Large enterprises- cost effectiveness, compliance, and local businesses have better regulatory and market indulgence.”

Therefore, the benefits of knowledge sharing are financial, non-financial, experiential learning, production processes, product differentiation, and value addition.

4.3.2.3 Use of technology in value chain management

Technological advancement is considered one of the important elements for planning, executing, and monitoring effective operational and functional activities of the organisation. The recruited participants from large organisations have supported the use of technology in different processes. Various software and dashboards are used in industries, including those supporting the technical drawings and programming of the machines and equipment. The analysis of collected responses highlighted the use of Microsoft Excel, Enterprise resource planning (ERP) software including SAP (Systems, Applications & Products in Data Processing), and other computing and invoicing dashboards.

Participant 1 notified that these ERP dashboards and MS. Excel has served as effective means of dealing with SMEs, reconciling and updating ledger balances, procurement history, technical literature, visuals, and graphical representation of the performance of value chain and sales tax invoices. Participant 2 and Participant 5 belong to the same organisation, so they have similarly signified the use of technology as a helpful tool in stimulating smooth and effective processes. The PSMC was using its in-house PRP system but is now migrating to SAP. Participant 2 said,

“It is going to help us monitor performance in a better way. It is anticipated to help in reporting, and analysing where we are and how far we have come.”

While participant 5 notified,

“Currently, we are doing it on Excel, like if any vendor is coming and delivering things and their ranking is done on Excel, but now we are in the phase of SAP implementation, and future all the things will be done on SAP.”

Participants 3 and 6 are from SMEs, and they expressed their concerns about the lack of technological advancement in their firms and issues with handling data, documentation

of processes, and financial aspects. Participant 6 stated they have partial access and use of SAP, but due to limited access and rights, they are mostly working manually. He said, *“There is no specific kind of technology we are using. We are just looking after all these operations manually.”*

Participant 4 responded that in Engro, the ERP is used to control and monitor all organisational operations and evaluate performance. It helps them access required information without any delays and reach the correct information immediately. He said, *“We use an ERP software (enterprise risk management software), such as SAP, and we use SAP for all our functions, mainly supply chain. We also use it for financial analysis and project management.”*

Participant 7 showed that technological tools other than communication tools are limited in their organisation. Similar responses were interpreted by Participant 8. Participant 9 elaborated that they use technology for communication, inventory, invoicing, etc., except for these basic technologies, cloud computing use is quite low. Participant 10 showed that,

“Digital technological advancements, including cloud computing, are integrated at very low scale and should be expanded further to create more opportunities for efficient handling of the value chain.”

Thus, responses interpret the use of communication tools, SAP ERP, and Excel for different operational processes.

4.3.2.3.1 Role of ERP in supply chain management

Participant 1 highlighted that the use of ERP in the value chain had provided the organisation with a single platform with centralised management of processes and operations such as procurement and demand forms. The added features of artificial intelligence are good for forecasting future needs, demands and budgeting. The centralised system has also facilitated the management of transportation services by

considering different scenarios and providing situational analysis. He further testified its benefits for value chain partners by saying,

“Partners get all the information at the click of a button through access to portals so it's very good for them as well.”

Participant 2 highlighted that SAP has changed the ways of doing business and documentation. He focused on the benefits of using software, including monitoring and adhering to KPIs of the value chain system of the organisation, performance, and information management, and documentation related to transactions, day-to-day work, processes, activities, and production. It also helps manage and control the capital nature of assets, procuring raw materials, etc. Participant 5 further added that apart from material controlling SAP helps in finance controlling and HR management processes as well. He said,

“HR will also use SAP for main management processes. Its utilisation in different departments will be very beneficial.”

Participant 4 systematically and profoundly explained the benefits of using ERP dashboards such as SAP by stating,

“SAP offers a lot of functions for warehousing. That includes essentially the sort of storage or the model for utilisation, for instance, if it's first in first out or last in first out. The FIFO is completely handled via SAP then we have my procurement functions where the generation of purchase requisitions and generation for materials and services are both done via SAP, the end user generates his requisition to get approved, and it is forwarded automatically to the supply chain department, procurement officer or the buyer and then the buyer once he has his bids, he can forward that data through SAP to the user which is of course very efficient. Then finally an order is placed based on that information. Getting services and materials becomes extremely easy for every user.”

Participant 7 showed that ERP's role in supply chain management is very important to keep records updated and accurate. This can directly affect the efficacy of organization.

However, participant 8 showed that ERPs are beneficial cost constraints and lack of trained personnel are the core barriers arising in its implementation. He stated,

“Beneficial but not implemented due to cost and lack of trained personnel.”

On the other hand, participant 9 highlighted the use of MS Excel for basic worksheets and manual entries. Participant 10 showed that if ERPs can be integrated effectively, transparency and traceability can be easily promoted in the value chain. He stated,

“If integrated effectively, it will help in promoting transparency and traceability in the value chain.”

Therefore, ERP’s role in supply chain management can promote transparency and traceability. SAP is one of the software used for this purpose. However, these require huge implementation costs that can constrain in its implementation along with the lack of trained personnel.

4.3.2.4 Levels of supply chain

The respondents were inquired to share their observations related to levels of the supply chain in their respective firms and associated SMEs. The respondents working in larger firms reported comprehensive levels in their firms but blended or undefined structures in the supply chain mechanisms of SMEs and micro businesses. Participant 1 reported no demarcation in SMEs by stating,

“They're more blended.”

Similar to these responses, those associated with SMEs also mentioned the absence of predefined lines or levels in the supply chain of their firms. Participant 6 said,

“We are tier one supplier of all the OEMs in Pakistan. We don't have such levels in our company.”

Participant 7 showed that the level of supply chain in their organization is based on 2 tier procurement and production that is usually intermixed. Participant 8 depicted they have one level of the supply chain that lacks clarity. He stated,

“One level, either procurement or production, lacks clarity.”

On the other hand, participant 9 showed that levels are 2 to 3 at max. Participant 10 showed that they have no fine boundaries in levels of the supply chain. Thus, most of the organizations don't have clarity on the levels of supply chain. Most of the responses show that these levels are blended in production and procurement.

4.3.2.4.1 Knowledge transfer among value chain partners

While examining the benefits of partnering with SMEs, the technology and knowledge are considered to be seamlessly shared with the partners at all stages of the value chain. Through analysis of collected responses, it is observed that there are various means of knowledge sharing with the supply chain partners established in larger enterprises, but due to limited technological access and resources in SMEs and Micro businesses, the sharing of knowledge cannot be optimised. However, there are mechanisms established in large firms to help small businesses and value chain partner's access and download technical information through portals. In large organisations, knowledge sharing is effectively managed by formal sessions, proper documentation, on-site visits, and mobile lab testing. Similarly, Participants 2 and 4 emphasised the role of documentation and its substantial effectiveness as compared to the use of verbal mode in knowledge sharing. Participant 1 shared that,

“We have technical assistance sessions, we visit their sites, we give them production tips for activities to enhance productivity, and we give them tips on site.”

Participant 5 added,

“We have our SRM portal (supplier relationship management portal) where we upload documents, and the supplier downloads it from there, and if it is normal routine information we transfer it verbally.”

Participants 3 and 6 emphasised documentation is important but lacking in SMEs for knowledge sharing among the value chain partners. The verbal mode of knowledge sharing has several disadvantages, such as discrepancies, inappropriate mixing of

quantities, and miscommunication. These issues may lead to ineffective outcomes. Participant 6 further said,

“The flow of knowledge sharing should not be verbal it should be on a document, it should be done on software available in the market.”

Participant 7 depicted that knowledge transfer is one of the benefits for SMEs. Knowledge sharing among value chain partners is limited to running smooth activities of production, supplier information transfer, and raw material PIS. Participant 8 showed that knowledge sharing is limited to joint ventures and little R&D operations. Participant 9 also showed a somewhat similar response. He said,

“Research for design development, seminars and training sessions, discussion.”

This means that knowledge sharing among value chain partners should be based on research for product design development. Training seminars and discussions could be other knowledge-sharing approaches. However, in this knowledge and profit-sharing process, microbusinesses have to suffer in most cases. The reason is portrayed by Participant 10. He showed,

“The knowledge sharing and profit sharing are limited as larger enterprises can easily dominate SMEs. In few cases-- no recognition at all.”

Knowledge sharing could be in terms of training seminars and discussions. These knowledge-sharing approaches could be used to share information about product design development, raw material PIS, supplier relationship management, and technical assistance sessions.

4.3.2.5 Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and microbusinesses

The reasons and needs of large firms are driving factors for effective collaborations of large organisations with SMEs and micro businesses. The factors involved in collaborations are discussed briefly in earlier themes, while this theme will focus on details of the needs of SMEs and microbusinesses as well as those of larger organisations to

maintain collaborative partnerships for effective value chain operations and performances. Participants 1 and 2 highlighted various intentions behind collaborations, such as improved quality of network and processes, cost advantages, guidance, and knowledge sharing regarding best practices of the industry. Participant 2 further signified,

“The cost is reducing, you are getting the product on time and there are no delivery delays. So, this whole process eventually turns out to be a monetary benefit.”

Participant 3 denoted collaboration should have positive outcomes like cost and feasible adaptations to different effective technical methods but the whole partnership and collaboration should never affect the quality of a product. He specified the quality of the product is an element that should remain independent of any collaboration with larger firms. He said,

“Collaboration probably should not affect the quality, if the SME is keeping their product to a certain quality, they should always deliver that quality.”

Participant 7 showed that the collaboration of SMEs with large firms can always be positive for outsourcing value activities, time efficiency, supplier and distribution system of SMEs. Participant 8 also showed,

“Better understanding of niche market, supplier and distribution system.”

Other benefits were also identified by Participant 9. These are cost benefits and enhanced overall performance improvement with the use of these collaborations. Whereas participant 10 showed collaboration outcomes in terms of product customization to meet local market demands. He stated,

“Quality products customised according to local market demands, in lower budget.”

The responses conclude that collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses can benefit in terms of product customisation, niche market, supplier and distribution system, as well as deliverance of quality.

4.3.2.5.1 Benefits of collaboration with larger organisations

Effectively planned and transparent communication among collaborators has positive effects on the overall value chain and experience. Participant 2 signified the various reasons and benefits including, seeking a review for their process or product, feasibility, along with benefits of clarity in instructions and directions received from large companies. Similarly, participant 3 also highlighted that larger firms have more systematic and transparent processes that provide more clarity in instructions facilitating ease of operations and production. Participant 3 also notified the benefits of technical drawings that are provided by larger organisations. He further emphasised,

“We put it in the machine, make a unit, look at it, measure it and then take it off, do further work on it. To make it perfect. By doing the detailed design that is given to us by collaborating with this large organisation.”

Participant 1 also indicated the sharing of technical knowledge, sustainable improvements in the quality of the product along with cost benefits. The larger firms willing to establish beneficial collaboration also supported their firm by providing the technical evaluation for their product.

Participant 5 signified that their collaboration with larger firms has potentially enhanced their organisational outputs along with having several benefits. Participant 4 mentioned the collaboration of his organisation with larger and international firms for improving their processes and gaining more insightful knowledge regarding best industry practices. Similar benefits were also elaborated in responses collected from participant 4 that organisations tend to gain insights from larger organisations to develop sound technical backgrounds related to technology through contracts for collaborations for symposiums and conferences to help knowledge sharing. He emphasised in benefits by saying,

“Collaborations helped essentially to learn from those organisations and to essentially grow our processes. We have also taken services from McKinsey to improve our overall processes for the supply chain and Human resource management.”

Participant 7 identified training and development, managerial, operational, and financial benefits as the core outcomes of collaborating with large-scale firms. Whereas,

participant 8 showed that by working in collaboration with large firms, SMEs can generate innovative solutions in their operational processes. He stated,

“Collaborating with large firms can bring innovative solutions, unique expertise, or specialised products to the value chain, contributing to overall competitiveness.”

On the other hand, participant 9 showed that collaboration with large firms helps SMEs to build a better identification and presence in the market. This can build up the competitive edge of these SMEs in the market. Participant 10 also revealed market competitiveness as one of the factors as SMEs get the opportunity to work with a highly recognised firm. He stated,

“Exposure and familiarity with complex structures, norms, and processes of the larger organisation. Opportunity to work with a recognised organisation. Market competitiveness – improved.”

The responses conclude that collaborations with large firms benefit SMEs in terms of innovative solutions, Market competitiveness, sound technical support, improved processes, practices, and gaining more insightful knowledge.

4.3.2.5.2 Barriers faced in collaboration

Collaboration with larger companies may have its challenges and to assess the willingness of firms to collaborate it is important to observe their efforts to minimise these barriers. Participant 2 notified that the only barrier they faced with collaborating with international organisations is a language barrier. Participant 3 mentioned that collaborations require regulatory procedures and approvals such as certification and licensing, in addition to banking requirements and other aspects.

Participant 4 also suggested that there were hardly any barriers they faced in collaborating with international or larger organisations. Participant 5 emphasised that collaborating with SMEs has some challenges like managing inventory, production and storage space is challenging. Otherwise, while collaborating with larger organisations he said,

“I don’t recall any barriers.”

Moreover, the response predominantly depicted that there are very few barriers compared to the benefits of collaboration with larger organisations.

However, participant 6 shared his reservations and experiences related to barriers and initiatives for minimising their impact. He notified the interviewer that during collaborations with other firms, there are chances of facing issues in a managerial capacity, communications and logistics issues. There are monetary challenges and such collaborations and improvements require optimisation of the budget for executing changes in infrastructure, processes and technological advancements. As participant 6 said,

“They can provide technical knowledge, they can provide as much assistance as needed. But it’s the SME who has to implement all those knowledge and which sometimes requires a hefty investment or huge investment.”

The barriers of collaborating with larger companies could be in terms of detailed processes in terms of approvals, management, and transactions. These responses were highlighted by Participant 7, who stated,

“Large organisations have detailed processes, including approvals, management, and transactions. Offer less for products and services with high market competition.”

Similar responses were attained from Participant 8. He showed that large-scale firms have complex and global supply chains. This also creates high market competition which is the reason that firms offer less for their products and services.

“Large organisations often have complex and global supply chains. Offer less for products and services with high market competition.”

Participant 9 showed that large organizations can overshadow SMEs. This situation leads SMEs to seek recognition from Participant 9 for their collaboration so that they can add value to their portfolio. However, these collaborations can negatively affect the protection of intellectual property. He stated,

“SMEs are easily overshadowed by larger companies. SMEs seek acknowledgment and recognition for their collaboration to add value to their portfolio. This will also hinder the protection of intellectual property (if applicable).”

Another reason is the dependency of medium-sized firms on larger firms. The justification that MBS can't access new markets for growth without partnerships with large firms. Participant 10 stated all these barriers.

“SMEs may face challenges in accessing new markets without the support of a larger partner. Large enterprises may control distribution channels, limiting the MB's ability to reach a broader customer base.”

Thus, the dependability of SMEs on large firms is higher as they cannot grow without their support. Other barriers are lack of technical knowledge, investment, communications, and logistics issues.

4.3.2.6 Role of SMEs and micro-business on the economy of Pakistan

The respondents were also inquired about their perspectives and beliefs related to the contribution and role of SMEs and Micro businesses in the economic state of the country, Pakistan. Participant 4 emphasised that Engro considers SMEs critical for their growth and the success of the country. Therefore, his firm is making efforts to encourage SMEs and help them sustain themselves. Respondents also denoted that an increase in business and production will eventually help industries grow and it will also affect the economy of the country. As participant 6 said,

“We increase our value chain, so more business comes to the industries and it will affect in a positive way. And the more the better.”

Financial activities and performances have a positive impact on the GDP and economic growth of the country. When respondents were asked to share their opinion, participant 1 implied stated,

"The growth of our SMEs is directly linked to the growth of polymer and the economic development of Pakistan."

In contrast, participant 7 demonstrated a positive impact of SMEs on Pakistan's economic output. Similar responses were observed from Participant 8, who stressed the fact that job creation majorly affects Pakistan's economic development. He stated,

"SMEs are significant contributors to job creation and economic development. Engaging with SMEs in the value chain can have positive social and economic impacts on local communities."

Similar types of opinions were observed from the responses of Participant 9, who stressed on employment opportunities. He stated,

"Job creation, employment opportunities, and foreign exchange (if applicable) can boost the economic situation of the country."

Interviewee 9 showed that foreign collaborations of local collaborators can reduce cost per unit which can directly affect financial performance. The results can be a major support factor for industry in Pakistan. An eventual impact can be seen in Pakistan's economic development.

"Foreign collaborations will bring high revenue.

In case of local collaborations, the profitability margins are enhanced remarkably, cost per unit is decreased, and increased financial performance will support the industry and eventually Pakistan."

The opinions of all respondents in the study were in favour of the positive role of SMEs and micro businesses in Pakistan's GDP growth and economy.

4.4 Chapter Summary

The findings are critically evaluated in this chapter to explore research questions or objectives formed in the study. The first question explores the level where SMEs/Microbusinesses could enter the value chain. Analysis concluded from the

thematic analysis shows that SMEs in different industries enter the supply chain at earlier stages for the production of quality products. The literature shows the reason is to reduce costs to get a positive change in a firm's profitability and other aspects of performance. Indirect procurement causes excessive costs in terms of custom duty on imports of raw materials and other costs.

On the other hand, the second question gives insight into the role of sustainability practices of microbusinesses and SMEs as value chain partner. The results from thematic analysis and literature confirm that sustainability can positively affect the reputation of microbusinesses. Responses identify that SMEs use sustainable practices of reducing wastage and offering improved quality of the material. The sustainability practices of these firms are limited as these can be a cost burden for microbusinesses or SMEs. These findings in the literature provide supporting evidence of responses.

The third question digs into the benefits offered to the supply chain partners, especially financial benefits. Participants shared that supply chain partnerships are affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks. The results could be improved profitability, cost benefits with alternative options for companies to outsource materials, and maximization in revenue margins. All of these findings are supported in the light of literature which confirms the positive financial benefits of supply chain partnerships.

The 4th question needs an evaluation on the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs. Findings show that large-scale businesses collaborate with SMEs to gain a helping hand in best practices used in the industry, i.e., distribution network minimise the cost base of the company. These responses confirm the findings of literature showing that collaboration with large companies helps SMEs be keen in knowledge sharing and sharing of technical information and other elements.

5 Chapter 5: Discussion

This section provides a brief insight into the analysis attained with the help of the qualitative data collection method of interviews. The responses of participants were analysed in the previous section to interpret research findings related to different questions of this study. The section provides a brief discussion of supportive evidence attained in light of previous studies which are used to back up the findings of this research. The discussion also provides insight into responses which are contradictory to the findings of previous studies.

5.1 SMEs' entrance into the value chain

This section provides insight into first regarding objective targeted in the study. SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain when they want to work collaboratively with larger firms to ensure a good final product. This is important to support the procurement and assembling of materials. Ali, Nag lingam and Gird (2017) also supported this aspect and identified that transportation of products or raw materials becomes challenging which is the main reason that SMEs enter the value chain. This is important to eliminate indirect procurement of raw materials and to get direct supply chain services (Kim, 2009). This can be ultimately supported by the resource-based view theory as the need for different resources required to produce the final product leads SMEs to enter the value chain. For instance, small contractors enter the value chain to get resources for civil works and minor mechanical works. On the other hand, responses in theme 1 and 2 reveals that SMEs in the garment industry enter the supply chain at earlier stages for the production of quality products. Another reason is that by entering the value chain firms can enable cost reduction which can ultimately cause a positive influence on a firm's profitability and other aspects of performance (Walters and Lancaster, 2000). For instance, indirect procurement causes custom duty on imports of raw materials and when firms enter the value chain this cost is eliminated from the production process. Other responses show that firms enter the value chain occasionally. Rajagopal and Bernard (1993) showed that

occasional procurement arises when customer demand is the higher or local market is facing challenges relating to the availability of raw materials due to some uncertain events. These aspects ultimately reveal evidence for 1st research objective targeted in the study which shows that the entrance of SMEs into the value chain can be occasional or as per the production needs of the company. Furthermore, analysis shows that the strategic needs of the company lead SMEs to enter the value chain. This can be evidenced by the example of Suzuki Motor Company Japan. Suzuki to remain competitive in the industry has set up joint ventures with local Chinese companies as different auto giants have adopted this strategy (GAO Et Al., 2022). The author showed that companies are taking the utmost benefit of Chinese low-cost labour and innovative technological advancements produced in the country.

5.1.1 Factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations

The analysis shows that some of the main factors include the cost of material and quality concerns, Scarcity or no other supplier, Import and assembling, and Price fluctuations, to produce a high-quality product and to improve efficiency. Xiao and Shi (2016) confirmed these findings and shows that the cost and prices of raw materials are the main concern of firms to bring changes in their value chain operations. For instance, when the local market reveals an increase in raw material prices firms switch towards the international market to get a hold of affordable raw materials; otherwise the production cost will be higher and they will be needed to increase their product prices (Auer, Bormio and Filardo, 2017). Thus, to keep up with customers and the market needs firms to enter the value chain or bring changes to it. On the other hand, many firms bring changes in their value chain when they want to keep up with rapid advancements in market needs. For instance, in the IT sector rapid market needs create a need for these companies to evolve their position and competitive edge (Prajogo and Olhager, 2012). This is the main reason that changes in value chain operations are more frequent in the IT sector. Responses further reveal that production department needs are fulfilled by bringing changes in value chain

operations and eliminating financial issues faced by the company. The fact is that financial sustainability is dependent on cost reduction and efficient management of cost is necessary to enhance a company's performance in the industry (Glover et al., 2014). On the other hand, scarcity of suppliers could be the main reason to bring changes in value chain operations. Lack of technological knowledge could be another reason as different automobile firms switch towards international markets when the local market lacks technical knowledge like engineers and others (Gupta, Kusi-Sarpong and Rezaei, 2020). This can be evidenced in the case of Pakistan as automobile companies are more reliant on international markets for technical knowledge required to manufacture products. All of these are mandatory for cater the needs of sustainable innovation (Gupta, Kusi-Sarpong and Rezaei, 2020).

Some of the needs identified by businesses to use the value chain are to maintain a low-cost advantage, meet KPI and a need to make continuous improvements in operations. Zokaei and Simons (2006) supported this element and demonstrated the fact that firms bring changes in their value chain when they are in need to bring changes to their product (new features, improved technology, or omitting outdated methods). This type of transformation of product is necessary to match with changing needs of customers and attain a competitive edge in the industry (Roper, Du and Love, 2008). In other cases, the lack of transformations of changes in products concerning market needs can lead the company to face survival issues in the market. Responses show that it can enable a win-win situation for the organisation. Chapman and Corso (2005) showed that if these continuous improvement needs were not catered companies can face a huge loss in their operations. Thus, a more sustainable competitive advantage can be gained by firms by bringing changes in value chain operations. Furthermore, monetary benefits can be higher as is evident from the analysis of responses. These aspects support the achievement of new resource capabilities for the firm and continuous improvements ultimately mark a unique performance of the firm in the industry (Chapman and Corso, 2005). A supporting response observed shows that companies use value chains when they need to be technically strong in the industry based on their unique product offerings

and based on their productivity/performance. Therefore, with improved performance productivity generated on resources of the company could be higher. These aspects ultimately conclude the fact that business needs to evolve their performance from time to time to meet the ever-changing needs of customers. This is the core reason that they use value chain operations to achieve these goals and to be competitive.

Qualitative data collection method of interviews provide insight into the analysis of factors which lead SMEs to globalise their value chain. Some of the factors identified in the analysis include the expansion needs of organisations with low-cost advantages, dynamics of the automobile industry, assembling cars on petrol, diesel, and natural gas and transforming to produce hybrid and electronic vehicles. Holweg (2005) supported the fact that the dynamics and changing needs of customers in the automobile industry have created a strong need for companies to globalise their value chains. The author showed that different markets are proved to be premiere resorts for vehicle assembly. For instance, China, India and Mexico have attractive automobile assembling industries (Humphrey and Memedovic, 2003). Whereas, In the Triad regions including America and Canada, i.e. North America, Japan and Western Europe are considered mature vehicles industry. During the 1990s, imported Japanese passenger cars were built in transplant factories which enhanced the production volume and sales of cars in the country (Humphrey and Memedovic, 2003). Therefore, by the expansion of operations in these global markets companies can expand their production volume and sales which can cause a positive influence on organisational performance. Another response in the analysis also provides supporting evidence by showing that they send their workers to different countries like Japan, and Thailand to gain insight into a good manufacturing conducive environment. The results can be in terms of improvements in their skill set which can enhance the knowledge base of the company so that quality and financial performance can be enhanced (Lorenz, 2015). Adam Smith (1776) also showed that the expansion of operations in the international market can be supported back from the findings of international trade theory. The theory shows that if one country has an advantage in one particular product over some other country and vice versa then trading

between these countries can be beneficial for the success of both. Therefore, under the evidence of international trade theory, companies get a competitive advantage when they globalise their value chains. The results can be in terms of efficient production outcomes, effective value chain mapping and achievement of customer needs.

Responses show that companies have attained expansion of operations, and enabled efficient production management with the use of value-creation activities. The changes in value-creation activities have enabled firms to enhance their financial and non-financial performance in the industry. The outcomes are enabling companies to evolve their position and a positive effect on the survival of firms can be seen. Kaplinsky (2004) showed that value chain development supports the creation of a customer-oriented chain which can enhance business productivity and functionality. Value chains within the private sector and public sector organisations are influencing the performance of different companies operating in the technological and automobile sectors (Irshad, 2015). Multinationals play an integral role in the automobiles and telecommunications industries which have enhanced the value chain development of these sectors (Hitt, Li and Xu, 2016). These multinationals in the value chain are also working in collaboration with SMEs which are positively influencing knowledge, technology and resource transfer that are benefiting SMEs. The justification is that SMEs cannot afford to invest in R&D activities, as these require huge amounts of investment and the results can be uncertain. This is the main reason that they are needed to rely on multinationals in the value chain to attain knowledge resources or technologies from them so that these can be appropriately used in organisational operations. By working with multinationals in the value chain, SMEs can utilise these resources to produce new products and to bring differentiation in existing products offered by the company. Therefore, outcomes of the value chain can be in terms of improved product portfolio, product differentiation, increased production, profitability and competitive edge of firms.

5.1.2 Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance

This section provides insight into the second research objective targeted in the study. The analysis provides findings related to value chain operations changes and the effects of these on organisational performance. Responses for the PVC sector show that demand has shown a rise and import has its issues besides disruptions. This is the reason that market demand is met by maintaining an equilibrium position in the market. Some of the strategies used by PVC companies to attain positive effects on organisational performance are exchanging defective goods to enable customer loyalty. Furthermore, quality is preferred over cost to maximise customer satisfaction which was also supported in the study by Lee, Lee and Feick (2001). Other responses show that value chain operation changes were installing new machinery to facilitate the new model and to boost organisational performance. It was shown by a participant that a local company provides the same job at a lesser cost in the same amount of time with no load and logistic problems. This ultimately contradicts the fact identified in international trade models as national transactions can cost lower for SMEs. However, the cost-based issues can be minimised for companies who are offering products in higher production volumes. Whereas, Birou and Fawcett (1993) showed that in case of lower production volumes, the cost of procuring raw materials internationally can be a burden on the financial performance of the company. Some responses show that Risk factor evaluation and analysis of different raw material prices such as Crude oil price effects are evaluated. These are used by participants in SMEs to bring changes in the value chain and procurement activities as the effects of crude oil prices can also influence the prices of different materials. Laborde, Martin and Vos (2021) showed that crude oil price changes directly influence transportation and logistics costs. This is the main reason that companies should critically analyse changes in their prices to develop new procurement strategies. Some responses provide evidence that SAP was used for the centralisation of all processes. Klaus, Rosemann and Gable (2000) showed that this ERP system provides data processing and effective resource planning which can enhance the outcomes of value chain operations. Therefore, problems or factors leading to inefficiencies can be

critically evaluated. A response shows that Joint ventures –helped Suzuki motors and local manufacturers. Bamford, Ernst and Fubini (2004) showed that joint ventures can at times not generate effective results as home and foreign country operational integration can be challenging.

5.1.3 Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs

A response identified in the analysis shows that SMEs do not have many sustainability practices, whereas, a participant has not responded to this question which ultimately reveals somewhat similar opinions. Müller and Voigt (2018) have supported these elements and identified that SMEs are usually in the growing phase which is the main reason that they struggle for profit generation and try to develop a strong image in the market. Some other strategic goals of SMEs are maximizing productivity, and sales volume and improving the value chain model which is the main reason that sustainability goals lack in many SME firms. Therefore, almost 3 participants have supported these elements as sustainability practices were not utilised. Other responses show that adaptability to change is important and the company is shifting towards electronic vehicles and hybrid style. Saidur et al., (2011) showed that these vehicles are enabling environmental sustainability as burning too much gasoline in vehicles can be avoided with the use of these vehicles. This would ultimately reduce CO₂ emissions from vehicles along with Greenhouse gas (GHS) emissions that arise in fuel extraction and refining activities. On the other hand, a response shows that sustainable practices like reducing wastage and offering improved quality of the material were also utilised. This is the most common sustainable practice which should be adopted by small companies to operate responsibly in the market. The analysis also reveals that sustainability practices have the potential to affect business value chain efficiency and effectiveness. For instance reduction of waste can also affect the cost efficiency of the company. Therefore, SMEs and micro businesses utilizing sustainability practices are getting positive outcomes from their strategies.

The analysis provides a brief insight into the negative and positive effects of sustainability on organisational performance. One of the responses highlights that sustainability has a negative effect and the respondent showed that SMEs are not interested in sustainable practices as they require investment. Therefore, affordability issues create barriers to developing these sustainability strategies. Vaaland and Heide (2007) have also demonstrated insight regarding this element and showed that SMEs can be a cost burden for these businesses in many cases as they require some initial investment. On the other hand, Singal (2014) showed that some sustainability initiatives can be easily used by firms with an upfront investment like keeping stuck with change and improvements in operations. This initiative can improve the efficiency of the company and economic sustainability can be higher. However, environmental sustainability initiatives like dumping waste lawfully and responsibly are important. Due to the fact that if these activities of firms will not be environmentally friendly; a firm can even face penalties or lawsuits from the government which can ruin the company's image or position in the industry. Overlooking these aspects it can be demonstrated that sustainability can positively affect SMEs or micro businesses and their value chain operations (Brammer, Hojmoose, and Marchant, 2012). Some other types of sustainability practices used by responses are change and evolution to bring out a positive impact, waste management, disposal of hazardous waste etc. inclusive of these environmental sustainability activities, economic sustainability is targeted by international contracts with exporters and stabilizing routine operational activities and performance. You and Bell (2007) showed that sustainability initiatives of firms support the development of a strong company image in the market which can directly affect its competitive edge. Therefore, sustainability has a positive influence on a company's value chain operations and performance in the long run.

The research questionnaire was designed to evaluate the sustainability of microbusinesses and their effect on the survival of the firm in the market. One of the responses shows that SMEs can challenge the existence of larger enterprises if they start considering sustainable practices. Jessica Hwang and Lockwood (2006) showed that

limited resources create barriers for SMEs to invest in sustainable practices which ultimately causes limited growth. However, if SMEs will focus on sustainability their existence can affect large-scale businesses as every country have a large number of SMEs in comparison with large enterprises. In the era of modernism, advancement and competitiveness the survival of SMEs has become very difficult. Sustainable performance in business is vital for the existence of SMEs. To attain sustainable performance one faces various social, technological and economic challenges. The biggest challenge for SMEs is competition. In the market where giant companies are working, SMEs face economic problems, as their pockets are not as deep as compared to national and multinational organisations. By achieving sustainability in the organisational performance SMEs can overcome economic challenges. However, sustainability has not enough potential to affect the survival of firms in the industry.

In contrast, RBV has the potential to affect a firm's survival in the industry as it could directly influence a company's performance. According to RBV, the firms have a goal of gaining maximum profit and managers should adopt logical and practical skills. This is important to deliver efficient deliverance and functioning in the industry to achieve stability in the business (Bromiley and Papenhausen, 2003). One of the dominant theoretical concepts of RBV is VRIO which shows that for sustainable management of resources, these should be valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable resources and effective organisation of these resources should be done (Barney et al., 2001). These aspects enable the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage with efficient management of resources.

One of the responses shows that Pak Suzuki does not have a vendor who could have helped develop parts in Pakistan. If parts were available in Pakistan this could have positively affected the survival of the automotive industry. This is the core reason that parts are needed to be imported which ultimately affects the cost and pricing of the cars. These challenges are causing survival issues for automotive companies. Singh (2011) showed that value chain operation with international trade creates ease for firms and

improves their production efficiency. However, it increases the cost burden as materials sourced from international markets can be affected by exchange rates. The reasoning is that a higher exchange rate might create a need to pay more home currency (Lu and Beamish, 2001). Further freight charges and other taxes might also push the cost. These aspects were identified in the analysis and respondents have shown that import, Freight charges, exchange rates and contractors could affect the survival of the business. On the other hand, a response shows that project delays can cause major issues. If one business stops it can affect others. For instance, the semiconductor shortage in Malaysia during covid-19 negatively impacted several MNCs. Therefore, it can be demonstrated that not only sustainability can affect the survival of SMEs but there are some internal and external organisational factors which can also influence the performance of the company. A response also backs up this fact by saying that in Pakistan sustainability cannot affect businesses. Given the fact that different developed countries have produced strong legislation and regulations against companies that are not adopting sustainability. However, Pakistan has not progressed on this matter and companies usually do not face any threat even when they do something against environmental sustainability (Ikram et al., 2019). This aspect ultimately provides insight or supporting evidence for 2nd research objective targeted in the study regarding the sustainability of microbusinesses and SMEs' role in the value chain.

5.1.4 Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners

This section provides insight into 3rd research objective developed in the study regarding the benefits (especially profits) shared by value chain participants. The analysis provides a brief insight into the benefits which can be obtained by SMEs as value chain participants. These benefits are higher product differentiation, improved portfolio, enhanced production and monetary benefits. National Research Council (2000) demonstrated the fact that product differentiation can be attained by SMEs as value chain participants. The reasoning is that companies can source material resources or technical skills from different markets nationally and internationally which can ultimately support the

company to differentiate products from its competitors. New opportunities to differentiate current products of the company. For instance, when SMEs only access the national market to obtain raw materials and skills required to assemble products; differentiation can be lower. However, from the international market procurement of materials and resources can enable the company to attain a wide range of resources which can ultimately enhance the differentiation aspect.

One of the responses shows that outsourcing was used for transportation, warehouse and labour which supports technical assistance and knowledge to maximise the financial performance of the company. Engro has used third-party logistics. Giri and Sarker (2017) supported the fact that outsourcing transportation, and warehousing reduces the operational burden on the company. One example can be evidenced by the case of McDonald's as the company has adopted technology-oriented outsourcing in Pakistan. Outsourcing is benefiting companies to get very modern and advanced food-oriented products to supply chains working almost in all parts of the globe (Ram, 2004). On the other hand, Liu et al., (2015) showed that logistics and management of transportation could burden companies at times but outsourcing can ultimately support effective management of logistics. For instance, the transportation of raw materials and finished goods can be effectively managed with the use of logistics services or 3PL. These aspects ultimately affect business stability and efficiency which can directly influence business outcomes like profitability and competitive edge.

Another response also shows that bidding, agreement and contracts are utilised to obtain specific services. The increasing demands and production volumes are resulting in suppliers getting winning contracts (Govindan, Kannan and Haq, 2010). Under these contracts, suppliers are required to work on one or a few parts of the vehicle. This ultimately supports the assembling of products in subsystems. After assembling subsystems these can be delivered to the location of the final assembly plant. One of the responses shows that they have shifted towards air shipment modes as other modes of transportation require precise delivery time. For instance, sea transportation might take

days to weeks. Therefore, findings relating to 3PL, outsourcing of operations and assembling of products play a supportive role to shed light on 3rd research objective targeted in the study regarding the benefits shared by value chain participants.

5.2 Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners

5.2.1 Use of technology in value chain management

The analysis provides insight regarding the fact that value chain participants can be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks. These perks are better revenues, lower costs, higher profit margins, and secure safe contracts for a fixed number of years, along with improved production and supply. These could deliver positive financial results in terms of improved profitability. Cost benefits can be higher as different participants create alternative options for companies to outsource materials (Arshinder, Kanda, and Deshmukh, 2007). On the other hand, a response shows that Value chain participants add an advantage to production and manufacturing processes.

Knowledge sharing between companies can enable companies to partner on specific projects and work together by improving manufacturing plants. For instance, automobile companies contract with small-scale suppliers/ vendors to support them in the production of parts. Lema and Lema (2012) demonstrated it as International technology transfer which is considered a multi-dimensional process to transfer information and technical data. Scientific and technical fields' data is shared among organisations, institutions and businesses. At times they also provide support and a helping hand with the company's technicians, engineers and other experts to enable the production of different parts. This sort of practice is adopted by manufacturers to assist their suppliers in different types of product improvements so that the overall value of the product can be improved. These supply chain sustainability practices are now adopted globally to transform for a better vision and change as per customers' needs and demands. These aspects ultimately affect long terms performance outcomes of the company (Marshall et al., 2015). Some other types of supply chain sustainability practices are to promote human rights, fair labour practices, environmental progress and anti-corruption policies. One of the

Responses shows this type of sustainability element that is to focus on minimizing wastage. This element of minimising waste can be considered a sustainability initiative and lacks an appropriate response to the question. Therefore, it can be demonstrated that value chain participants are affected financially as cost benefits are attained by them which maximises revenue margins.

5.2.2 Role of SAP in supply chain management

The analysis provides insight into the evaluation of technology used by companies to monitor the value chain. The majority of them have shown that they are using SAP or ERP software that is positively affecting the evaluation of value chain performance. Monk and Wagner (2012) showed that Enterprise resource planning software's replacing traditional or manual data handling and management methods. Hillman Willis and Hillary Willis-Brown (2002) showed that ERP supports the firm in the effective management of different business functions of an organisation. ERP helps organisations automate and manage core business processes for optimal performance. Using this software large amounts of data can be handled effectively and these can be organised for effective management of resources. Beheshti (2006) showed that ERP directly affects the value chain management of companies as it allows manufacturers to know how and where the inventory is within the chain. This ultimately supports the company to draft a well-planned production strategy. This means that they use data regarding inventory levels, disposal, material procurement records, production performance and other aspects. All of these support the company in supply chain management practices and production management to achieve the targeted production level set up by the organisation.

Analysis reveals that the majority of the participants are using SAP as an ERP software. Gattiker and Goodhue (2004) showed that SAP stands for System Applications and Products in data processing. Some of the benefits of SAP in value chain performance can be in terms of attaining cost efficiency, Better Collaboration throughout Business, enhanced data management, data security can be improved, and faster forecasting and analysis of data can be higher. Cost cutting can be done easily with the use of SAP as

real-time data management can be done which eliminates the administration cost of manual data handling (Plattner and Zeier, 2012). Effective inventory management can play a supporting role to prevent disturbances relating to low inventory which can cause a pause in the production system of the company. Responses show that MS Excel and customised dashboards are also used in this regard. This software is utilised by companies for inventory management. However, their results can be less efficient in comparison with SAP or ERP. One of the respondents showed that none of the technology was used in data handling and manual data handling is performed in paper and tabular forms.

Teittinen, Pellinen and Järvenpää (2013) showed that many companies do not adopt technological software as they have cost issues and limited skills. However, free-of-cost software like Excel available to companies should be incorporated as these can deliver more accurate results in contrast to manual data handling. The justification is that it requires more administration costs and the chances of errors can be higher (Vosburg and Kumar, 2001). Therefore, the majority of the companies have used technologies like SAP, ERP, Excel and dashboards which are supporting them to improve their performance in inventory management and production management.

The analysis provides insight into the supply chain benefits of software used by the company. Some of these benefits of using SAP, MS Excel and customised dashboards are in terms of maintaining and Dealing with SMEs, ledger balances, Buying history, Graphs and performances, Sales tax invoices and Technical literature. Shang and Seddon (2000) showed that SAP could be used according to business scalabilities like SMEs and large-scale firms. One of the benefits of SAP is better management of the business in terms of collaboration. Coordination between the departments is the key to improved management of information throughout the departments of the organisation. SAP helps the organisation to send, receive and manage the data and helps employees and management to use the data effectively. SAP helps the management of data which is very essential for any organisation. The security of the data is also very vital for the

survival of any business sap comes with advanced technologies, security systems and firewalls. The needs of small companies differ from large enterprises, sap is the solution for both of them; whether it could be a start-up business or expansion needed by the firm, Sap helps all types of organisations. Faster and perfect analysis and forecasting is the benefit of SAP (Shang and Seddon, 2000).

Organisations can reduce human error, duplicate entries, and time delays with the help of SAP software. This software enables the organisation to monitor real-time information throughout the departments which helps to manage the resources and forecast effectively the supply and demand for the business. One of the most important benefits of sap is flexibility. Sap is so flexible that every department can use it in their way separately for their benefit. For example, the inventory management module is different from the module of distribution.

Customer information is also manageable in sap which helps customer relation managers to access the information of each customer to satisfy the need of the customer at any time. The role of ERP software like SAP has increased recently and the majority of organisations are replacing their traditional software or manual data handling with ERP software like SAP (Arshinder, Kanda and Deshmukh, 2007). It helps and supports organisations to manage and automate a large amount of data effectively. Sap allows manufacturers to monitor real-time information throughout the business. For example, manufacturers at any time can find out about the inventory in the warehouses or use it. This means that the manufacturers can easily and effectively forecast the needs and demands of the organisation. Responses show that quality and control in management can be higher with the use of SAP as it enables the dissemination and flow of accurate information throughout the organisation. This software plays a significant role in keeping an efficient track of production and management, production management, inventory and product supply which ultimately keeps smoothness of the whole operational process. Using the software, firms can keep track of supply chain needs i.e., to transfer finished

products to market or inventory/ raw material needed to be entered into the production process.

The benefits of utilizing SAP were analysed in the analysis. The results show that this can be adopted as a Single platform, where Centralised procurement can be performed. It helps in forecasting materials and customer demand can be done easily. For instance, customer demand relating to different products might change from season to season. These demand changes can be critically evaluated from buyer history and forecasts can be produced for future customer demands. Lenart (2011) showed that these demand forecasts are used by businesses to draft annual and monthly production plans so that demand and supply gaps might not arise. Other benefits of using SAP are setting up Transportation services scenarios and situational analysis. Situational analysis plays a significant role in companies making alternative plans to deal with different market situations and the needs of customers (Leigh, 2009). Here, internal and external market factors (PESTLE, SWOT, Porter's analysis) are evaluated to observe how these might influence the company's value chain performance in future. Based on this situation analysis, firms make plans to eliminate any potential market threats that they might face in future from the market and strategies are developed for potential market growth options (Sarsby, 2016). Responses also show that KPIs set up for improved value chain performance can be effectively achieved with the use of SAP. Some of these KPIs can be in terms of improved productivity, increased profit margins, lower cost, higher EPS and others (Wu, 2012). These KPIs and their achievement could be easily tracked with the use of SAP and areas requiring improvement can be critically evaluated with the use of this software. The analysis shows that using SAP and Ms Excel Financial analysis can be done conveniently by firms. This can play a significant role in Material controlling and finance controlling, inventory management, financial management and bookkeeping which can be effective to manage inventory efficiently to avoid wastage (Kale, 2014). A response also shows that SAP supports supply chain management from starting from buyer's/suppliers' bids to streamlining the production process and producing the final

product in the market. Responses show that a firm has also partially implemented SAP in the production division.

5.3 Levels of supply chain

This section aims to shed light on 4th research objective designed in the research that is intended to evaluate data of SMEs and micro-businesses at different supply chain levels. One of the responses shows that no demarcations were used and an excel-based supply chain system is adopted which is the core reason that there is a lack of real-time reporting. Another response shows that a procurement agent or vendor is chosen and bidding is used for contracts. Another response shows the use of warehousing facilities which is dependent on the size of an organisation. These responses provide an accurate insight into supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro businesses. This could be because many SMEs and micro businesses are still in the early ages of supply chain management and SCM operations are not matured.

Furthermore, analysis shows that a response which highlights that no distinctive supply chain levels were adopted by SMEs but documented lines of responsibility such as buying/purchasing/production. A response shows that V2V partners, tier one vendors and tier two vendors, tier three partners were used as supply chain levels. This ultimately shows that virtual-to-virtual communication is utilised to exchange information from vendors relating to materials, their cost, and quality and features so that orders could be placed online in Pakistan. However, at times virtual orders can cause quality-related concerns as a detailed physical examination of materials cannot be performed before making a purchase decision. When it comes to Tier 1 Suppliers, are direct suppliers who provide final products and Tier 2 suppliers are subcontractors of these tier 1 suppliers (Tachizawa and Yew Wong, 2014).

Further, a response shows that transportation partners are vehicle-to-vehicle which can play a significant role in eliminating product storage or warehousing cost. V2V communication can support the exchange of information relating to vehicle speed, heading time, current location, traffic and other patterns which can directly affect logistics

management in a positive manner (Harding et al., 2014). Ease of delivery can be higher and the feasible time frame for product and raw material delivery can be higher. On the other hand, a response shows that most SMEs are working here as the downstream and upstream suppliers. Vaachon and Klassen (2006) showed that the upstream supply chain includes all activities used by organisations to source raw material suppliers needed to introduce input in the manufacturing process of the company. Whereas, the downstream supply chain plays a significant role in post-manufacturing activities like distributing the product to the final customer in the market. Therefore, different supply chain levels are tier 1, two and tier 3 vendors, upstream and downstream suppliers in Pakistan which can be used as supporting evidence for 4th research objective.

One of the responses shows that in contrast with SMEs Large firms have proper and defined levels of supply chain and procurement teams. They play a significant role in finalizing the contracts, pricing contracts and performing procurement physically through vendors. Lenny Koh et al. (2007) also demonstrated the fact that the majority of SMEs do not have proper and defined supply chain levels or departments. In Pakistan, there are only a few firms that have defined levels of the supply chain. Whereas, micro-businesses even do not have these.

Lenny Koh et al., (2007) showed that SMEs that do not have good profitability face cost-related issues to maintaining a separate supply chain management team as it can cause a higher payroll cost. However, if these firms can bear the burden of one-time investment in SAP ERP systems, benefits could be higher which can play a supporting role for the company to maximise its return and improve its survival in the market. Therefore, it is true that supply chain management can be different in large-scale and SMEs as both types of companies have different production levels, needs and scalability. In contrast, De Burca Fynes and Marshall (2005) showed that the effects of SCM on operational performance can be the same and the positive influence of SCM can be seen. This can be supported by the responses of participants which shows that a direct and positive influence on the operational performance of firms can be seen.

On the other hand, a response shows that three levels of the supply chain were adopted by a firm. This could include three different levels of the supply chain that are strategic, tactical and operational level. The strategic planning supply chain is all about making decisions relating to single sourcing or multiple supplier sourcing, location and other decisions are made according to the company's strengths and weaknesses. Here, this strategic planning plays a vital role in supporting the achievement of organisational goals (Bilgen and Ozkarahan, 2004). Tactical planning is used to develop specific plans and develop strategic targets to achieve specific goals. Examples of these can include purchasing, transportation, warehouse location, distribution channels and centres. Operational execution is used to enable the implementation of tactical plans into actions, where day-to-day tasks are performed, production schedules are set up and inventory is managed accordingly along with coordinating resources. All of these levels ultimately support on-time delivery and cost-efficiency in the process. However, the majority of SMEs have not adopted these levels as responses evaluated in the analysis show.

5.3.1 Knowledge transfer among value chain partners

The analysis provides insight into the practices used by supply chain participants for knowledge transfer. One of the responses shows that Knowledge transfer is formal and informal both via newsletters, on-site visits, and presentation sessions. They have used pamphlets, finished products are tested through mobile labs and demos are performed. Three other respondents have also shown that they are using verbal and formal communication with the use of documents. Two participants showed that they are using SAP for complete documentation. The supplier relationship management portal on SAP is used to communicate with different suppliers. Knolmayer et al., (2009) have supported this aspect and showed that from one platform effective communication with different suppliers can be done regarding the needs of raw materials, cost, quality and other aspects. Therefore, SAP could be considered an effective tool for knowledge transfer and formal communication. On the other hand, respondents that are not using SAP have shown that lack of documentation and SAP use might cause errors, discrepancies and

quantities to get mixed. Furthermore, the communication gap with suppliers could be higher due to the fact that verbal or informal communication is used which might negatively influence organisational performance (Li et al., 2015). Both formal and informal communication should be used by organisations in SCM to enable the free flow of information irrespective of hierarchy and structure. This can directly affect the company's performance positively with effective knowledge transfer.

5.4 Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses

This section intends to analyse 4th research question which is to assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses. One of the responses shows that large-scale business collaboration with SMEs is used to gain guidance on best practices used in the industry, in distribution network quality and to minimise the cost base of the company. Van Gils and Zwart (2004) supported these elements and demonstrated that this can positively influence product quality. The collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs can directly affect a company's production scale. For instance, by collaborating with large-scale firms, SMEs can enhance their production levels as they can gain useful experience and expertise from these companies. Thus, SMEs can attain the benefit of on-time product delivery and no delivery delays (Van Gils and Zwart, 2004). Another response shows that knowledge sharing between large SMEs and small-scale businesses results from OEM. Original Equipment manufacturing term is common in the automotive and IT industry, where a company produces a product and it is resold or rebranded by another firm (Lin, 2004). Thus, OEM gives business to small manufacturing enterprises which was also highlighted in the responses. This ultimately supports knowledge transfer as certain technical information relating to tools and material are shared with SMEs reselling their products. Lewis (2002) showed that for quality, it is important that larger firms should transfer their information to SMEs to help optimise their operations and maximise profits by reducing costs. A response shows that Pak Suzuki has introduced a supplier uplifting programme in this regard to enable knowledge transfer

to supplier firms or SMEs. Knowledge transfer should include technical, managerial and operational knowledge, leadership skills and other attributes.

The analysis provides insight into large-scale collaborations done by the company. One of the responses shows that they have collaborated with exporters. Another response shows that Pakistan Suzuki Motors have collaborated with Indonesia Thailand and Taiwan Suzuki corp. These international collaborations of different subsidiaries in foreign countries enable companies to attain knowledge transfer that can deliver performance improvements (Kaminski, de Oliveira and Lopes, 2008). Benefits in the automobile industry can be in terms of high vehicle quality, improved design features and other aspects. Instructions are also transferred from the headquarters of the company in this manner so that overall company performance can be higher and targeted KPI benchmarks can be achieved. Responses also show that collaboration with IMC or Pak Suzuki has enabled the company to attain technological achievement in terms of robots for welding and manual work replace by robots. These technological advancements are enabling the company to improve time duration, production and quality of products which was also supported in the study of Koc and Ceylan (2007). Another response shows that a PVC-producing company has also collaborated with SGS and ICI. The partnership is used for the betterment with the help of informal communication or discussions related to safety, practices, sales and production. These support the company to eliminate PVC industry issues. A company has collaborated with McKinsey for overall processes for the supply chain and HR. O'Mahoney and Sturdy (2016) showed that McKinsey plays a supporting role for companies to analyse their current market situation and internal environment and to develop new strategies for delivering performance improvements. All of these attributes show that collaboration with large-scale companies is done to improve product quality and other operations.

5.4.1 Benefit of partnership

Analysis shows that organisation output of organisations has changed by collaborating with large-scale firms. These benefits are in terms of Technical knowledge, cost benefits

and securing improved quality. Nieto and Santamaría (2010) supported these findings and highlighted that collaborations with large-scale firms can enable SMEs to enable position their brand and product in the market. Furthermore, international clients can be attained which can directly affect organisational output. These aspects were observed in the responses of participants. One of the responses shows that locals give sketches and simple CAD drawings with minimum details. However, more technical details were provided by large-scale firms. This could directly deliver an improvement in process efficiency and improvement capacities and capabilities (Nieto and Santamaría, 2010). The Author showed the fact that collaboration with large-scale firms can be highly supportive in scenarios when the company offers complex products in the market (i.e., PVC or automobiles). The technical teams in these companies can play a supporting role as they are good at technicalities which can be minimal in SMEs. One of the supporting responses shows that radiators or shock absorbers or silencer assembly was supported with the help of large-scale collaboration. Therefore, collaboration with the large-scale firm can benefit organisations to enable the achievement of targeted organisational objectives in terms of improved product quality, improved capacity and performance.

The analysis provides barriers faced in collaboration with large firms and one of the response shows Language barriers as one of the most common issues. Tenzer, Pudelko and Harzing (2014) also showed that language barriers can arise while working in partnership with large-scale firms in international markets. This language barrier can directly affect informal and formal communication between the companies which might cause communication gaps at times. Another response shows that contracts with European countries have different barriers to Export licensing issues and different types of Regulatory requirements (banks and other agencies are involved). Export licenses are issued by licensing agencies after critically reviewing the facts surrounding the given export transaction (Moyer Jr and Mabry, 1983). This export licensing can be challenging at times as rejection might be faced. Furthermore, there could be unforeseen tariffs, custom issues and other aspects. These aspects can cause an indirect influence on the cost base of the company. Other responses show managerial issues, communications

issues, logistics issues and financial barrier is the most important. The fact is that SMEs need investment to execute collaboration and implement new changes which can be a burden at times. However, Nieto and Santamaría (2010) showed that the benefits of collaborating with large-scale firms can be much higher in comparison with investment done by SMEs as long-term changes in financial and non-financial performance can be evidenced.

5.5 Role of SMEs and micro business on the economy of Pakistan

The analysis provides an overview of the effects of the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs and their effects on the economic development of Pakistan. One of the responses in this regard shows that SMEs Growth is linked with Engro and another response also shows that Engro Polymer understands the issues and hardships of SMEs. Another response shows that all activities of the value chain have a positive impact on the economy of Pakistan. Zafar and Mustafa (2017) have also supported the response and showed that value chain maturity in Pakistan can directly affect the value of businesses and the economic development of the country. Therefore, for uninterrupted growth, value chain challenges must be minimised so that companies can thrive towards the success and growth of Pakistan. Kongolo (2010) also showed that SMEs play a major role in employment creation in Pakistan and more SMEs should come into the market for the GDP and employment growth of the country. These effects were also uncovered in the responses of participants. However, a participant also showed that SMEs are less acknowledged for their efforts. On the other hand, a response shows that the profitability of SMEs has the potential to directly affect the GDP growth of the country and its economic stability which can directly affect industrial growth as well. It can play a supporting role in the economy of Pakistan as Dollar payments are bringing remittances to the country. Therefore, a positive impact of SMEs can be seen in the economic growth of Pakistan.

5.6 Critical summary for findings of Themes

The first theme reveals SMEs' entrance into the value chain. Responses show that microbusinesses enter the value chain to work collaboratively with larger firms to ensure a good final product. The need for entrance can be in terms of procurement and assembling of materials. Ali, Nag Lingam, and Gird (2017) supported these findings by highlighting that they could be supportive in the transportation of products or raw materials. Without entrance in the value chain, these can be challenging for SMEs which also eliminates indirect procurement of raw materials (Kim, 2009). These factors and needs to enter the value chain are identified by respondents in theme 2. They have elaborated on the needs of material procurement, elimination of indirect procurement process, improvements of supply chain processes, and other aspects. These findings of theme 2 were also covered in the study of Walters and Lancaster (2000). The author identified that value chain firms can enable cost reduction to being positive improvements in their profitability and other aspects of performance. Given the fact that indirect procurement causes custom duty on raw material imports which ultimately affects production costs. Thus, cost reduction can be done. These aspects are identified in findings obtained from theme 3.

The findings observed regarding 4th theme highlight sustainable practices used in Microbusinesses and SMEs. Participants show that sustainability practices are used to adapt to change which is done by shifting from electronic vehicles to hybrid styles. Saidur et al. (2011) supported that these vehicles enable environmental sustainability and reduce CO₂ emissions and Greenhouse gas (GHS). On the other hand, responses show that sustainability can be a cost burden on SMEs. These findings were also supported by Vaaland and Heide (2007). The author showed that sustainability can be a cost burden as it requires some initial investment.

Responses obtained from theme 5 elaborate on the benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners. These could be in terms of addressing changes in market demand, reducing defective goods, elimination of logistic problems, lesser cost, installing new machinery to

facilitate the new model, and quality maximisation and customer satisfaction. These findings were supported by the research of Lee, Lee and Feick (2001); Birou and Fawcett (1993). Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners can produce positive results on the company's performance, as identified in theme 6. These knowledge-sharing elements were also discovered in the findings of theme 10. Value chain partnerships help companies share knowledge by partnering on specific projects to improve manufacturing plants. Lema and Lema (2012) provided supporting evidence showing that International technology transfer is a multi-dimensional process of transferring technical data and information.

Theme 7 findings show that technologies like SAP, ERP, Excel, and dashboards can support improvements in inventory management and production management. Findings of this theme are also backing up theme 8 responses. SAP or ERP software can positively affect the evaluation of value chain performance. This can be backed up by the findings of Monk and Wagner (2012); Hillman Willis and Hillary Willis-Brown (2002). Using these softwares, organisations can automate and manage core business processes for optimal performance by replacing traditional or manual data handling.

Theme 9 shows that the majority of SMEs have no fine boundaries in levels of the supply chain. Lenny Koh et al. (2007) highlighted these findings and showed that there are no defined supply chain levels or departments as SMEs do not have good profitability to maintain a separate supply chain management team. Theme 11 shows that international collaborations of SMEs with large-scale firms can support them to get new knowledge which can deliver performance improvements. Kaminski, de Oliveira, and Lopes (2008) also identified these findings that support the evidence of theme 12.

Theme 13 identified barriers to this collaboration which could be in terms of managerial issues, communications issues, logistics issues, and financial barriers. These can be supported by the findings of Tenzer, Pudelko, and Harzing (2014); Nieto and Santamaría (2010). Meanwhile, theme 14 shows the positive role of SMEs and micro-businesses on

Pakistan's economy by improving industrial growth, GDP, and remittances (Kongolo, 2010).

5.7 Comparative analysis of sectors

Comparative analysis of different sectors targeted in this study can be conducted. Here, it has been identified that multinationals play an integral role in automobile development to enhance the value chain (Hitt, Li, and Xu, 2016). One of the reasons is that the competition level in the automobile industry is much higher in comparison with other firms, i.e., the petrochemicals industry or a PVC firm. Automobile firms have a burden to maintain a competitive edge while keeping a strong focus on cost reduction. This is the reason that they enter the value chain to evolve as identified from findings and discussion of objective 1.

Objective 2 identifies that Automobile firms are using sustainability practices to avoid lawsuits and penalties. The justification is that consumer demands are evolving to adapt to change, creating a need for companies to shift towards electronic vehicles and hybrid styles. On the other hand, PVC firms are highly in need of reducing their carbon footprint, increasing the recycling of PVC, and incorporating bio-based and recycled raw materials (Cefic, 2023).

The findings obtained in the discussion of question 3 reveal an indirect impact on financial performance. This is due to the fact that knowledge sharing among large-scale companies and SMEs from the automobile and petrochemical industries can face improvements in their financial performance by working in a value chain. The findings of objective 4 confirm that collaboration with large-scale firms is supportive for every SME, whether it be a PVC or Automobile firm. Given the fact that technical assistance can be gained from these companies, as SMEs in their growing stage and they are not good at these technicalities (Nieto and Santamaría, 2010). For instance, a petrochemical firm might need technical assistance from a large-scale PVC firm for material recycling. Whereas, large-scale collaboration can help deliver technical expertise to Automobile SMEs in assembling of a car.

6 Chapter 6: Conclusion

This chapter is designed to create a conclusive overview of the whole research so that the findings attained in the study can be understood. The first section provides an insight into the realisation of research questions where findings obtained against the research questions or objectives developed in the study are concluded. The second section provides insight into research limitations which are providing insights into characteristics of research design and methodology that are limiting the findings of this research. In the third section, research questions developed for future research options are observed and many of these are used to eliminate limitations that occurred in this study.

6.1 Research Question - Realisation

The research aims to explore the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro businesses to facilitate the development of the Pakistani Economy. For the evaluation of this aim qualitative data collection method is targeted in the study. The justification to use this method is that it facilitates insight and in-depth information related to theoretical and human perspectives related to the phenomenon. Furthermore, the qualitative research method was also used in numerous previous studies of supply chain management and value chain which reveals that this seems to be an appropriate methodology for this research. On the other hand, quantitative data collection requires numeric data collection and analysis which can be complex at times and an inappropriate, large-scale survey instrument. Furthermore, the numeric data lacks the factors and comprehensiveness in terms of perceptions, human behaviours and other elements which is the main reason that the quantitative data collection method is not used in this research.

The structured interview questionnaire was designed to conduct in-depth interviews with research participants. The questionnaire is including different sections to gather the demographical and research-related qualitative data from the respondents. These open-ended questions were used to obtain supplementary data, including their feelings,

experiences attitudes and understanding of the participants about the research topic and questions. The sample size targeted in this research is 6 participants for an in-depth interview, where two managers from Pak Suzuki Pvt. Ltd. and two managers from Engro Petrochemical Ltd were targeted. The other two interviewees were managers of MSMEs in Pakistan from both industries, i.e.; petrochemical and automotive. Inclusive of this data collection method to gather primary data, the secondary data collection method was also utilised in the research. This data in the form of previous studies, articles and books were used to gather literature so that data relating to the research question can be gathered. Furthermore, the theoretical background was used to devise an interview questionnaire with the support of this secondary data or literature.

The literature review provides insight into different theories of international trade, Resource-based theory, FDI theory, translation theory and others. These theories conclude that international trade has evolved with the need for different resources required by companies to produce a product or a service. This need ultimately leads companies to go internationally for outsourcing different materials or services needed in the value chain of the firm. Furthermore, the literature shows that the SMEs in Pakistan are influential to play a strong role in the economic development of the country. Thus, these firms collaborate with other firms in international markets to outsource materials or labour from the market. This aspect ultimately influences the productivity of the company in a positive manner which has the potential to transform the company's performance in the industry. Literature reviews show that SMEs' value chain operations are benefiting them to gain a strong position in the industry.

6.1.1 Research Question 1: SMEs' entrance into the Value Chain

The research concludes the evaluation regarding the level when SMEs/Microbusinesses can enter the value chain which was observed using the evaluation of the first research question. SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain when they want to work in collaboration with larger firms to ensure a good final product. In analysis, responses show that SMEs in the garment industry enter the supply chain at earlier stages for the

production of quality products while some other firms enter the value chain occasionally. The literature review provides evidence that occasional long-term procurement arises when customer demand shows an extensive increase and casual procurement strategies could not be used to satisfy these demands. Some other reasons could be in terms of the availability of raw materials in the local market due to some uncertain events. The discussion concludes that the theoretical perspective of the resource-based view shows reasons behind the decisions made by the company to enter value chain operations. They need to enter the value chain to procure raw materials and assemble products in these countries.

Another reason is that the transportation of products or raw materials becomes challenging at times. Thus, SMEs enter international markets which is the main reason that SMEs enter the value chain so that indirect procurement options can be eradicated to get direct procurement of supply chain services. These decisions played a significant role to minimise cost which can ultimately cause a positive influence on the firm's performance and profitability. This cost in an indirect procurement can be in terms of custom duty on imports of raw materials. By entering into the value chain this cost can be eliminated from operations. Furthermore, another reason to enter the value chain could be an attempt to improve product quality. For instance, a response shows that SMEs in the garment industry enter the supply chain at earlier stages for the production of quality products. Therefore, firms may enter the value chain to get different options on the quality of raw materials or to get different types of fabrics. Therefore, inclusive of cost, quality is another main reason to enter the value chain.

The research concludes that these aspects could be considered as strategic needs of the business which means that cost minimisation or quality can lead the business to change its value chain operations. A response shows this can be evidenced by the case of Suzuki Motor Company Japan. Suzuki has set up joint ventures with local Chinese companies as different auto giants or competitors have adopted this strategy. This enables the achievement of a competitive edge for the company as different companies are taking the

utmost benefit of Chinese low-cost labour and innovative technological advancements in China. Therefore, the findings of 1st research question showed that SMEs enter the value chain as per the production, strategic, and occasional needs and to remain competitive in the industry.

6.1.2 Research Question 2: Sustainability practices in microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain

The research concludes the role of sustainability of microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain from the data analysis of 2nd research question. Analysis shows that almost 3 participants have supported the importance of sustainability and it is used by them in their organisations. Previous studies support that SMEs are in their growing phase while struggling for profit generation and trying to develop a strong image in the market. Therefore, their strategic goals are more focused on maximizing productivity, and sales volume while improving the value chain model. This ultimately causes a lack to focus on sustainability goals in SMEs and micro businesses as many of these sustainability strategies require an upfront investment which can cause affordability issues for firms. Affordability issues create barriers to developing these sustainability strategies and it can be a cost burden for these businesses.

In the automotive industry, sustainability is done by adapting to change and companies are shifting towards electronic vehicles and hybrid styles. Previous studies provide evidence that these vehicles enable environmental sustainability as burning too much gasoline in vehicles can be avoided large companies to collaborate with SMEs to raise quality standards and lower costs with the use of these vehicles. The results could be in terms of a reduction in CO₂ emissions from vehicles along with the elimination of Greenhouse gas (GHS) emissions that arise in fuel extraction and refining activities. Other sustainable practices observed in the analysis are reducing wastage and bringing positive changes in material quality. Reduction of wastage has the potential to affect the cost efficiency of the company in a positive manner which is the most common sustainability strategy used by businesses to operate responsibly in the market. The

analysis reveals that majority of the firms have evidenced positive effects of sustainability on organisational performance as these strategies enable firms to develop a strong positive image in the industry.

However, some of the sustainability concerns are quite crucial and firms must have to act responsibly to avoid threatening situations. For instance, environmental sustainability initiatives like dumping waste lawfully are important as companies can even face penalties or lawsuits to act against these sustainability practices. Therefore, appropriate waste management, disposal of hazardous waste etc. are important. Findings show that sustainability practices in this era of modernism, advancement has the potential to affect the competitiveness and survival of SMEs. Some of the vital sustainability practices or initiatives should be designed to address social, technological and economic challenges. Furthermore, effective Management of resources according to RBV and VRIO is important for the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage.

A response also shows that Pak Suzuki does not have a vendor who could have helped develop parts in Pakistan which is the main reason that international vendors and suppliers are contacted. Though the cost can be high, this strategy is used to avoid survival issues in the automotive industry. A response also shows that project delays can cause major issues as can be evidenced by the case of Covid-19 which has caused transportation issues and lockdowns have created issues in the production of materials and different products. Therefore, sustainability is an important attribute however, different market conditions or uncertain events can affect the survival of SMEs. Therefore, the role of internal and external organisational factors is quite important for SMEs and micro businesses aside from sustainability.

Thus, it was concluded that Automobile firms are bringing more sustainable product options meet sustainability. On the other hand, strategies used by PVC companies to attain positive effects on organisational performance are exchanging defective goods to enable customer loyalty. Furthermore, quality is preferred over cost to maximise customer satisfaction which was also supported in the study by Lee, Lee and Feick (2001).

6.1.3 Research Question 3: Benefits shared by value chain participants

The conclusion derived from the data analysis of research question 4 shows the benefits (especially profits) to be shared by value chain participants. The analysis shows that some of the benefits could be in terms of higher product differentiation, improved portfolio, enhanced production and monetary benefits. Product differentiation can be attained by SMEs as value chain participants as material resources or technical skills from different markets nationally and internationally enable the company to differentiate its products from its competitors. Thus, as a value chain participant, the company can attend new opportunities to differentiate current products. Furthermore, a wide range of resources or materials can be accessed as a value chain participant which can enable companies to maximise the quality of their products. The outcomes can be in terms of an improved product portfolio, improved production and higher monetary benefits which can directly influence the financial performance of the company.

Other responses show that benefits could be in terms of outsourcing transportation, warehouse and labour. This ultimately plays a significant role in the company obtaining effective technical assistance and knowledge needed to maximise the financial performance of the company. Responses show that Engro is using third-party logistics so that the operational burden of transportation could be reduced. With effective transportation of raw materials and finished goods in 3PL, business stability and efficiency can be higher which can directly influence profitability and competitive edge of businesses. Inclusive of these benefits of outsourcing logistics, warehousing and supply chain, value chain participants are attaining benefits in terms of knowledge sharing. This aspect has the potential to enable better revenues, lower costs, and higher profit margins, secure safe contracts for a fixed number of years, and improved production and supply.

The findings concludes that all of these results of knowledge sharing could be in terms of positive financial results in terms of improved profitability and higher cost benefits. Given the fact that as a value chain participant companies get valuable alternative options to outsource materials. This ultimately adds an advantage to production and manufacturing

processes. Knowledge sharing is supportive for companies to partner on specific projects and work together to improve manufacturing plants. International technology transfer could be the main domain in this regard as the multi-dimensional process is used to transfer information and technical data. This technology transfer can enable manufacturers to assist their suppliers in the production of different parts so that product differentiation or the overall value of the product can be improved.

These practices are used to meet customer needs and bring changes in products to meet ever-changing customer demands which can play a significant role to transform the long-term performance outcomes of the company. Therefore, the question concludes that outcomes can be in terms of technology sharing, knowledge sharing via partnerships, outsourcing of logistics, warehousing and supply chain. The results of these partnerships can be in terms of higher production, improved product portfolio, improved monetary benefits, cost benefits and other aspects. Thus, outcomes can be in terms of improved financial and non-financial performance of the company.

The research concludes assessment and analysis of data of SMEs and micro-businesses at different supply chain levels. Analysis shows that a company is using tier one vendors and tier two vendors, tier three vendors are used. These are different levels or types of vendors in the Supply chain that are used to acquire materials. Here, Tier 1 vendors are direct suppliers who provide final products and Tier 2 vendors are subcontractors of these tier 1 vendors. Literature shows that the V2V or virtual-to-virtual communication strategy is used to exchange information regarding materials, rates and other elements which can ease supply chain operations. This plays a supporting role to place orders online for raw materials. However, quality-related concerns can arise as a detailed physical examination of materials cannot be performed in this communication process.

A response also shows that SMEs are using downstream and upstream suppliers at different levels of the supply chain. The upstream supply chain revolves around activities used to procure raw materials so that they can be used as input in the manufacturing process. On the other hand, the downstream supply chain is significant in post-

manufacturing activities i.e., product distribution to final customers in the market. Therefore, tier 1, tier 2 and tier 3 vendors, upstream and downstream suppliers in Pakistan. On the other side analysis reveals that in comparison with SMEs and microbusinesses, large firms have proper and defined levels of supply chain and procurement teams. Previous studies show that the majority of SMEs do not have proper supply chain levels or departments as they face cost-related issues to develop and maintain a separate supply chain management team. The reasoning is that it may lead to higher payroll costs. This is the core reason that many SMEs are making one-time investments in SAP ERP systems so that issues can be eliminated. However, the issue is that inclusive of one-time investment, SMEs are also needed to hire experts to work on these systems. The benefits could be higher as returns on investment can be maximised and the company can improve its survival in the market.

However, this fact cannot be neglected that the supply chain management of large-scale and those SMEs cannot be the same. It is observed that large firms are making more efforts in their SCM systems as compared to SMEs. Differences in production levels, scalability and other needs are the main reasons for these differences. Furthermore, the literature review shows that three different levels of the supply chain are strategic, tactical and operational level. In strategic planning, SCM is used in making decisions relating to material sourcing (single or multiple suppliers), location and other decisions made for the achievement of new strengths of a company and to eliminate weaknesses. In the second stage, tactical planning is used to implement these strategies into plans for the achievement of organisational goals. Operational execution is all about introducing tactical plans into actions with different day-to-day tasks. For instance, production schedules are set up and inventory is managed accordingly to achieve plans. This ultimately plays a supporting role in on-time delivery and cost-efficiency of the whole process. However, these three attributes were not utilised by the majority of SMEs.

6.1.4 Research Question 4: Large companies collaborate with SMEs for quality and cost

The findings of question 4 conclude collaboration of large companies with SMEs for quality and cost. Responses show that this collaboration is used by SMEs to gain guidance on best practices used in the industry, to improve distribution network quality and for cost minimisation. This type of knowledge transfer or collaboration can include technical, managerial and operational knowledge, leadership skills and other attributes. Findings of previous studies show that large-scale business collaboration can directly affect the production scale of SMEs. The reason is that this could be utilised for knowledge sharing and experience of these companies which can play a significant role to enable on-time product delivery.

A type of collaboration mentioned in responses is regarding OEM or Original Equipment manufacturing. This term is used in the automotive and IT industries, where a company produces a product which is resold or rebranded by another firm. Here, large automobile companies use knowledge sharing as technical information related to tools or material are shared with SMEs reselling their products. This collaboration ultimately plays a significant role to optimise the operations of SMEs and maximise profits thereby reducing costs. One of the examples in this regard can be evidenced by the case of Pak Suzuki. The company has introduced a supplier uplifting programme for the purpose of knowledge transfer to supplier firms and most of these are SMEs. Pakistan Suzuki Motors have collaborated with Indonesia Thailand and Taiwan Suzuki corp. These are mainly devoted to knowledge transfer for performance improvements which can ultimately ease the achievement of KPI benchmarks. Moreover, a collaboration between IMC and Pak Suzuki was done and the responses show that technological achievement was the main reason for these collaborations.

These advancements are in terms of robots for welding so that manual work could be replaced by robots. On the other hand, findings show that a PVC-producing company has also collaborated with SGS and ICI. Informal communication or discussions carried out

by these partners related to safety, practices, sales and production are supportive to eliminate PVC industry issues. A McKinsey collaboration was also evidenced in the responses which were done to improve supply chain and HR processes. By collaborating with McKinsey, SMEs can evaluate their internal and external environment and new strategies could be developed according to these environmental challenges so that performance improvements can be attained. Therefore, findings show that SMEs are working in collaboration with large-scale businesses according to their operational or strategic needs. No willingness issues are observed in the analysis and all of these collaborations are done to improve product quality and other operations.

At the end of the analysis, responses conclude the effects of the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs and their effects on the economic development of Pakistan. Some response shows that SMEs Growth is linked with Engro and Engro Polymer's role is higher in understanding issues and hardships of SMEs. A response shows that value chain activities have a positive impact on the economy of Pakistan. Whereas, previous studies provide evidence that value chain maturity in Pakistan can directly affect businesses and the economic development of the country. Furthermore, to enable uninterrupted growth, value chain challenges should be reduced in order to enable the economic growth of Pakistan. SMEs do play a significant role in employment creation in Pakistan. Therefore, it is important that policies should be eased for SMEs so that more SMEs can come into the market for GDP and employment growth in Pakistan. A response also shows that the profitability of SMEs can directly affect industrial growth, GDP growth and economic stability. The companies are also bringing remittances in terms of dollar payments to the country which can positively impact the economic growth of Pakistan.

6.2 Research Question - Limitations

In this section, the limitations of the research are discussed which have the potential to affect the research scope, findings and other elements. These limitations raised related to the research scope and research methodology.

6.2.1 Limitations in the Research scope

In this research, Pakistan was targeted as the country is in its developing stage. Whereas, Researchers belong to the US which is a developed market. As one of the focuses to select a research topic is attributed to the selection of a country that is in its developing stage, the US was not targeted in this research. The wider research scope of targeting different developing countries is excluded from the scope of this research. The justification is that this wide scope to conduct research in different developing countries relating to SMEs' value chains could require a huge amount of time. Further, a high amount of investment was also needed in this regard as visiting different countries and acquiring data or conducting interviews in different countries might require huge transportation costs and other costs. The limitation is that funds cannot be accessed as loans or other sources to invest in this regard. This is the main reason to target Pakistan's economy and SMEs in the industry while excluding other developing countries from the research scope. Furthermore, for DBA/Doctoral research, it is more appropriate to select a single country for the purpose of data collection. Another limitation to making this decision is that limited time was available to accumulate data and work on the completion of this research. This is the main reason to determine this exclusion criterion of omitting different developing countries from the scope of this research. Therefore, time and fund limitations were the main reason to select this topic and market.

6.2.2 Limitations in research methodology

There are limitations in the data collection method. Due to time limitations, only the qualitative data collection method was used in this research, whereas quantitative data is added to the exclusion criteria of the study. Byrne and Humble (2007) showed that mixed methodology or combining the use of quantitative data with qualitative data can ensure trustworthy outcomes of the research as limitations of each method can be covered by the other one. However, as limited time was available in the research this methodology or use of a survey questionnaire along with interviews was avoided so that time delays

might not arise. Roulston and Shelton (2015) showed that the use of qualitative data might cause personal biases and other ethical considerations in the research.

Personal biases are considered as unintentional incorrect judgments which might cause biases in the analysis as findings interpreted could be different from actual ones (Kvale, 1994). This ethical consideration is important and these issues should be avoided as research quality can be influenced by these elements in a negative manner. The reasoning is that qualitative data interpretation requires personal observations of the researcher and his/her interest might cause biases in data interpretation at times. Therefore, to overcome these limitations, it is preferable to use the qualitative method of data collection and analysis in combination with quantitative data. Since the quantitative techniques of data analysis are performed by using Excel, SPSS, descriptive statistics, regression and other analytical tools have the potency to eliminate any sort of personal biases in analysis and craft unbiased findings and discussion of the research. Hence, the limitation of this study was raised as a subject to time horizon and research methodology of keeping stuck with the use of qualitative data. By deploying mixed-method for data collection and analytical techniques, the deductive approach can be primarily adopted for this study in combination with the inductive as the inductive approach was applied in previous studies. For applying the deductive approach in primary data collection and analysis as preceding research papers have directed to focus on certain topics/issues. The hypotheses could be developed and scientifically tested to produce unbiased and further rationalised research findings.

Moreover, the sample size and sampling technique can be considered another limitation of this research. The sample size was comprised of 6 participants for an in-depth interview. The study included two managers from Pak Suzuki Pvt. Ltd. and two managers from Engro Petrochemical Ltd as participants of the study. Moreover, further two interviewees were managers affiliated with MSMEs in Pakistan from both industries, i.e., petrochemical and automotive. According to Bernard (2013), 10 to 20 well-informed individuals are sufficient to reveal findings regarding research objectives. Therefore, it is

suggested that future research options should focus on the maximisation of research participants and up to 10 participants should be contacted for research interviews. Convenience sampling is subject to selection bias and an inability to comprehend the true essence of the target population (Etikan, Musa and Alkassim, 2016, pp. 3).

This can ultimately support the company to get a deep insight into the research topic. Furthermore, as participants are from different industries, it was difficult to interpret appropriate findings relating to one industry and for each industry findings obtained were not sufficient enough to prove anything about a particular industry. For instance, research findings are providing some insight relating to the automotive industry; however, in the case of the Petrochemical industry, it lacks depth. Another reason for this limitation is that previous studies show some insights relating to the automotive industry and few studies were produced on the petrochemical industry. Therefore, these limitations should be eliminated in future by keeping more focused research on the petrochemical industry and excluding other fields from the research criteria.

6.3 Future Research options generated

In this section different future research options are produced according to the limitations of the study. Two different research options are discussed in this section, where one is produced to enable the elimination of limitations raised in this research relating to research methodology. Whereas, a second research option is produced to conduct this research on the same topic to exclude the scope limitations of this research.

6.3.1 First future research option

One of the research options could be terms of using the same research topic to conduct a study in Pakistan while eliminating limitations raised regarding the research methodology in this study. The findings of this study are providing some insight relating to the automotive industry; whereas, there is a lack of details relating to the Petrochemical industry. Whereas, previous studies are also revealing limited insights relating to the petrochemical industry on the value creation and supply chain. Therefore, in future, it is

suggested that research should solely target this industry while eliminating research methodology limitations raised in this study. It is suggested that with the use of the current research topic, research should be conducted in the petrochemical industry with the use of mixed methodology which is the main weakness of this research. In this instance, the deductive approach will be targeted and hypotheses should be developed on the basis of 4 research questions targeted in this study. To explore these hypotheses, quantitative research methodology should be used. In this instance, a survey questionnaire could be designed to utilise in future research studies on employees of the petrochemical industry. In this manner, issues regarding the lack of literature on the Petrochemical industry can be eliminated. However, challenging situations can arise in terms of obtaining sufficient respondents required to collect data. These challenges will be eliminated with the use of the snowball sampling method. With the use of this sampling method, current respondents of the research can play a supporting role by referring others who can provide quality information needed to accomplish the research aim. Another challenge can be in terms of valid statistical analysis of data obtained from respondents. For this purpose, reliability statistics will be performed on quantitative data to evaluate dispersion in the data set which can interpret reliability. Therefore, by combining these attributes valid statistical analysis can be performed in the study.

One of the future research option is that the sample size for the survey questionnaire should be almost 50-70. The justification is that Memon et al. (2020) suggested a sample of 100 participants to conduct surveys in large-scale firms. Therefore, 50-70 participants can be appropriate to gather data from SMEs in the petrochemical industry. On the other hand, qualitative data collection of interviews can be conducted by managers of these firms targeted, from where employees are sourced for the survey questionnaire. As Bernard (2013) suggested that appropriate sample size of interviews could be between 10 to 20 well-informed individuals which is sufficient to reveal findings regarding research objectives. Therefore, in future research up to 10 participants from targeted firms should be contacted for research interviews.

Combining the analysis of both of these methods, future research could offer more better and in-depth insight relating to this current research topic. Both quantitative and qualitative findings can be used to support each other for the evaluation of the research hypothesis. In this way, ethical considerations of personal biases can be avoided. This could be considered as a most appropriate future research option that could be used to avoid limitations in research methodology, sample size and approach used in previous studies. Thus, findings in future research options with the use of this strategy can be more reliable, realistic and trustworthy. This can ultimately provide in-depth insight into the value chain and supply chain of SMEs in the petrochemical industry which can be considered a core research question in future.

6.3.2 Second research option

The research targets the evaluation of the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro businesses in Pakistan. Pakistan is targeted as a country as it is in its developing stage. As only one developing country was targeted that shows the limited scope of this research. It is suggested that future research options should focus on the selection of different developing countries. Some of these countries could include Bangladesh, Indonesia, South Africa, Sri Lanka and others countries. It is suggested that in future research personal evaluation should be made by the researcher relating to observing the countries from where data can be easily accumulated by conducting interviews. Countries which can be accessed easily should be only included in the inclusion criteria of the study. In this instance, it is suggested that friends, family, and colleagues should be contacted by the researcher to observe the list of countries that can be referenced by them. However, ethical considerations will be developed regarding Social Desirability Bias which has the potential to affect the tendency of respondents to interpret responses that are socially acceptable to others, even if they consider them untruthful. Therefore, awareness will be offered to respondents regarding these types of biases so that they can offer truthful responses rather than offering socially acceptable ones.

A similar research methodology used in this research can be applied to conduct interviews from each country. The reason is that number of countries and participants will be higher as at least 5 countries will be targeted in the study. Thus, only qualitative data collection methods should be used while avoiding quantitative data collection methods as the use of mixed methodology will need more time. Recommended Sample size should be up to 3-5 participants from each country. Here, video conferencing options like Skype or other technologies could be used to conduct interviews with participants. This strategy can play a significant role to avoid issues raised regarding budget/ fund limitations as each country can be accessed to conduct interviews and transportation costs can be eliminated. In this manner, budget limitations can be eradicated as there will be no need for transportation investment. Furthermore, time limitations can be avoided by conducting interviews through video conferencing and the management of data through this tool can also enable time-saving. Therefore, future research questions could be based on the evaluation of the value chain and supply chain in SMEs of developing countries.

6.4 Practical implications of the study

SMEs, micro businesses and large scale firms can effectively apply the findings of this study in their operations. These findings can be applied by SMEs to enter value chain operations. For instance, the research identifies needs and factors in terms of cost reduction, quality improvements, procurement needs, and other factors. On the other hand, the findings observed against the second research question show that sustainability can be a cost burden on microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain. SMEs can benefit from the literature cited in this research which shows that sustainability can be adopted by shifting from electric to hybrid style, reducing waste, CO₂ emissions, and others. Petrochemical firms are recommended to gain technical assistance from large-scale PVC firms in the material recycling process to cater to sustainability needs. One of the findings shows that sustainability requires investment, and SMEs can search for measures that require less investment to adopt affordable sustainability practices. SMEs can easily use

these strategies to attain the benefits as value chain participants from the findings of this research.

One of the implications is that they can use it to attain product differentiation to satisfy the needs of their customers. For instance, as value chain participants, they can gain benefits as material resources or technical skills from national and international markets. Some other benefits could be in terms of improved portfolio, enhanced production, and monetary benefits. Pakistani SMEs can even implicate findings of Global Value Chains (GVCs) theory which shows that international production sharing can be used by breaking down production into activities and tasks. Question 4 identified how large companies' collaboration with SMEs and MBs. SMEs can implicate these findings to attain guidance on best practices used in the industry. Through the help of it Pakistani SMEs can improve their distribution network quality and minimise costs for better output of the firm. Technological achievement could be one of the biggest benefits in this case, and SMEs can evolve their manual working process to robotic ones.

This reveals the application of technology transfer theory on practical grounds as firms in the value chain and working in collaboration with large firms can attain technical knowledge to improve. On the other hand, Michael Porter's Value Chain could be the best implication on practical grounds in SMEs. Here, firms can apply five sets of activities from the theory to enable top-notch supply chain operations. Thus, overall findings of the research can contribute to positive social change in Pakistan. With the help of it, SMEs can make significant improvements in their value chain, advancing positivity in employment levels, poverty, and economic development aspects of Pakistan.

6.5 Research Contributions

Contribution to knowledge: The research contributes the elimination of limitations identified in previous studies, significantly improving this study's literature gap. Nag (2017); Mirza and Manarvi (2011) have produced findings related to technological advancements in the automobile sector. Whereas, Khurshid and Chaudary (2010); Ahmad, Akram, and Amin (2017) have identified factors affecting the production in the

petrochemicals industry. None of these studies contribute an in-depth analysis on the value chain of automobile and petrochemical sector. This study offers robust findings by providing an in-depth evaluation of both sectors. As a value chain participant, SMEs can improve procurement strategies, cost reduction, technological advancements and knowledge transfer. All of them can contribute positive changes in performance of SMEs.

Strategic contributions from Policymakers: The findings highlight several areas requiring contributions from policymakers as they can initiate projects to foster innovation and encourage technological advancements in SMEs and micro businesses. Some of these favourable policies can include; reducing regulatory burdens, simplifying the business registration process, and creating ease in micro financing. Moreover, the findings show that most large-scale firms are unwilling to collaborate with SMEs as value chain participants. For this purpose, the government can bring new strategic initiatives in their Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs). In PPPs, SMEs collaboration can be set up as a mandatory principle for Public sector firms. Thereby, these collaborations can easily enhance knowledge transfer, technology transfer, and other advancements in value chain of SMEs.

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8 Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview Guide

Appendix 2: Summary of participant's response

Appendix 3: Sample - Qualitative Data Analysis (Example Formation of themes)

Appendix 4: Participant information sheet

Appendix 5: Consent form

8.1 Appendix 1: Interview Guide

Greetings

1. Introduce yourself to the participant:

My name is Qandeel Bhatti. I am currently enrolled in University of West Scotland (UWS). I am conducting this research as a mandatory part of Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) Program. This research is focused on role of value chain and supply chain of SMEs and Microbusinesses in economic development of Pakistan.

2. Explain the process of the interview:

The online one-on-one interview of approximately 40-50 mins was conducted via Zoom Meeting. This interview is divided into 4 sections, where the first part is designed to explore the demographics of respondents as well as background information relating to education and professional life. In sections 2, 3 and 4, research questions and objectives are targeted so that these can be presented through interview questions.

Your participation and opinions are highly appreciated.

3. Audio Recording permission and instructions:

Audio recording was done during the interview if you will provide consent over this. The purpose is that recording necessary details will create ease in analysing data collected. However, the information provided was kept confidential and data will not be misused. This will also assure the application of the Data Protection Act 1998 in the whole data collection process.

4. Reassure confidentiality, privacy and safety of data:

All information collected was secured and no identifiable information was used to upkeep the privacy and confidentiality of participants. The data collected will not be used for any other purpose except for this research.

Section One – Demographical profile of participants	
1.	What is your name?
2.	Specify the name of your present employer or organisation?
3.	What is your job position in the organisation?
4.	Please specify the highest education level you have received.
5.	What are some of the responsibilities of your job position?
6.	Discuss some of your skills?
1.	What is your experience level in your current organization? Less than 1 year More than 1 year More than 5 years
2.	What is your age? 25 years or less 25-35 years 35-40 years 40 years to more

3. What is your role in the organization? Strategic Tactical Operational
4. What is your function in the organization? Marketing Operations HRM/D Finance
5. What type of products does your organization offer? Automobiles Petrochemicals Specify for others _____

Section Two- RO1 and RO2
Entrance of SMEs/Micro businesses in the value chain Sustainability practices in microbusinesses and SMEs in the value chain
1. When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?
2. What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?
3. What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?

4. What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalize their value chain?

5. In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organizational performance?

6. What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?

Section Three- RO3 and RO4

Profit sharing and other benefits shared by value chain participants?

Assessing the reasons leading to large companies willingness to collaborate with SMEs and microbusinesses

7. What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?

8. How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?

9. In your organization and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?

10. Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?

11. What benefits are possessed by the organization in the utilization of this software?

12. What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?

13. Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?

14. How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)

Section Four- RO4

Assessing the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.

15. Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors?
How?

16. Has your organization ever collaborated with a large company?
What were the reasons?

17. Discuss how these collaborations have affected organizational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?

18. What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms?
Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?

19. In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?

----- End of Interview-----

8.2 Appendix 2: Summary of participant's response

8.2.1 Participant 1

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.1.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Engro Polymer and chemicals limited			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	Area Sales Manager			
		Specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			

		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	Sales of PVC in Sindh and Baluchistan Bidding in the open market and negotiating with the global traders Meeting annual sales target			
		Discuss some of your skills?	SPSS, SAP, MS office			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	More than 1 year and less than five years.			
		Age group	25-35			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Strategic and tactical			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Marketing			

		What type of products your organisation offers?	Petrochemicals			
8.2.1.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	<p>SMEs enter the value chain during the need for operational activities, maintenance and transportation of products.</p> <p>Occasionally for procurement of material.</p> <p>At Engro, SMEs and Microbusinesses come after dealers</p>	Negative	SMEs entrance into the value chain	

3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Factors include the Low cost of material Scarcity or no other supplier In Engro, SMEs are customers because SMEs work on credit	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	Specialised services with a low-cost advantage Meeting each KPI and continuous monitoring is an important part of adding any partner to Engro outsource transportation	Positive		

		What are the factors which lead SMEs to globalise their value chain?	They look for business and expansion providing organisations with low-cost advantages and better service.	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	<p>The demand for one of the leading products PVC was more than it was produced initially. The import has its issues besides disruptions.</p> <p>The company hold command as the leading producer and supplier of PVC but to meet market demand effectively additional facility was established this led to a loss of command power</p>	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	

			<p>but equilibrium was maintained</p> <p>Besides these, its value of Financial involvement</p> <p>Quality is preferred over cost</p> <p>Exchange of defective goods lead to loyal customers</p>			
		<p>What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?</p>	<p>There are no sustainable practices. microbusinesses and SMEs are only adding cost advantage to the value chain</p>	<p>Negative</p>	<p>Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs</p>	

		Does sustainability affect SMEs and micro businesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	They are not interested in sustainable practices as they require investment, they have issues with affordability and so few Practices are not aligned with the concept of sustainability	Negative		
		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	SMEs can challenge the existence of larger enterprises in the market if they start considering sustainable practices	Positive		
8.2.1.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participants?	Engro have 3PL Model (third-party logistics) Outsourced partners are SMEs including services for	Positive	Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners	

			<p>transportation, warehouse and labour.</p> <p>So SMEs get affiliation, technical assistance and knowledge while gaining financial numbers</p>			
5	<p>Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?</p>	<p>How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?</p>	<p>SMEs as value chain participants gain consistent support / enhance skills secure safe contracts for a fixed number of years</p> <p>They are trained for maintaining the highest possible safety standards, working with SOPs</p> <p>Technical assistance</p>	Positive	<p>Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners</p>	

			<p>Helping them improve production and supply</p> <p>Minimise wastage</p> <p>Global initiatives for Skills development</p> <p>Pills for farming</p> <p>garden hose cable doors and windows</p> <p>all good practices</p>			
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	<p>SAP and MS Excel</p> <p>Customised dashboards</p>	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	

		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	Dealing with SMEs, ledger balances Buying history Graphs and performances Sales tax invoices Technical literature	Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Single platform Centralised procurement Anticipate building AI tools for forecasting Transportation services scenarios and situational analysis	Positive		

		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	No demarcations Blended system of SMEs Excel-based Lack of real-time reporting	Negative		Response was more focused on software and technology
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	SMEs do not have any software for business purposes and no demarcations of levels of supply chain	Negative		
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Formal sessions Demos Testing of finished products through mobile labs Usually through pamphlets	Positive	knowledge transfer	

			Knowledge transfer is formal and informal both via newsletters, on-site visits, presentation sessions			
8.2.1.4 Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	distribution network quality, lowering their cost, guidance for best practices	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	

		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	<p>PVC issue</p> <p>SGS and ICI collaboration</p> <p>Partnership for betterment through discussions related to safety, practices, sales and production</p>	Positive	Benefit of partnership	
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	<p>Technical knowledge cost benefits and securing improved quality</p> <p>INEOS- Indonesian company PVC samples improved and approved</p> <p>This gave a boost to the cable sector</p>	Neutral		

		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	Yes INEOS provided technical evaluation for PVC because there are very limited supplier	Positive		
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	Engro polymer SMEs as customer SMEs Growth is linked with engro 60 industries are related to the construction sector All activities of the value chain have a positive impact on the economy of Pakistan	Positive	Impact on economy of a country	

8.2.2 Participant 2

S.No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.2.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Pak Suzuki Motor Company Limited.			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	Manager in production engineering department			
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	Operational Maintaining and adjusting Dyes/assembly lines according to product			

			specifications or changes in model			
		Discuss some of your skills?	Ms office SAP			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	More than 5 years			
		Age group	35-40 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Operational			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Operations management			
		What type of products does your organisation offer?	Automobiles			

8.2.2.2 Section Two

2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	SMEs enter the value chain at the production stage or planning/production of start a new model. All significant strategic steps and processes are approved or endorsed by SMC Japan Suzuki Motor Company Japan Assembling of all parts Minimizing import of CKD	Positive	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	
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3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	<p>Importing CKD and assembling</p> <p>Cost – US Dollars</p> <p>At the time option left is to reduce profit margins</p> <p>Price fluctuations</p> <p>To produce any part locally all standards should be conformed</p> <p>feasibility</p> <p>specifications</p> <p>material</p> <p>quality</p> <p>inspection department</p> <p>same standards</p> <p>quality gates are passed then we send that particular part to SMC Japan</p>	positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
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		<p>What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?</p>	<p>If local lacks tools but have the expertise, the company help them identify the required tools</p> <p>come into the agreement with them to help them out, facilitate them to you know, actually it's like a win-win situation</p>	<p>Positive</p>		
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		<p>What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?</p>	<p>dynamics of the automobile industry</p> <p>assembling cars on petrol, diesel, natural gas</p> <p>moving towards hybrid and electronic vehicles</p> <p>terms of adaptability, these SMEs are sort of trying to send their workers to different countries like Japan, Thailand, where there is you know, a good manufacturing conducive environment</p> <p>learn, they sort of improve their skill set</p> <p>knowledge back</p>	Positive		
		<p>In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?</p>	<p>Value Chain Operations</p> <p>SAPs into the equation</p>	positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	

			<p>More vendors bring in more SMEs to facilitate you to do the job.</p> <p>Boost organisational performance besides</p> <p>install new machinery to facilitate the new model</p> <p>reliant on a few of the partners that we were working with who were outside Pakistan.</p> <p>good technological advancement</p> <p>e</p> <p>already working with organisation performance</p> <p>cost</p> <p>the local company doing the same job at lesser costs in the</p>			
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			same amount of time with no load, no logistic problems			
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	adaptability to change is important a shift towards electronic vehicles and hybrid style	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	Change and evolution bring out a positive impact and an ability to match up with the speed of the industry.	Positive		

		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	If Pak Suzuki had a vendor who could have helped develop those parts in Pakistan, we could have survived in the sedan sector with the automotive industry import everything raises the cost mid-sized sedan the parts localised keep the price of the car or the cost of the car	Positive		
8.2.2.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	SMEs trickle-down effect on finances and performance of an organisation and an SME or microbusiness	Positive	Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners	

5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Better revenues, lower costs, and better profit margins. better presence Engineer from SMEs Can come and explain machine, tools and other requirements for localisation of new part	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	SAP	Positive	Use of Technology in value chain management	

		<p>Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?</p>	<p>Engineer from SMEs</p> <p>Can come and explain machine, tools and other requirements for localisation of new part Knowledge sharing is helpful</p> <p>if one local production is achieved same can be done for MNCs</p> <p>they're also catching up with the industry</p> <p>Machines</p> <p>Tools</p> <p>Investment and benefits</p>	<p>Positive</p>		
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		<p>What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?</p>	<p>the value chain has its own KPIs</p> <p>monitor</p> <p>value chain performance</p> <p>Information system</p> <p>Maintaining documentation</p> <p>transactions</p> <p>day-to-day work</p> <p>manufacturing</p> <p>production of cars</p> <p>capital nature of assets,</p> <p>procuring</p> <p>raw material</p>		<p>Benefits of technology</p>	
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		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	<p>Choosing a procurement agent or vendor</p> <p>Bidding</p> <p>Capabilities and delivery time</p> <p>Material and quality cost</p> <p>Warehousing</p> <p>Facility</p> <p>All depends on the size of an organisation</p>			
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	three levels			
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain	knowledge be transferred between the supply		Knowledge transfer	

		Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	normal practice do it through documents predominantly verbal is just informal but the formal document is there and authentic			
8.2.2.4 Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Increase the quality and minimise the cost To produce that particular part on a mass level. cost reduction product on time there are no delivery delays		Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	

		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	PSMC collaborate with Indonesia Thailand and Taiwan Suzuki crop Collaborate for review Feasibility Benefits include The clarity in instructions and directions		Benefit of partnership	
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	positioning your product, your brand collaborations are important			
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	Language barrier			
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations	There are major benefits for Allied industries		Impact on the economy of a country	

		of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	Employment creation Overall economy			
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8.2.3 Participant 3

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.3.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Sunplastic			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	Production manager			
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			

		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	Producing and managing inventory fulfilling customer demands delivery time and process			
		Discuss some of your skills?	management of people coved disruptions raw material scarcity			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	More than 5 years			
		Age group	35-40 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Operational.			
		What is your function in the organisation?	operations and finance			

		What type of products your organisation offers?	garment hangers			
8.2.3.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	SMEs enter the supply chain at earlier stages of the garment industry Through working collaboratively together with larger firms for ensuring a good final product	Negative	SMEs' entrance into a value chain	
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Quality and cost play the biggest factor	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change	

		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	the garment manufacturers, specific to our industry specialised firm in SME it's just a machine or something off-the-shelf sort of thing that you can make material and colour	Positive	their value chain operations	
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	quality premium for it export ensure regular supply	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Risk factor evaluation Crude oil price affects raw material By-products of crude oil, PB is mainly imported into Pakistan.	Neutral	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	Respondent talks about issues and difficult situations instead directly

						targeting the question.
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	Sustainable practices and technological advancement lead to reduce wastage and improved quality of material	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	International contracts with exporters natural gas or diesel generation the regular power supply of electricity which is costly at times	Positive		

		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	SMEs have their challenges. Such as global policies co2 emission levels or reduction in co2 co2 emission levels or reduction in co2 natural gas generator	Neutral		
8.2.3.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	Delivery time is precise Low risk profitability for both SMEs and large firms	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge	streamlining the process cost advantage knowledge sharing	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	

	SMEs and Microbusinesses?	sharing and other perks of the value chain?	collaboration where we are putting our input into the design cost adjustment material and colour adjustment act to a requirement			
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	No technology Manual handling Along with Paper—tabular-- ticketing system in database software	Neutral	Use of technology in value chain management	

		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	<p>Database software---supplier perspective--- production number – which is later adjusted with real numbers and things (supervisors and workers)</p> <p>Helps to see numbers and keep track of production and management</p> <p>Inventory to keep orders supply process smooth</p>	Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	<p>Things are aligned well with production and costing</p> <p>The supervisor makes actual changes to the actual input of raw material cost quantity and production</p> <p>Our machinery supports outputting all the data</p> <p>Units produced per minute and raw material qty.</p>	Positive		

		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	No distinctive supply chain levels were adopted by SMEs but documented lines of responsibility such as buying/purchasing/production	Negative		
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	The manufacturing process and microbusinesses focused on the production and generating revenue Large-scale firms have larger benefits e.g. proper workforce, expansion plans, different priorities Small scale have to work from scratch for maintaining a business, surviving and processing things	Positive		
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will	The major mode of Knowledge transfer among SC partners is Verbal communication	Negative	knowledge transfer	

		knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Lack of documentation because of the nature of the tasks involved			
8.2.3.4 Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Quality shouldn't be effected by collaboration cost or price and methods may differ but quality should be consistent	Neutral	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	

		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Exporters Technical drawings Better designing Mould adjustments Delegated a percentage of worker export designs It brings value	Positive	Benefit of partnership	
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	International clients provide detailed technical drawings Locals give sketches and simple CAD drawings with minimum details	Positive		

		<p>What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?</p>	<p>Having contracts with European countries there are various barrier</p> <p>Export licencing issues</p> <p>Regulatory requirements (banks and other agencies are involved)</p>			
		<p>In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?</p>	<p>It supports the economy of Pakistan by several means including the impact of Dollar payments are bringing remittances to the country</p> <p>There is an absence of any middle man bias leading to beneficial and transparent business</p> <p>Transactions and trading is done in a specified timeframe</p>		<p>Impact on the economy of a country</p>	

8.2.4 Participant 4

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.4.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Engro polymer and chemicals limited			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	Manager project planning and contracts			
		specify the highest education level you have received	Bachelors			

		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project planning Software scheduling Firmware Engineering knowledge documentation Analysing bids Stakeholder Contractors 			
		Discuss some of your skills?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> utilise all sorts of project management tools validity phase feasible bidding stage 			

			currently two major projects, handling two expansion			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	more than five years			
		Age group	35-40 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Strategic and operational			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Operations			
		What type of products does your organisation offer?	Petrochemicals			
8.2.4.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	SMEs enter in the value chain as per	positive	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	

	businesses enter the value chain?		<p>needs of large organisations</p> <p>For services or materials or supply chain services, products or materials</p> <p>direct procurements</p> <p>small contractors for civil works and minor mechanical works</p>			
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	<p>centralised procurement function</p> <p>Engro Corporation consistently looking forward to improving efficiency</p>	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	

		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	Smooth operations and functions of an organisation	Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	Effective financial and operational processes and functions Expansion plans and revenue besides efficient production	Positive		

		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	<p>multiple changes in the value chain</p> <p>procurement of raw materials</p> <p>centralisation of all processes through SAP</p> <p>problems, factors leading to inefficiencies</p> <p>accumulate all data into a single source</p> <p>improve that analytical capacity</p>	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	-			Not responded

		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	Stability is important after you start stabilizing your routine operational activities and performance	Positive		
		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	Freight charges, exchange rates, contractors Manpower All are essentially part of value chain and helps in managing projects' Small business performance is importantly liked with large organisations	Neutral	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	

8.2.4.3 Section Three

4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	<p>stable business for longer periods</p> <p>Blanket Purchase Orders</p> <p>blanket service order</p> <p>I set up a list of prices or rates with my contractor for specific services</p> <p>bidding</p> <p>agreement in</p> <p>improves my service times</p> <p>billing</p> <p>actual quantity</p> <p>improves my supply chain</p> <p>our customers</p>	Positive	<p>Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners</p>	
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			plant and consumer essentially ensures that the SME has definite revenue for that specific service of that specific item			
5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Value chain participants SMEs adds an advantage to production and manufacturing processes	Positive		
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	ERP software	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	

		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	Yes, it maintains the dissemination and flow of accurate information throughout the organisation	Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Software ERP or SAP allows From requisite to buyers' bid processes to be well-versed and streamlined Financial analysis is very convenient	Positive		

		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	raw materials, chemicals mechanical and then buyers for electrical items bidding RFQs Purchase Requisition mapped out in the software and in our documents	Positive		
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	Vendors and processes are sorted No value chain or supply disruptions Direct impact on the operational	Positive	Levels of supply chain	Discusses supply chain levels of larger firms instead those of SMEs

			performance of an organisation			
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	<p>verbal transfer of knowledge is the most effective</p> <p>documentation via SAP is a must</p> <p>Supply chain participants</p> <p>complete software</p> <p>documentary evidence</p> <p>strictly documented</p>	Positive	Knowledge transfer among various partners	

8.2.4.4 Section Four

6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	<p>of quality and cost factors</p> <p>set of standards for the provision of services or specific times</p> <p>SMEs instil quality standards in their promises</p> <p>bulk</p> <p>lowers the cost for each shipment</p>	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
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		<p>Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?</p>	<p>collaborated with other PVC manufacturers, other VCM manufacturer</p> <p>improve our technology</p> <p>improve our processes, the efficiency</p> <p>collaborated with EOS technology</p> <p>in the US as with Sasol which is a VCM</p> <p>Saudi Arabia</p> <p>McKinsey</p>	<p>Positive</p>		
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			overall processes for the supply chain and HR.			
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	technology improvement, improvement of process efficiency and improvement of capacities and capabilities	Positive		
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	technology and specific collaboration contracts symposiums and conferences help knowledge sharing instead of getting to bosses and asking them directly	Positive	Barriers to knowledge transfer and collaboration	

		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	SMEs are less acknowledged Engro understand the issues and hardships of SMEs	Neutral	Impact of the value chain on the economy of a country	
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8.2.5 Participant 5

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.5.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Pak Suzuki motor company			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	assistant manager procurement supply chain			
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	Design and coordinate with the			

			SAP consultation team. SAP implementation procurement and cost management cost breakups			
		Discuss some of your skills?	costing, procurement Excel			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	More than one year experience			
		Age group	Age group 25-35			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Operational role			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Finance supply chain			

		What type of products your organisation offers?	Automobiles			
8.2.5.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	The specific quantity of the parts Parts to different vendors. Limited capacity	Positive	SMEs entrance in value chain	

3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SME's roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	<p>Continuous increase in Cost and prices</p> <p>Lack of technical knowledge of material, processes, inventory planning</p> <p>Cost reduction</p> <p>process optimisation and</p> <p>management layout design and processes</p> <p>inventory facility</p> <p>5S activities</p> <p>Financial issues</p> <p>Low mark-up on loans from SCB</p>	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
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		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	pricing matter technically strong the inventory on time	Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	Technical assistance	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Local production of the front mirror Challenges overcome Financial and technological Joint ventures – helped Suzuki motors (shared investment) and local manufacturers	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	

		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	Sustainable practices are to help run business efficiently and effectively diversification key suppliers started manufacturing parts for MNCs like Indus and KIA	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	They effect positively	Positive		

		<p>The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?</p>	<p>Small or big vendors (SMEs) are equally important b/c of each stops production, shipping cost assembling and customer (everything will be challenged)</p> <p>Efficient survival is important</p> <p>If one business stops—the production line is effected—project delays</p> <p>e.g. semiconductor shortage in Malaysia during covid impacted</p> <p>several MNCs as well</p>	positive		
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8.2.5.3 Section Three

4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	<p>Coved — pandemic lead to 2 months of closure</p> <p>After 8 9 months sales record broke</p> <p>warehouses store imported inventory for approximately two to three months</p> <p>started air shipments to help smooth production lines at every cost</p> <p>Planning and launching projects</p>	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	
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5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	<p>making an SME or a value chain partner with that we have some long-term business relationship with the SME which is a benefit in the form that we are not going to do business with other vendors to design the part from scratch</p> <p>Asked them to produce that part at a high production level so that they can be used in other models.</p> <p>Value Chain Partner or SMEs to procure that nut or that fastener from that vendor</p>	Positive		
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			<p>SMEs Lack basic business / financial bank knowledge</p> <p>Cost-benefit</p> <p>Check for periodic custom duties or SROs</p> <p>reduce cost duties on raw materials and effective procurement</p>			
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	Excel and SAP previous was ERP	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	
		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	Controlling and quality matters	Positive		

		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Material controlling and finance controlling SAP with HR management processes	Positive		
		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	V2V partners tier one vendors and tier two vendors tier three partners small shops/ small manufacturers Transportation partners are V2V They help us ensure ease of delivery in a feasible timeframe	positive	Level of supply chain	

		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	Large firms have proper and defined levels of supply chain procurement team which is finalizing the contracts, pricing contracts procurement is physically done through vendors	neutral		
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Technology advancement Proper documentation through SAP SRM portal (supplier relationship management portal)		Knowledge transfer between supply chain partners	

8.2.5.4 Section Four

6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Vendor's management department And Cost Management Department		Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Quality and price SME-producing shock absorbers for all MNCs Good Quality and price cost advantage			

		<p>Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?</p>	<p>large inventory</p> <p>technical teams are also good at technicalities</p> <p>radiators or shock absorbers or silencer assembly</p> <p>the cost difference between the large enterprises</p> <p>technical knowledge</p> <p>overhead</p> <p>corporate structure</p> <p>their product complexity</p>			
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		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	Finding and managing warehouses is challenging			
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	Organisational profitability and growth have a direct impact on GDP		Impact on the economy of a country	

8.2.6 Participant 6

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.6.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Loads Limited (SME)			
		What is your job position in the organisation?	Assistant Manager Production			
		specify the highest education level you have received	Master			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position	Production, assembly line, Supply material			

			Reduce downtime Audit documentation Management of team including labour			
		Discuss some of your skills?	Technical and managerial			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?	More than 5 years			
		Age group	25-35			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Operational			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Operations			
		What type of products does your organisation offer?	Automobile spare parts			

			OEM (original equipment maker) Radiators Sheet metal parts Exhaust systems			
8.2.6.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	The product is designed by an engineer value stream analysis	Neutral	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs' roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Advancing with the market needs and analysing changes in market demand Production dept	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	

		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	monetary benefit competitive advantage sustainability costing	positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	Vendors adjust act to the need of a customer Material handling Costing approvals Value chain mapping	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	primary goal maximised profits, higher profits improve sales improve value chain		Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	SMEs do not have many sustainability practices		Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	

		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	The practices which are best to avoid are part value chain such as waste management, disposal of hazardous waste etc.			
		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	In Pakistan considers that market sustainability does not play any significant role in the survival of SMEs or microbusinesses			
8.2.6.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	<p>Monetary benefits</p> <p>Enhanced production</p> <p>Kenya company collar</p> <p>cost saving</p> <p>product differentiation</p> <p>portfolio - improved</p>		Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners	

5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Kenyan companies Aluminium labour importing that machinery from Kenya will make cheaper and higher quality radiators		Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	

		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	<p>vendor of OEM</p> <p>contract any business</p> <p>technical knowledge to the operational knowledge</p> <p>all the information they provide to us</p> <p>products</p> <p>outsource</p> <p>share the knowledge</p> <p>this will affect us financially because</p> <p>sharing the finances</p> <p>sharing the profit with them</p>		Use of technology in value chain management	
		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	No technology to monitor the value chain			

		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?			Role of SAP in supply chain management	
		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?				
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?			Level of the supply chain in SMEs	
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Verbally mostly and document where needed problem arises discrepancies Quantities get mixed. Miscommunication.		Knowledge transfer	

8.2.6.4 Section Four

6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	<p>knowledge sharing between the large SMEs and small-scale businesses</p> <p>OEM give the business to small manufacturing enterprises</p> <p>transfer knowledge</p> <p>The tools and material information to SMEs.</p> <p>technical training to the small scale businesses</p> <p>larger scale businesses are very much interested in uplifting the quality of products in SMEs</p> <p>For quality information should be transferred to SMEs by larger firms to help optimise their operations and maximise</p>		Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
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			<p>the profits by reducing the cost.</p> <p>supplier uplifting programme by PSMC</p> <p>technical</p> <p>managerial and</p> <p>operational knowledge</p> <p>SMEs can enhance production capability</p> <p>improve our quality</p> <p>leadership skills, managerial skills,</p>			
		<p>Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?</p>				

		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	International level training but pandemic affected the collaboration shifted to online			
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	<p>managerial issues</p> <p>communications issues</p> <p>logistics issues</p> <p>financial barrier is the most important</p> <p>SMEs have to allocate the budget for the improvement</p> <p>They provide information, technical assistance, and operational assistance so definitely it will require the cost it will require investment to improve the facility at SMEs</p>		The willingness of larger firms in eliminating barriers	

			Larger firms only provide technical knowledge SMEs need investment to execute collaboration and implement new changes			
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	if business and production are increased more business comes to the industries and will affect the economy of the country		Impact on the economy of a country	

8.2.7 Participant 7

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		

8.2.7.1 Section One

1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Loads Limited SME			
		What is your job position in the organisation?				
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position				
		Discuss some of your skills?	Creating proposal documents, analysing bids, handling stakeholders and Contractors			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?				
		Age group	25-35 years			

		What is your role in the organisation?	Operational			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Supply chain			
		What type of products your organisation offers?	OEM and Spare parts			
8.2.7.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	SMEs becomes part of value chain during the production and distribution activities	positive	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	With evolving production and distribution activities	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	

		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	Feasible Logistics.	Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	Financial benefits and availability in shorter time	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Procurement and other Operational activities are smooth, faster and quick	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	-			Not responded
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	Environmental sustainability measures are considered	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	

		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	Sustainability is adopted but practiced in limited capacity	Neutral		
8.2.7.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	Financial and market penetration	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	
5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses ?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Limited to few technological tools other than communication tools	Positive		

		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	Limited technologies.	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	
		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?		Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Very important in keeping records updated and accurate	Positive		
		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	2 tier procurement	Positive		
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	Yes, they can be different. SMEs use it in production usually intermixed levels of supply chain.	Positive	Levels of supply chain	Discusses supply chain levels of larger firms instead those of SMEs

		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Limited to ensure smooth activities such as prod techniques, supplier information and raw material PIS	Positive	Knowledge transfer among various partners	
8.2.7.4 Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Positive for outsourcing value activities	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	

		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Yes collaborated with large firm. Positive for Time efficiency, supplier and distribution system	Positive		
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	Training and development, managerial, operational and financial benefits	Positive		
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	Large organisations have detailed processes including approvals, management and transactions. Offer less for products and services with high market competition	Positive	Barriers to knowledge transfer and collaboration	
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of	Positive impact	positive	Positive impact on the economy of a country	

		SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?				
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8.2.8 Participant 8

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
8.2.8.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Loads Limited			
		What is your job position in the organisation?				
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position				

		Discuss some of your skills?	SPSS, meeting sales targets, finalising quotations, meeting with clients, establishing business relationships			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?				
		Age group	25-35 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Strategic and operational activities			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Marketing			
		What type of products does your organisation offer?	OEM and Spare parts			
8.2.8.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	Raw material procurement, production and distribution activities	positive	SMEs' entrance into	

	businesses enter the value chain?				the value chain	
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Taxes duties WHTaxes conversion rates fluctuations profit margins.	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?		Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?	Financial benefits and availability in shorter time.	Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Ease of access and availability. Low cost alternatives	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on	

		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	Environmental sustainability very limited capacity		organisational performance	Not responded
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	It can positively affect value chain operations.	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	Microbusinesses don't have much funds to invest in sustainability measures.	Neutral		
8.2.8.3 Section Three						
4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	Financial and market share, local connections and relationships, ease in involved regulatory processes	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing	

5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Very little	Positive	with value chain partners	
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	Limited to few communication tools	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	
		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?		Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Beneficial but not implemented due to cost and lack of trained personals	Positive		
		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	One level either procurement, or production , lacks clarity	Positive		

		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?	Yes, they can be different. SMEs use it in production usually intermixed levels of supply chain.	Positive	Levels of supply chain	Discuss es supply chain levels of larger firms instead those of SMEs
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Limited to joint ventures and little R&D	Positive	Knowledge transfer among various partners	

8.2.8.4 Section Four

6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Collaborations are done.	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Collaborating with SMEs can bring innovative solutions, unique expertise.	Positive		
		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	Collaborating for specialised products to the value chain, contributing to overall competitiveness.	Positive		

		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	Large organisations often have complex and global supply chains. Offer less for products and services with high market competition	Positive	Barriers to knowledge transfer and collaboration	
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	SMEs are significant contributors to job creation and economic development. Engaging with SMEs in the value chain can have positive social and economic impacts on local communities.	positive	Positive impact on the economy of a country	

8.2.9 Participant 9

S. No		Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		
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	Research Questions		Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral	Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
8.2.9.1 Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Sunplastic			
		What is your job position in the organisation?				
		specify the highest education level you have received	Masters			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position				
		Discuss some of your skills?	Managerial skills to manage a team.			

			Maintaining supply and production during raw material procurement and finalising quotations			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?				
		Age group	25-35 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Strategic and operational activities			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Marketing			
		What type of products your organisation offers?	Distribution and wholesale of PVC			
8.2.9.2 Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	Raw material procurement (supplier), production, research and development,	positive	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	

	businesses enter the value chain?					
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Changes in value chain is done for growth and globalisation of business.	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	Local existence and rapport, SMEs are flexible and cost effective. SMEs have expertise and understanding of local market, regulations, policies and needs of community.	Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?		Positive		
		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Cost affectivity, better compliance and same quality product is developed in less time	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on	

		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	SMEs have responsible attitude towards environment.		organisational performance	Not responded
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	Positive	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	
		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	With limited resources and scope, SMEs are considerate of minimising waste	Neutral		

8.2.9.3 Section Three

4	What benefits are offered to the supply chain partners esp. financial?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	As value chain partners SMEs can gain visibility and successful partnership is considered a ground-breaking achievement if recognised by larger enterprises. Larger enterprises have multiple benefits such as cost cutting, high quality products in less cost and time, customised solutions to meet specific customer needs, competitive advantage in markets.	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	
5	Why large companies are willing to collaborate with SMEs and Microbusinesses?	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Collaborative events, training and development and opportunity for SMEs to surpass other local competitors in market	Positive		
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	Excel is used.	Positive	Use of technology in	

		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	For communication, inventory and invoicing etc	Positive	value chain management	
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Basic excel worksheets and manual entries	Positive		
		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	2 to 3 at max	Positive		
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?		Positive	Levels of supply chain	Discuss es supply chain levels of larger firms instead those of SMEs

		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)	Research for design development, seminars and training sessions, discussion	Positive	Knowledge transfer among various partners	
8.2.9.4 Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Large scale collaboration for cost benefits.	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Cost benefits and enhanced overall performance	Positive		

		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	Identification and better market presence	Positive		
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	SMEs are easily overshadowed by larger companies. SMEs seek acknowledgement and recognition for their collaboration to add value to their portfolio. This will also hinder the protection of intellectual property (if applicable)	Positive	Barriers to knowledge transfer and collaboration	
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the economic development of Pakistan?	SMEs are significant contributors to job creation and economic development. Engaging with SMEs in the value chain can have positive social and economic impacts on local communities.	positive	Positive impact on the economy of a country	

8.2.10 Participant 10

S. No	Research Questions	Interview Questions	Responses (Summary)		Emerging Themes	Unpredicted Responses
			Main Pointers	Negative, positive or neutral		
Section One						
1	Interviewee Background and demographics	Specify name of present employer or organisation	Plastochem Corporation			
		What is your job position in the organisation?				
		specify the highest education level you have received	Bachelors			
		What are some of the responsibilities of your job position				

		Discuss some of your skills?	Project management, supervising procurement, machinery and maintenance			
		What is your experience level in your current organisation?				
		Age group	25-35 years			
		What is your role in the organisation?	Strategic and operational activities			
		What is your function in the organisation?	Procurement			
		What type of products does your organisation offer?	Distribution and wholesale of PVC and polymers besides other packaging material			
Section Two						
2	At what level could SMEs/Micro	When do SMEs/Micro businesses enter the value chain?	Microbusiness – can be a part of value chain at any stage from planning to customer	positive	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	

	businesses enter the value chain?					
3	How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs roles in the value chain?	What are the factors which triggered your firm to bring changes in these value chain operations?	Microbusiness despite all setbacks are more flexible and spontaneous as compared to larger organisations.	Positive	Needs and factors leading micro businesses and SMEs to change their value chain operations	
		What are the needs of these businesses which lead them to use the value chain?	The time efficiency and finances are few of the important factors	Positive		
		What are the factors which leads SMEs to globalise their value chain?		Positive		

		In your firm, how were value chain operations changed and how have these affected organisational performance?	Cost effectiveness, time, low budget but high quality products – heightens organisational performance by all means (e.g. if they can import single batch from other country, via MB and SMEs they can have multiple)	Positive	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	
		What sustainable practices are adopted by microbusinesses and SMEs in their value chain?	Microbusiness are inclined towards environmental wellbeing			Not responded
		Does sustainability affect SMEs and microbusinesses as well as their value chain operations positively or negatively?	Positive	Positive	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness	

		The sustainability of microbusinesses has the potential to affect the survival of the firm in the market. Why do you think this is the case?	Sustainable measures are used to safeguard environment and responsible consumption of resources	Neutral	ess and SMEs	
Section Three						
4	How will the benefits (especially profits) be shared by value chains participants?	What benefits can be obtained by SMEs as a value chain participant?	Financial benefits and market penetration / recognition	Positive	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	

5	To assess and analyse the data of SMEs and micro-businesses at different supply chain levels.	How can value chain participants be affected financially by knowledge sharing and other perks of the value chain?	Microbusinesses- Financial benefits and experiential learning. Large enterprises- cost effectiveness, compliance and local businesses have better regulatory and market indulgence	Positive		
		In your organisation and industry which technology is used to monitor value chain performance?	Digital technological advancements including cloud computing are integrated at very low scale and should be expanded further to create more opportunities for efficient handling of value chain	Positive	Use of technology in value chain management	

		Do you think that this software is beneficial for supply chain participants?	Digital technological advancements including cloud computing are integrated at very low scale and should be expanded further to create more opportunities for efficient handling of value chain	Positive		
		What benefits are possessed by the organisation in the utilisation of this software?	Digital technological advancements including cloud computing are integrated at very low scale and should be expanded further to create more opportunities for efficient handling of value chain	Positive		

		What are the different supply chain levels adopted by SMEs and micro-businesses in Pakistan?	no fine boundaries	Positive		
		Do you think that supply chain levels adopted by large firms differ in SMEs? How supply chain management is benefiting these firms?		Positive	Levels of supply chain	Discusses supply chain levels of larger firms instead those of SMEs
		How will knowledge be transferred between Supply Chain Participants (e.g. Will knowledge be transferred	The knowledge sharing and profit sharing are limited as larger enterprises can easily dominate microbusinesses. In few cases-- no recognition at all	Positive	Knowledge transfer among various partners	

		verbally/informally or via documentation/formally?)				
Section Four						
6	To assess the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs in order to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.	Do you think that collaboration of large-scale businesses with SMEs might affect SME products in terms of quality and cost factors? How?	Quality products customised according to local market demands, in lower budget	Positive	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	
		Has your organisation ever collaborated with a large company? What were the reasons?	Quality products customised according to local market demands, in lower budget	Positive		

		Discuss how these collaborations have affected organisational output? Or objectives targeted behind this collaboration were achieved or not?	Exposure and familiarity with complex structures, norms and processes of the larger organisation. Opportunity to work with recognised organisation. Market competitiveness – improved	Positive		
		What were the barriers faced in collaboration with large firms? Have they showed willingness to eliminate these barriers?	MBs may face challenges in accessing new markets without the support of a larger partner. Large enterprises may control distribution channels, limiting the MB ability to reach a broader customer base.	Positive	Barriers to knowledge transfer and collaboration	
		In your opinion, how can the value chain and supply chain operations of SMEs affect the	Foreign collaborations will bring high revenue In case of local collaborations, the profitability margins are	positive	Positive impact on the economy	

		economic development of Pakistan?	enhanced remarkably, cost per unit is decreased and increased financial performance will support the industry and eventually Pakistan.		of a country	
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8.3 Appendix 3: Qualitative Data Analysis (Example Formation of themes)

Column1	Theme 1	Theme 2	Theme 3	Theme 4	Theme 5	Theme 6	Theme 7	Theme 8	Theme 9	Theme 10	Theme 11	Theme 12	Theme 13	Theme 14
Macro themes	SMEs' entrance into the value chain	Factor and needs of organisations leading to change in their value chain	Impact of changes in Value Chain on organisational performance	Sustainable practices in Microbusiness and SMEs	Benefits of SMEs as value chain Partners	Knowledge sharing and profit sharing with value chain partners	Use of technology in value chain management	Role of ERP in supply chain management	Levels of supply chain	Knowledge transfer among value chain partners	Collaborations of larger firms with SMEs and Microbusinesses	Benefits of collaboration with larger organisations	Barriers faced in collaboration	Role of SMEs and micro-business on the economy of Pakistan
Respondent 1	SMEs enter the value chain during the need for	They look for business and expansion providing	The demand for one of the leading products PVC was	There are no sustainable practices. microbusinesses	Engro have 3PL Model (third-party logistics) Outsourc	SMEs as value chain participants gain	SAP and MS Excel Customised dashbo	Dealing with SMEs, ledger balances Buying history	SMEs do not have any software for busine	Formal sessions Demos Testing of finishe	Distribution network quality, lowering their	Technical knowledge cost benefits and securing improved	Yes INEOS provided technical evaluation for PVC because	Engro polymer SMEs as customer SMEs Growth is linked with

operation al activities, maintena nce and transport ation of products. Occasion ally for procure ment of material. At Engro, SMEs and Microbus inesses come after dealers	organisa tions with low- cost advanta ges and better service. Specialis ed services with a low-cost advanta ge Meeting each KPI and continuo us monitori ng is an	more than it was produced initially. The import has its issues besides disruptio ns. The company hold comman d as the leading producer and supplier of PVC	and SMEs are only adding cost advantag e to the value chain. They are not intereste d in sustainab le practices as they require investme nt, they have issues	ed partners are SMEs including services for transport ation, warehou se and labour. So SMEs get affiliation, technical assistanc e and knowledg e while gaining	consist ent support / enhanc e skills secure contrac ts for a fixed number of years They are trained for maintai ning the highest	ards. Single platfor m Central ised procure ment Anticip ate buildin g AI tools for forecas ting Transp ortation service s scenari os and	Graphs and performanc es Sales tax invoices Technical literature.	ss purpos es and no demarc ations of levels of supply chain	d product s through mobile labs Usually through pamphl ets Knowle dge transfer is formal and informa l both via newslet ters, on-site	cost, guidan ce for best practic es. PVC issue SGS and ICI collabo ration Partner ship for betterm ent through discuss ions related to safety,	quality INEOS- Indonesi an company PVC samples improved and approved This gave a boost to the cable sector	there are very limited supplier	engro 60 industries are related to the constructi on sector All activities of the value chain have a positive impact on the economy of Pakistan
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		important part of adding any partner to Engro outsourcing transportation. Factors include the Low cost of material Scarcity or no other supplier In Engro, SMEs	but to meet market demand effectively additional facility was established this led to a loss of command power but equilibrium was maintained Besides these, its	with affordability and so few Practices are not aligned with the concept of sustainability. SMEs can challenge the existence of larger enterprises in the market if they start	financial numbers	possible safety standards, working with SOPs Technical assistance Helping them improve production and supply Minimize wastage	situational analysis			visits, presentation sessions	practices, sales and production.			
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		are custome rs because SMEs work on credit	value of Financial involvem ent Quality is preferred over cost Exchang e of defective goods lead to loyal customer s	consideri ng sustainab le practices		e Global initiativ es for Skills develo pment Pills for farming garden hose cable doors and window s all good practic es								
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Respondent 2	SMEs enter the value chain at the production stage or planning/production of start a new model. All significant strategic steps and processes are approved	Importing CKD and assembling Cost – US Dollars At the time option left is to reduce profit margins Price fluctuations To produce any part locally all	Value Chain Operations SAPs into the equation More vendors bring in more SMEs to facilitate the job. Boost organisational performance besides install	adaptability to change is important a shift towards electronic vehicles and hybrid style. Change and evolution bring out a positive impact and an ability to match up with the speed of	SMEs trickle-down effect on finances and performance of an organisation and an SME or microbusiness	Better revenues, lower costs, and better profit margins. Better presence Engine from SMEs Can come and explain machine, tools	SAP. Engineer from SMEs Can come and explain machine, tools and other requirements for localisation of new part Knowledge sharing	Choosing a procurement agent or vendor Bidding Capabilities and delivery time Material and quality cost Warehousing Facility All depends on the size of an organisation	three levels	knowledge be transferred between the supply normal practice do it through documents predominantly verbal is just informal	Increase the quality and minimize the cost To produce that particular part on a mass level. cost reduction product on time there are no	positioning your product, your brand collaborations are important	Language barrier	There are major benefits for Allied industries Employment creation Overall economy
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	<p>or endorsed by SMC Japan Suzuki Motor Company Japan Assembly of all parts Minimizing import of CKD</p>	<p>standards should be conformed feasibility specifications material quality inspection department same standards quality gates are passed</p>	<p>new machinery to facilitate the new model reliant on a few of the partners that we were working with who were outside Pakistan. good technological advancement</p>	<p>the industry. If Pakistan Suzuki had a vendor who could have helped develop those parts in Pakistan, we could have survived in the sedan sector with the automoti</p>		<p>and other requirements for localization of new parts</p>	<p>is helpful if one local product ion is achieved same can be done for MNCs they're also catching up with the industry Machin</p>	<p>the value chain has its own KPIs monitor value chain performance Information system Maintaining documentation transactions day-to-day work manufacturing production of cars capital</p>		<p>document is there and authentic</p>	<p>delivery delays. PSMC collaborate with Indonesia Thailand and Taiwan Suzuki collaborate for review Feasibility Benefits</p>			
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		then we send that particular part to SMC Japan. If local lacks tools but have the expertise, the company help them identify the required tools come into the	e already working with organisation performance cost the local company doing the same job at lesser costs in the same amount of time with no load, no logistic problems	ve industry import everything raises the cost mid-sized sedan the parts localised keep the price of the car or the cost of the car			es Tools Investment and benefits	nature of assets, procuring raw material			include The clarity in instructions and directions			
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		agreement with them to help them out, facilitate them to you know, actually it's like a win-win situation. dynamics of the automobile industry assembling cars on												
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		petrol, diesel, natural gas moving towards hybrid and electroni c vehicles terms of adaptabil ity, these SMEs are sort of trying to send their workers to different												
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		countries like Japan, Thailand , where there is you know, a good manufacturing conducive environment learn, they sort of improve their skill set												
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		knowled ge back												
Respo ndent 3	SMEs enter the supply chain at earlier stages of the garment industry Through working collaboratively together with larger firms for ensuring a good	Quality and cost play the biggest factor. the garment manufacturers, specific to our industry specialised firm in SME it's just a machine or something off-the-	Risk factor evaluation Crude oil price affects raw material By-products of crude oil, PB is mainly imported into Pakistan.	Delivery time is precise Low risk profitability for both SMEs and large firms. Sustainable practices and technological advancement lead to reduce wastage	streamlining the process cost advantage knowledge sharing collaboration where we are putting our input into the design cost adjustment material	Things are aligned well with product ion and costing The supervisor makes actual changes to the actual input of raw material cost	No technology Manual handling Along with Paper — tabular-ticketing system in database software	Database software--- supplier perspective --- production number – which is later adjusted with real numbers and things (supervisor s and workers) Helps to see numbers and keep	No distinctive supply chain levels were adopted by SMEs but documented lines of responsibility such buying/purcha	The major of Knowledge transfer among SC partners is Verbal communication Lack of documentation because	Quality should n't be effected by collaboration cost or price and method differ but quality should be consistent. Export	International clients provide detailed technical drawings Locals give sketches and simple CAD drawings with minimum details	Having contracts with European countries there are various barrier Export licencing issues Regulatory requirements (banks and other agencies are involved)	It supports the economy of Pakistan by several means including the impact of Dollar payments are bringing remittance s to the country There is an absence of any

	final product	shelf sort of thing that you can make material and colour. quality premium for it export ensure regular supply.		and improved quality of material. International contracts with exporters natural gas or diesel generation the regular power supply of electricity which is costly at times.	and colour adjustment act to a requirement	quantity and production Our machinery supports outputting all the data Units produced per minute and raw material qty.		track of production and management Inventory to keep orders supply process smooth.	sing/pr oduction	e of the nature of the tasks involved	ers Technical drawings Better designing Mould adjustments Delegated a percentage of worker exports designs It brings value			middle man bias leading to beneficial and transparent business Transactions and trading is done in a specified timeframe
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				SMEs have their challenge s. Such as global policies co2 emission levels or reduction in co2 co2 emission levels or reduction in co2 natural gas generator .										
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Respondent 4	SMEs enter in the value chain as per needs of large organisations For services or materials or supply chain services, products or materials direct procurements	Centralised procurement function Engro Corporation consistently looking forward to improving efficiency. Smooth operations and functions of an	multiple changes in the value chain procurement of raw materials centralisation of all processes through SAP problems, factors leading to inefficiencies accumulate all	Freight charges, exchange rates, contractors Manpower All are essentially part of value chain and helps in managing projects' Small business performance is	Value chain participants SMEs adds an advantage to production and manufacturing processes	stable business for longer periods Blanket Purchase Orders blanket service order I set up a list of prices or rates with my contractor for specific services	ERP software	Yes, it maintains the dissemination and flow of accurate information throughout the organisation. Software ERP or SAP allows From requisite to buyers' bid processes to be well-versed and streamlined Financial analysis is	Vendors and processes are sorted No value chain or supply disruptions Direct impact on operational performance of an organisation	verbal transfer of knowledge is the most effective documentation via SAP is a must Supply chain participants complete software	quality and cost factors set of standards for the provision of service or specific times SMEs instill quality standards in their promises	Collaborated with other PVC manufacturers, other VCM manufacturer improve our technology improve our processes, the efficiency collaborated with	Technology and specific collaboration contracts symposiums and conferences help knowledge sharing instead of getting to bosses and asking them directly	SMEs are less acknowledged Engro understand the issues and hardships of SMEs
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	small contractors for civil works and minor mechanical works	organisation. Effective financial and operational processes and functions Expansion plans and revenue besides efficient production	data into a single source improve that analytical capacity	importantly liked with large organisations. Stability is important after you start stabilizing your routine operational activities and performance		bidding agreement in improves my service times billing actual quantity improves my supply chain our customers plant and consumer		very convenient		documentary evidence strictly documented	bulk lowers the cost for each shipment	technology in the US as with Sasol which is a VCM Saudi Arabia McKinsey overall processes for the supply chain and HR.		
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						essentially ensures that the SME has definite revenue for that specific service of that specific item.								
Respondent 5	The specific quantity of the parts Parts to	Continuous increase in Cost and prices	Local production of the front mirror Challenge	Sustainable practices are to help run business	Covid — pandemic lead to 2 months of closure	making an SME or a value chain partner	Material controlling and finance controll	Excel and SAP previous was ERP. Controlling	V2V partners tier one vendors and	Technology advancement Proper docum	Vendor's management department	large inventory technical teams are also good at	Finding and managing warehouses is	Organisational profitability and growth have a

	different vendors. Limited capacity	Lack of technical knowledge of material, processes, inventory planning Cost reduction process optimization and management layout design and processes	es overcome Financial and technological Joint ventures –helped Suzuki motors (shared investment) and local manufacturers	efficiently and effectively diversified key suppliers started manufacturing parts for MNCs like Indus and KIA. Small or big vendors (SMEs) are equally important	After 8 9 months sales record broke warehouses store imported inventory for approximately two to three months started air shipment to help smooth production lines at every	with that we have some long-term business relationship with the SME which is a benefit in the form that we are not going to do	ing SAP with HR management processes	and quality matters.	tier two vendor tier three partner shops/ small manufacturers Transportation partners are V2V They help us ensure ease of deliver	entation through SAP SRM portal (supplier relationship management portal	And Cost Management/ Department/ Quality and price SME-producing shock absorbers for all MNCs Good Quality and price cost	technicalities radiators or shock absorbers or silencer assembly the cost difference between the large enterprises technical knowledge overhead corporate structure	challenging	direct impact on GDP
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	inventory facility 5S activities Financial issues Low mark-up on loans from SCB. pricing matter technical ly strong the inventory on time. Technica l assistance"		b/c of each stops production, shipping cost assembling and customer (everything will be challenged) Efficient survival is important If one business stops—the	cost Planning and launching projects	busine ss with other vendors to design the part from scratch Asked them to produce that part at a high production level so that they can be used in			y in a feasible timeframe. Large firms have proper and defined levels of supply chain procurement team which is finalizing the		advantage	their product complexity		
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				<p>production line is effected —project delays e.g. semiconductor shortage in Malaysia during covered impacted several MNCs as well.</p>		<p>other models . Value Chain Partner or SMEs to procure that nut or that fastener from that vendor SMEs Lack basic business / financi</p>			<p>contracts, pricing contracts procurement is physically done through vendors</p>					
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						al bank knowle dge Cost- benefit Check for periodi c custom duties or SROs reduce cost duties on raw materia ls and effectiv e								
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						procurement								
Respondent 6	The product is designed by an engineer value stream analysis	Vendors adjust to the need of a customer Material handling Costing approvals Value chain mapping . monetary benefit competitive	primary goal maximised profits, higher profits improve sales improve value chain	SMEs do not have many sustainability practices. The practices which are best to avoid are part value chain such as waste management, disposal of	Monetary benefits Enhanced production Kenya company collar cost saving product differentiation portfolio - improved	Kenyan companies Aluminium labour importing machinery from Kenya will make cheaper and higher quality radiators	vendor of OEM contract any business technical knowledge to the operational knowledge all the information they provide		tier one supplier of all the OEMs in Pakistan We don't have such levels in our company No strategy and tactics	Verbally mostly and document where needed problem arises discrepancies Quantities get mixed. Miscommunication.	knowledge sharing between the large SMEs and small-scale businesses OEM give the business to small manufacturing	International level training	managerial issues communications issues logistics issues financial barrier is the most important SMEs have to allocate the budget for the improvement They	if business and production are increased more business comes to the industries and will affect the economy of the country

		<p>advantage sustainability costing. Advancing with the market needs and analysing changes in market demand Production dept</p>		<p>hazardous waste etc. In Pakistan considers that market sustainability does not play any significant role in the survival of SMEs or microbusinesses</p>			<p>to us products outsource share the knowledge this will affect us financially because sharing the finances sharing the</p>		<p>in SMEs Only operations. Most SMEs are working here for the downstream and upstream suppliers.</p>		<p>enterprises transfer knowledge The tools and material information to SMEs. technical training to the small scale businesses larger</p>	<p>provide information, technical assistance, and operational assistance so definitely it will require the cost it will require investment to improve the facility at SMEs Larger</p>	
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							profit with them				scale busine sses are very much interest ed in upliftin g the quality of product s in SMEs For quality informa tion should be transfer		firms only provide technical knowledg e SMEs need investmen t to execute collaborati on and implemen t new changes	
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											red to SMEs by larger firms to help optimis e their operati ons and maximi se the profits by reducin g the cost. supplie r upliftin g			
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											progr mme by PSMC technic al manag erial and operati onal knowle dge SMEs can enhanc e product ion capabili ty improv			
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											our quality leadership skills, managerial skills,			
Respondent 7	SMEs becomes part of value chain during the production and distribution activities	Feasible Logistics , Financial benefits and availability in shorter time	Procurement and other Operational activities are smooth, faster and quick	Environmental sustainability measures are considered but practiced in limited capacity	Financial and market penetration	Limited	Limited to few technological tools other than communication tools	Very important in keeping records updated and accurate	2 tier procurement, production , usually intermixed	Limited to ensure smooth activities such as production techniques, supplier information and	Positive for outsourcing value activities , Time efficiency, supplier and distribu	but pandemic	Large organisations have detailed processes including approvals , management and transactions. Offer less for products	Positive impact

										raw material IPIS	tion system		and services with high market competitio n	
Resp onde nt 8	Raw material procure ment, productio n and distributi on activities	Financial benefits and availabili ty in shorter time (taxes duties WHTaxe s conversi on rates fluctuatio ns profit margins)	Ease of access and availabilit y. Low cost alternativ es	Environm ental sustainab ility very limited capacity	Financial and market share, local connectio ns and relations hips, ease in involved regulator y processe s	Very little	Limited to few commu nicatio n tools	Beneficial but not implemente d due to cost and lack of trained personals	One level either procure ment, or product ion , lacks clarity	Limited to joint venture s and little R&D	Better underst anding of niche market, supplie r and distribu tion system	affected the collabora tion	Large organisati ons often have complex and global supply chains. Offer less for products and services with high market	SMEs are significant contributor s to job creation and economic developm ent. Engaging with SMEs in the value chain can have positive

													competition	social and economic impacts on local communities.
Respondent 9	Raw material procurement (supplier), production, research and development,	SMEs have expertise and understanding of local market, regulations, policies and needs of community. Local existenc	Cost effectivity, better compliance and same quality product is developed in less time	SMEs have responsible attitude towards environment. With limited resources and scope, SMEs are considerate of	As value chain partners SMEs can gain visibility and successful partnership is considered a ground-breaking achievement	collaborative events, training and development and opportunity for SMEs to surpass other local compet	For communication, inventory and invoicing etc	Basic excel worksheets and manual entries	2 to 3 at max	Research for design development, seminars and training sessions, discussion	Cost benefits and enhanced overall performance		SMEs are easily overshadowed by larger companies. SMEs seek acknowledgement and recognition for their collaboration to add value to	SMEs are significant contributors to job creation and economic development. Engaging with SMEs in the value chain can have positive

		<p>e and rapport, SMEs are flexible and cost effective.</p>		<p>minimising waste</p>	<p>ent if recognised by larger enterprises. Larger enterprises have multiple benefits such as cost cutting, high quality products in less cost and time, customised</p>	<p>itors in market</p>							<p>their portfolio. This will also hinder the protection of intellectual property (if applicable)</p>	<p>social and economic impacts on local communities.</p>
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					solutions to meet specific customer needs, competitive advantage in markets.									
Respondent 10	Microbusiness – can be a part of value chain at any stage from planning to customer	Microbusiness despite all setbacks are more flexible and spontaneous as compared to	Cost effectiveness, time, low budget but high quality products – heightens organisat	Microbusiness are inclined towards environmental wellbeing and take measures to safeguard	Financial benefits and market penetration / recognition	Microbusinesses- Financial benefits and experiential learning. Large	Digital technological advancements including cloud computing are integrated at very	If integrated effectively it will help in promoting transparency and traceability in the value chain.	no fine boundaries	The knowledge sharing and profit sharing are limited as larger enterpri	Quality products customised according to local market demands, in	Exposure and familiarity with complex structures, norms and processes of the larger organisat	MBs may face challenges in accessing new markets without the support of a larger partner.	Foreign collaborations will bring high revenue. In case of local collaborations, the profitability margins are

		larger organisations. The time efficiency and finances are few of the important factors	ional performance by all means (e.g. if they can import single batch from other country, via MB and SMEs they can have multiple)	environment and responsible consumption of resources		enterprises-cost effectiveness, compliance and local businesses have better regulatory and market indulgence	low scale and should be expanded further to create more opportunities for efficient handling of value chain			ses can easily dominate microbusinesses. In few cases--no recognition at all	lower budget	ion. Opportunity to work with recognised organisation. Market competitiveness – improved	Large enterprises may control distribution channels, limiting the MB ability to reach a broader customer base.	enhanced remarkably, cost per unit is decreased and increased financial performance will support the industry and eventually Pakistan.
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8.4 Appendix 4: Participant information sheet (PIS)

Name of department: School of Business and Creative Studies, University of West of Scotland

Title of the study: How can the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro-businesses facilitate the development of the economy of Pakistan?

Introduction

My name is Qandeel Bhatti and I am a doctoral student at the University of West of Scotland. I am undertaking this research as part of my degree. For further information, you are more than welcome to contact my supervisor. His details are listed in the end.

What is the purpose of this research?

This research is intended to explore the ways how the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and Microbusinesses facilitate the development of the economy of Pakistan. The research is aimed to examine at what level could SMEs or microbusinesses enter the value chain? How sustainable are the microbusinesses and SMEs' role in the value chain? How will benefits (especially profits) be shared by value chains participants? Furthermore, it will also assess and analyse the data of SMEs and micro-businesses at different supply chain levels. Along with the willingness of large companies to collaborate with SMEs to raise the quality standards and lower the costs.

Do you have to take part?

Your participation is thoroughly voluntary. You have a right to deny or refuse to respond to any of the questions. You are free to withdraw from the research at any point in time without any consequences. A consent form is attached with this information sheet. If you are willing to participate, please read, and go on with the questionnaire. The collaboration and completion of the interview process will be considered as your consent to use the provided data for research in this project.

What will you do in the project?

As you confirm your participation, you are anticipated to take a part in the interview which is planned to explore different approaches and perspectives involved in developing the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro-businesses. Moreover, the interview questions you will be asked to respond to are designed to get insight related to different theories and their practical implications based on your experiences. You are requested to confirm your availability in the next 2 weeks. We will require 40-60 minutes for the interview session considering your feasibility.

Why have you been invited to take part?

This research project is focused on the key strategic and operational areas of SMEs and large enterprises. The participants recruited are from strategic and top managerial levels of an organisation. The inclusion criteria included the two major sectors automobile and petrochemicals based in Pakistan. All other sectors and levels of employees working at various functional levels in an organisation are excluded.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

The researchers do not expect the questions to cause any harm or discomfort to you. This study is considered to be risk-free. For that reason, you do not have to fear your association in this research project.

What information is being collected in the project?

The demographics of respondents will be collected during the process as well as background information in respect of education and professional life of the participants. Moreover, the researcher will strongly ensure that the information provided by the subject will be kept confidential and data will not be misused.

Who will have access to the information?

The information collected from the interview will remain confidential unless permitted by the participant. The confidentiality, anonymity, and privacy of the participants will be strongly ensured. The identity of the participants will not be disclosed and the identifiers will be assigned a code based on the numeric value. It will be kept protected while assuring the accessibility to the researcher only. The access, control and dissemination of data are also protected under the Data Protection Act 1998.

Where will the information be stored and how long will it be kept for?

The data collected from the participants will be used for a limited purpose. It will not be reserved for longer than is needed.

Thank you for reading this information – please ask any questions if you are unsure about what is written here.

All personal data will be processed in accordance with data protection legislation.

What happens next?

In case, you are interested in knowing the details of the project, please contact the researcher Ms. Qandeel Bhatti at the given email address. The outcomes of the research will be available to you upon request after the completion of the project.

Thank you again for taking the time to go through this information sheet, and looking forward to your anticipated involvement in the project.

Researcher contact details:

Researcher: Qandeel Bhatti

University of West of Scotland

London Campus

235 Southwark Bridge Road

London

United Kingdom

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Chief Investigator details:

**Chief Investigator: Dr David Burl
University of West of Scotland**

Paisley Campus

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Scotland

United Kingdom

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This research was granted ethical approval by the University of West of Scotland Ethics Committee.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the research, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

██

████████████████████

8.5 Appendix 5: Consent Form (CF)

Name of department: School of Business and Creative Studies, University of West of Scotland

Title of the study: How can the value chain and supply chain of SMEs and micro-businesses facilitate the development of economy of Pakistan?

- I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet for the above project and the researcher has answered any queries to my satisfaction.
- I confirm that I have read and understood the Privacy Notice for Participants in Research Projects and understand how my personal information will be used and what will happen to it (i.e. how it will be stored and for how long).
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, up to the point of completion, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.
- I understand that I can request the withdrawal from the study of some personal information and that whenever possible researchers will comply with my request. This includes the following personal data:
 - audio recordings of interviews that identify me; if any
 - my personal information from transcripts.
- I understand that anonymised data (i.e. data that do not identify me personally) cannot be withdrawn once they have been included in the study.
- I understand that any information recorded in the research will remain confidential and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.
- I consent to being a participant in the project.
- I consent to being audio recorded as part of the project (Yes / No).

(NAME)	
Signature of Participant:	Date:

